

CULNA 78

March 2024

**SAMUEL MAKOANYANE
(1909- 1944) artist in clay**

Curious Tiger flies of
Southern Africa

The Art of Bonsai: Cultivating
Nature in Miniature

36 Aliwal Street
 P.O. Box 266
 Bloemfontein 9300
 Tel: 051 447 9609
 Fax: 051 447 6273
 culna@nasmus.co.za
 www.nasmus.co.za

an agency of the
Department of Sport, Arts and Culture

Front cover

Ceramic sculpture by Samuel Makoanyane (1909-1944) of warrior Joshua Nau Makoanyane, great-grandfather of Samuele Makoanyane, and a military commander in King Moshoeshoe's army. Collection of the Iziko Museums of South Africa. Photographic rendition by Stephen Wessels (DIJONDESIGN photogrammetry specialist).

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Culna ke makasine wa hang ka selemo oo ho fanwang ka ona mahala ke Musiamo wa Setjhaba. Tlhahiso leseding tse phatlaladitsweng ka hare ho makasine ona di ka sebediswa ka pusoloso kapa tumello ya mohlodi. Maikuflo a hlahlisitsweng ke ao a bangodi mme ha kaalo ha se a bao ba Musiamo wa Setjhaba.

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Editorial Team

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Sharon Snell

Head of Design
Christo Venter

Language Editing
Dr Sirion Robertson

Language Editing
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Design & Layout
Carien van Eck

**Publications
Website Manager**
Monde Sithole

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A Message from the Editor

I am proud to congratulate the CULNA Magazine editorial team for bagging the 2023 award for best design for a publication. The National Museum won the coveted 87th SAMA: Publication Design Awards Competition. The artwork for the winning volume was done by Carien van Eck, who is the Museum's graphic designer. The Museum has an in-house award-winning Design Department.

the professionalisation of museums always starts with strong compliance and administration support. It allows for the seamless achievement of our primary objectives.

CULNA Editorial team from L to R. Christo Venter (Head of Design and Workshop), Monde Sithole (Graphic designer / Website Manager), Sharon Snell (Editor), Carien van Eck (Graphic designer / Artist) and Marelle van Rensburg (Senior Museum designer / Artist).

The contents of Volume 78 of CULNA Magazine reflects the busy year we had at the National Museum. One of our strategic outcomes is to generate and disseminate new knowledge about our natural, cultural, and ancient environments. In line with this, the Museum researchers publish both peer-reviewed and popular scientific publications. We also use the opportunity to create awareness around the significance of our special days on our calendar through research and exhibitions. It is for this reason, that some of the popular articles in this edition have specific themes.

I was chuffed when the Mr Zizi Kodwa, the Minister of Sport, Arts and Culture, recently congratulated the Museum for the achievement of its 3rd consecutive clean audit. For me,

CULNA Magazine is a popular scientific magazine which showcases Museum research in Human and Natural Science. CULNAonline is our online platform for popular scientific articles which was created to make Museum research readily available to the scientific community and the public free of charge. Article contributions to our magazine our welcome. To learn more visit our publications website www.nationalmuseumpublications.co.za.

Thank you to our creative Editorial team for this excellent edition of CULNA and CULNAonline. I had such fun editing Volume 78. I do hope you enjoy reading this edition.

Sharon Snell
Editor
culna@nasmus.co.za

Crocodiles:

facts, myths, and symbolism in Africa

By Loudine Philip

Image: Photograph by Sharath G. retrieved from <https://www.pexels.com/photo/close-up-shot-of-a-crocodile-11571391/>

Crocodiles are fascinating and fearsome creatures, and along with sharks today they are at the top of the food chain in the Animal Kingdom. Adult crocs have almost no natural enemies, apart from humans. Crocodiles are some of Earth's oldest inhabitants, descending about 94 million years ago from the non-avian reptiles—pseudosuchians—that appeared 248 million years ago. In addition to crocodiles, pseudosuchians included those archosaurs that were more closely related to crocodiles than to birds.

As their long existence suggests, pseudosuchians, and crocodiles in particular, have some unique features that ensured their survival through several

major natural disasters, which severely impacted the Earth's biodiversity. Massive volcanic eruptions at the end of the Triassic, that is approximately 200 million years ago, wiped out many, but not all, then dominant pseudosuchians and allowed the dinosaurs and pterosaurs to thrive. However, 66 million years ago a meteorite, which slammed into the sea near Mexico and resulted in what is today known as the Chicxulub Crater, caused a mass extinction that eradicated the dinosaur population, but spared the crocodiles! By that time, they already established themselves in aquatic habitats and looked pretty much as they do today.

What likely saved the crocodile for millions of years is its ability to

adjust to ever-changing and often adverse natural circumstances with adaptations developed during a slow process of evolution. Over time, the crocodile transformed its skin into a bony armour that covers most of its body, developed strong jaw muscles, a powerful immune system, behaviour to control its body temperature and advanced metabolism that helps utilize nearly all the food the crocodile consumes, which is why crocs can go for over a year without having a meal. Under extreme conditions, they can shut down and live off their fat reserves and muscle tissue for a long period of time. Their stomach is the most acidic of all vertebrates and crocs can eat almost anything, as they are able to

Image: Lesotho blanket depicting four crocodiles on a black background. This blanket may only be used by the royal house. (Collections Department, National Museum)

digest bones, horns, hooves, shells, and so forth – nothing is left behind. The hard objects help to grind coarse food and crocs will sometimes deliberately swallow pebbles to aid the process. This habit would later play a role in some of the cultural practices connected with crocodiles.

In this article, the focus is on the Nile crocodile (*Crocodylus niloticus*), which is often also referred to as the African Crocodile. Given its appearance and extraordinary characteristics, it is unsurprising that the crocodile occupies an important place in the cultural practices of several groups across Africa, starting from Egypt all the way down to South Africa. Since ancient times, the crocodile has been playing a significant role in the Egyptian society. Not only was it associated with Sobek, a divine protector and healer, but there is also evidence that crocodiles were bred as pets for the royal courts, as well as for their fat that was used as a medicine to alleviate physical aches, stiffness and even baldness. Due to the crocodile's sacred status, this muti was most likely reserved for royalty only. The Ancient Egyptian pantheon of gods and goddesses was quite impressive, with approximately 1500 names, but not fixed as new gods would appear and others would cease to be worshipped. Sobek had quite a long standing in the Egyptian pantheon from circa 2686 BCE up to the end of the Roman period at 350 CE – that is over 3000 years! Sobek was often depicted as a human with a crocodile head, but also in its natural form with no human features. It is, therefore, not strange that many of the excavated tombs contained mummified crocodiles. Over time, Sobek merged with other gods which served to lend him more power. During the reign of Amenemhat III (19th–18th centuries BCE; Twelfth Dynasty), for instance, Sobek was fused with Re-Harakhti (a solar deity) into Sobek-Re and depicted with a crocodile body and a falcon head.

Much further south we find another cultural group, the Venda, intimately connected to the crocodile. The Venda, or VhaVenda, people live in the present-day Limpopo Province

in South Africa, almost on the border with Zimbabwe. The Venda have a close spiritual association with water creatures and spirits, and Lake Funduzi, among others, features prominently in their stories. Lake Funduzi is situated at the foothills of the Soutbansberg, and a legend narrates that the lake was created by a curse when a passing leper was refused food and shelter in the village. The village was flooded and disappeared under the newly formed lake. Lake Funduzi does not only have a legendary white snake (python) but also a white crocodile, which guards the ghosts of the Venda ancestors who reside beneath the water surface. Venda chiefs would eat food cooked with pebbles from a crocodile's stomach during their installation ceremony in order to take on the powerful attributes of crocodiles. In the Venda culture, the crocodile is expressly associated with leaders.

Right on the Free State's doorstep is the landlocked country, the Kingdom of Lesotho. The Bakoena is one of the largest clans in Lesotho and its coat of arms bears a crocodile on a shield, flanked by two Basotho ponies. Ponies are a major form of transport for many in the rugged mountainous terrain of Lesotho, but this is not the natural habitat of the crocodile.

The crocodile is, however, symbolic of the Bakoena's place of origin in the region between the Mariko and Limpopo rivers, which are full of crocodiles. In Sesotho and Setswana, Bakoena literally means 'people who venerate the crocodile'. Moshoeshe I, the first king of Lesotho, was from the Bamokoteli (Mochuli) branch of the clan. Bakoena beliefs in terms of the crocodile are very similar to those of the early Egyptians.

Image: Sobek by Jeff Dahl - Own work, CC BY-SA 4.0 Image:

Lesotho coat of arms: Fenn-O-maniC - Own work, Wikimedia Public Domain

It is revered as a god, but whereas Egyptians would sometimes kill crocodiles for medicinal purposes, the Bakoena believe that killing a crocodile would adversely affect rain patterns, leading to either total drought or flooding. In addition, the crocodile is considered to be the Bakoena's godly father, so the deliberate killing of a crocodile amounts to murder.

The Lesotho coat of arms does not feature on its national flag, but it does decorate the royal standard. Lesotho is famous for its blankets and one design in particular has a crocodile motif, but that may only be worn by royalty. The National Museum has a beautiful collection of carved wooden crocodiles and a mummified crocodile head that served as a sheath for a dagger and is currently on display in the museum.

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The story of a priest called Venturi and a tractor manufactured a century later

Image: Giovanni Battista Venturi (1746 – 1822) source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Giovanni_Battista_Venturi

By Elmar du Plessis

Giovanni Battista Venturi was born in 1746 in Bibbiano, a small village in the Province of Reggio Emilia, Italy. At the age of 23, he was ordained as a Catholic priest and, in the same year, was appointed as a teacher of logic at the University of Reggio Emilia. In 1774, he moved to the University of Modena as a professor of geometry and philosophy. Over the next years, Venturi would also have success as a university-level mathematics instructor, a civil engineer, a politician, a statesman, a confidant of Napoleon I Bonaparte, and, in later years, as a renowned historian.

But perhaps his greatest achievement was made in 1797, with the publication of *Experimental Inquiries Concerning the Principle of the Lateral Communication of a Motion in Fluids*. Venturi discovered that fluids moving through a gradually narrowing pipe gain speed. Scientifically explained, it can be said that since the number of fluid molecules going in and coming out of the pipe is constant, they have to gather momentum in order to move through the constriction.

Venturi further noticed that at the same time when the fluid flowing through the constriction speeded up, the pressure the fluid exerted on the pipe walls dropped. In fact, the pressure is the lowest where the speed and constriction are the greatest, creating a partial vacuum. Known as the Venturi effect, this phenomenon is used to this day to move, push or drag one fluid by using nothing else than the motion of another – the “lateral communication of motion in fluids,” as Venturi described it.

The same phenomenon is observed in airflow. The Venturi effect predicts that a narrow air

passage or opening that acts as a constriction will force the flow of air from a high-pressure area through a low-pressure area (or constriction), hence creating a natural flow of air.

In 1909, nearly a hundred years after Venturi first published his findings, the Rumely Company launched its first tractor in La Porte, Indiana (USA).

Meinrad Rumely, who along with his brother Jacob founded the M. & J. Rumely Company in 1853, was a blacksmith turned agricultural equipment manufacturer. The company’s corn shellers and horse-drawn threshers were successful enough so M. & J. Rumely Co.

Image: Rumely “Oil Pull” tractor with its chimney-shaped radiator source: Elmar du Plessis

THE VENTURI EFFECT

Image: The Venturi effect source: <https://resources.system-analysis.cadence.com/blog/msa2022-explaining-the-venturi-effect-and-wind-flow-analysis-in-structural-design>

shortly afterward expanded its agricultural product lines and sales regions. In 1895, Rumely started building steam-powered traction engines and, by 1908, was experimenting with internal combustion tractors.

"Kerosene Annie" was Rumely's first prototype tractor built in 1909 and led the company to become the first American tractor manufacturer to use kerosene, a cheap petroleum-based fuel. However, Rumely tractors had many other unique features aside from the use of kerosene. For one, the Rumely "Oil Pull" used oil instead of water as a cooling medium to keep the engine at a steady temperature.

During the period of 1910–1930, four models of "Oil Pull" tractors were manufactured by Rumely. Around the same time, the tractor history in South Africa took off. Not that tractors had not already been used in South Africa, but the popularity of tractors increased especially during the 1920s with tractor manufacturers from all over the world, including Rumely, exporting their models to South Africa. The history collection of the National Museum possesses an example of one such Rumely "Oil Pull" tractor, a 20-30 model 'W'. The smallest of the super powered Rumely tractors, the 20-30 Rumely, first came into production in 1928. When production ended in 1930, 3 952 models had been manufactured. With its heavy duty, two cylinder engine it was claimed that the 'W' could put out 20 horsepower (hp) on the drawbar and 30hp on the belt, which was mostly used to power threshing machines and other agricultural equipment. Unfortunately, not much more is known about the 'W' in the collection other than that it was donated to the National Museum by the then *Vrystaatse Boerderymuseum*.

The Rumely "Oil Pull's" oil-cooling system, the most unique feature about Rumely's tractors, works largely the same way as a water-based cooling system, pumping the oil from the engine through the radiator before circulating the cool oil from the radiator back through the engine. The reason behind using oil instead of water is that kerosene engines tend to produce a lot more heat under load compared to petrol engines and oil has a much higher boiling temperature than water and does not freeze in the winter.

One may wonder what keeps the oil from overheating during the long hours when the engine is running as there is no fan in the radiator as with modern water-cooling systems. The answer is simple: the Venturi effect.

The shaft in which the Rumely "Oil Pull"'s radiator is built narrows towards the top, almost like a chimney. Therefore, taking advantage of the fact that air expands, becomes lighter and rises above cool air when heated, together with the constriction in the shaft, a low-pressure vacuum is created, causing fresh cool air to be sucked into the shaft and to push the hot air out through the constriction. Thus, the presence of the Venturi tube facilitates the constant circulation of air through the radiator, cooling the oil without the need for a fan. And now you also know why a chimney is shaped like a pyramid.

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SAMUEL MAKOANYANE

(1909- 1944)
artist in clay
from Lesotho

By J Dreyer

The Basotho people were always known for their innovative and creative range of indigenous crafts. Traditionally the women produced various forms of clay pottery, while the men cleverly plaited grass baskets and hats. These objects were marketed to foreign visitors in Maseru and elsewhere across the border in South Africa.

Image: Ceramic sculpture by Samuel Makoanyane (1909-1944) of warrior Joshua Nau Makoanyane, great-grandfather of Samuele Makoanyane, and a military commander in King Moshoeshoe's army. Collection of the Iziko Museums of South Africa. Photographic rendition by Stephen Wessels (DIJONDESIGN photogrammetry specialist).

Image: Ceramic sculpture by Samuel Makoanyane (1909-1944) of a woman playing a moropa drum. Kirby Collection, University of Cape Town. Photographic rendition by Stephen Wessels (DIJONDESIGN photogrammetry specialist). From the virtual exhibition *KE LIHA PENE – I lay down my pen* developed for the Iziko Museums of South Africa and the Lesotho National Museum and Art Gallery.

A severe drought during the 1930s and 1940s, resulting in poor crops, combined with various other intricate economic factors in Africa, created serious want and distress in Lesotho. An increasing number of people were forced to resort to other means of generating additional income. Samuel Makoanyane, a young man from Koalabata, exploited his skills in the modelling of clay figurines. Makoanyane started by producing a variety of clay models of animals copied from books. These included baboons, buck, tigers, lions, birds, and frogs. The frog turned out to be very popular and sold well during his trading travels to other villages and across the border in the Free State. Gradually other figures were added to Samuel's inventory. A visit by Pagel's Circus to Maseru inspired the production of a series on elephants.

Samuel increasingly turned his attention to human figures. He succeeded in depicting Chief Moshoeshoe and his commanding warrior, Makoanyane, in fine detail, incorporating a considerable amount of historical and cultural authenticity. These models became extremely popular, eventually numbering several hundred in total. Samuel produced only a few figures of Europeans, mostly of his acquaintances in the service of the Roman Catholic Church of which he was a member. People who recognised Samuel's ability to model from life encouraged him to establish himself in portraying his own people going about their daily chores. He went on to make the various types of

Basotho figures for which he eventually gained acclaim. He made a great effort to manufacture the Basotho weapons of his figures as close to the originals as possible. The knobkierie for instance, was carved from wood, the tuft of feathers on the forehead (*sekola*) and war stick (*mokhele*) came from small birds and the skin for the shield (*thebe*) from a rat or mouse.

Prices were limited during the initial stages, with figures selling at 3 to 4 shillings each. Later, single objects earned up to 8 shillings and eventually the price was increased to 21 shillings. Figurines made on special commission were not always to Samuel's own benefit because of the time it took to perfect a new figure. Nevertheless, in 1936 he took on his first commission from the renowned Prof. Percival Kirby of the University of the Witwatersrand, to produce a sequence on traditional Basotho musical instruments. This resulted in a series of seven figures, each playing a different musical instrument. A specific figure of interest was a woman playing the initiation drum (*Moropa*).

In the same year a request came from Dr W.T. Beukes, ethnologist at the Transvaal Museum, to provide models for display during the British Empire Exhibition. Samuel put his best into this, trying to take full advantage of the opportunity to advertise his potential. Although not completely satisfied with the results, he managed to supply several figures of

warriors and women carrying babies. This could also be the origin of the warrior figurine in the anthropology collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein.

The year 1938 saw one of his crocodile models being sent to an arts and crafts exhibition at Grahamstown, together with examples of the work of a basket maker and a woman who specialised in making clay heads. Interestingly enough, the other objects were highly rated, but the crocodile was not sold and had to be returned to Lesotho. Despite such periodic setbacks, Samuel's work seemed to become known in South Africa and regularly emerged in places such as Johannesburg, Pretoria, East London, Bloemfontein, Kimberley, and Fort Hare. A curio dealer from Victoria Falls in Rhodesia (Zimbabwe) also showed interest.

Outside the continent Samuel's work formed part of exhibitions in New York and Paris in 1935, exposures which assisted to distribute his work and establish Makoanyane's name in America, England, Ireland, Scotland, and France. From his own people Samuel experienced a constant demand for certain figures. They often reacted in wonder to the skill of their countryman. The popular demand for models of crocodiles, the totem of the greater part of the inhabitants of Lesotho, could hardly be satisfied.

It is possible that because certain local people could be recognized in his models, some observed him with suspicion. Nevertheless, it is known that he had two great admirers among his own people. Chief Theko Makhaola of Qacha's Nek and Chief Jeremiah Moshoeshe of Mpharane in East Griqualand were keen collectors of Samuel's work, the latter

even presenting General Smuts with a number of these models. In retrospect Samuel Makoanyane was successful from the beginning. He was undoubtedly talented and developed his own individual style. His models were carefully made and particularly true to life. His work proved to be innovative and remarkable, and his creations did not fall into the ordinary range of curio manufacturing. True to the nature of artists, Samuel was never satisfied with his creations, always aspiring to improve on technique and innovation while aiming for the perfection which he did not recognise in himself.

Despite all the acclaim for his work, Makoanyane remained a very humble person. He did not like people watching while he was at work and constantly discouraged visits to his workplace by claiming that his "office" was very untidy. Samuel also remained a very reserved person, preferring to work or to play with a football all by himself. He never married but cared for his brothers and other next of kin. It is said that he did not own livestock, but granted himself little luxuries in food and clothing, expressing his artistic nature in colour and individuality.

Samuel Makoanyane was born in about 1909 near Parys in the Free State where his father worked at the time. In 1913 the family returned to Lesotho, to settle in Chief Majara's village at Koalabata, near Berea in the district of Teyateyaneng. In later years Samuel developed a chest illness which became serious over time. During 1942, he had to attend a TB hospital in Johannesburg for treatment. He returned to Lesotho where he passed away on 24 October 1944 and was buried at Koalabata where his grave is still to be seen.

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This article is a reprint from the 1999 edition of CULNA.

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Image: Ceramic sculpture by Samuel Makoanyane (1909-1944) of a woman feeding a baby. Collection of the Iziko Museums of South Africa. Photographic rendition by Stephen Wessels (DIJONDESIGN photogrammetry specialist). From the virtual exhibition *KE LIHA PENE – I lay down my pen* developed for the Iziko Museums of South Africa and the Lesotho National Museum and Art Gallery.

Samuele Makoanyane, Warrior, circa 1930s, clay (East London Museum). PhotoCredit: ShanBright Photography

KE LIHA PENE

- a tribute to Samuele Makoanyane

By Goslame 'Amy' Goitsemodimo

Oliewenhuis Art Museum held a temporary exhibition entitled *Ke Liha Pene* - a tribute to Samuele Makoanyane. The exhibition focused on the small clay warrior figurines made by Samuele Makoanyane (1909-1944) between the late 1930s and early 1940s. Samuele was born in Parys, Free State province, but he lived and worked at the village of Koalabata, in the Teyateyaneng district of Lesotho. He is renowned for making about 250 warrior figurines that resemble his great grandfather, Joshua Nao Makoanyane, a commanding general in King Moshoeshoe's army. He also made 150 in the image of King Moshoeshoe.

Samuele was a self-taught artist who began his career at an early age making clay models of animals and then ventured into making human figurines. His friend, agent and biographer, C G Damant, encouraged him to focus on depicting his own people. He created various figurines that included men and women going on with their daily activities (e.g., women carrying pots or breastfeeding babies), musicians playing traditional instruments etc. The figurines of musicians, which are now part of the Kirby Collection at the College of Music in Cape Town, were made for Professor Percival Kirby in the

1930s. Prof Kirby had commissioned Makoanyane to create eight figurines of Basotho musicians playing traditional musical instruments, but Samuele only managed to make seven.

Each figurine is finely made and most feature important Basotho national symbols such as the blankets and hats. The warriors are depicted in their regalia (headdresses, copper gorget and etc) carrying weapons (shield, spear, battle axe), while the musicians are playing various instruments. The sizes of the figurines range from about 8 to 18 cm in height, a recommendation made by Damant after Makoanyane's bigger sculptures became difficult to transport and handle. Most of his work was sold through trading stores in Lesotho and South Africa. It is also found in the collections at the Iziko Museums of South Africa, Museum Africa in Johannesburg, the Duggan-Cronin Gallery in Kimberley, the East London Museum, Killie Campbell Museum in Durban, and the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

The exhibition comprised of warrior sculptures on loan from various institutions as well as the regalia and weapons commonly associated with Basotho warriors, particularly his great grandfather. This includes the headdress

(sekola), a copper gorget (khau), stabbing assegai/ spear (lerumo), great plume (mokhele), shield (thebe), battle axe (koakoa) etc. It was curated by Steven Sack, who first came across Makoanyane's work in 1988 when he curated the exhibition "The Neglected Tradition: Towards a New History of South African Art 1930-1988" at the Johannesburg Art Gallery. Steven has been fascinated by the artist ever since. Steven mentions that the "exhibition involves the rethinking of the Makoanyane collections in public institutions, as they migrate from social history collections and museums into the discursive space of the art museum - and thus the recognition of Samuele Makoanyane as an artist".

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Filling a blank page in the
history of
Mozambican
biodiversity: Scientists discover new
dung beetle species from Mabu Forest

By Gimo Daniel

Fig. 4: A Landscape view of Mabu Forest, Zambézia, Mozambique.

In April 2022, I led the first biological expedition focusing on dung beetles at Mount Mabu in the Zambézia Province of Mozambique. The expedition team was composed of Dr Werner Strümpfer (Ditsong Museum of Natural History), Mr Isildo Nganhane (Universidade Lúrio, Mozambique) and I (PI of the project – Fig. 1). Werner and I flew from South Africa to Nampula (northern Mozambique), and Isildo took a bus from Maputo to Nampula. We hired a company that drove us from Nampula to the village of Tacuane (Zambézia Province, Mozambique). There is no road from Tacuane to Mount Mabu, thus, we hired local porters to carry our camping/kitchen gear and fieldwork equipment (Fig. 2). We took eight hours of hiking from Tacuane to the camping site inside of Mabu Forest.

Mabu Forest is located in Zambézia Province, central Mozambique, comprising a chain of two mountains: Mount Namurothone in the foothills and Mount Mabu in the uphills. Mabu Forest includes c. 7,880 ha block of undisturbed rainforest, mostly at medium altitude (900–1,400 m), a forest type that is not well represented elsewhere (Figs. 3–4). It is the largest continuous block of medium-altitude forest in southern Africa; with patches at higher altitudes reaching approximately 1700 m a.s.l. The foothills are clothed in dense transitional woodland, bamboo and riparian forest to at least 300 m a.s.l (Daniel *et al.*, 2023; Bayliss *et al.*, 2014).

Mabu Forest was originally inhabited by hunters of the *Manhawa* Bantu ethnic group. *Mabu* means “beekeeping” in the native *eManhawa* language, which alludes to a community of beekeepers. However, nowadays, Mabu Forest is sometimes referred to as the Google Forest as it was “discovered” by western explorers through Google Earth or the Butterfly Forest because of the butterfly hill-topping on the summit at a certain period of the year.

Why dung beetles? Firstly, dung beetles are the prettiest creature in nature. Also, these beetles are mainly coprophagous, conducting a series of ecological processes and environmental services, such as secondary seed dispersal, control of other insects or parasite suppression, dung and nutrient recycling in ecosystems and subsequent increasing of soil fertility (Scholtz *et al.* 2009; Nichols *et al.*, 2008) – which is important to other creatures, including humans, making them an important topic for investigation. However, these ecosystem processes can only be studied and understood when the constituent species are known. Secondly, surveys of dung beetles are frequently used to determine faunal patterns and are bioindicators of environmental quality in an area, owing to the relative cheap and easy way of obtaining quantitative data using baited pitfall traps and their sensitivity to differences in macroclimate, soil type, vegetation cover and microhabitat parameters (Davis *et al.*, 2004; Nichols *et al.* 2007).

Why Mozambique and Mabu Forest? Only 326 species of dung beetles have been recorded in Mozambique (Daniel *et al.*, 2023; Daniel & Génier 2019). However, the number of species reflects at the most half of the country’s diversity because many dung beetle surveys focus on southern Mozambique and Gorongosa National Park. In contrast,

Fig. 1. Dr Gimo Daniel – Museum Scientist and National Geographical Society Explorer conducting dung beetle survey at Mount Mabu.

other areas of the country are poorly known. On the other hand, the increasing development, including land-use drivers, fragmentation, global climate change, direct overexploitation, and co-extinction of species dependent on other species are threats to biodiversity, as well as insect declining globally (Hallmann *et al.*, 2017; Cardoso *et al.* 2020). Thus, it is critical that biodiversity surveys are expanded to remote and unsampled areas, especially “sky-island forests”, like Mount Mabu.

My curiosity about dung beetle exploration at Mount Mabu began in 2012, as an MSc student at the Federal University of Grande Dourados, Brazil, when I read about previous expeditions on plants, mammals, reptiles and butterflies, where at least 20 new species on these taxa were discovered. Based on the information of the previous expeditions and biogeographical isolation of the region, I was expecting many new dung beetle species to be discovered. As rightly predicted, within 15 days of a biological exploration, we collected over 4000 specimens of dung beetles from 30 species, of which half are new to science, and several are new country records (Figs. 5–6). Other novelties will likely increase in number with more detailed examination of material by fellow specialists. Most importantly, many dung beetle species collected on the expedition seem to be restricted (endemic) to this sky-

Fig. 2: Local community supporting our dung beetle expedition.

island forest. For those species widely distributed are at the southern limit of their range – with these exciting findings, I can assure you that I am filling a blank page in the history of Mozambican biodiversity. Also, it is a call to national and international authorities to protect Mount Mabu and its rare and distinctive biodiversity.

Identifying these species is just the first step. My ultimate goal is to understand how these species are collectively inserted into a historical context of the evolution of African dung beetles, including its relationships in time and space with insect fauna from other sky-island forests in northern Mozambique, such as Mount Namuli, Mount Chiperone, Mount Rico and Mount Ribaué.

Fig. 6. A new *Onthophagus* dung beetle species collected at Mount Mabu.

Fig. 3-4: A Landscape view of Mabu Forest, Zambézia, Mozambique.

Fig. 5. A new flightless *Janssensantus* dung beetle species collected at Mount Mabu.

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The Art of Bonsai:

Cultivating Nature in Miniature

By Oladayo A. Idris

Eurya emarginata (Japanese common name: Hama-hi-sakaki) bonsai on display at the National Bonsai and Penjing Museum at the United States National Arboretum, Washington, DC, USA. This bonsai tree has been trained to this shape since 1970. It was donated to the Museum by Susumu Nakamura. Photo by Ragesoss, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=2555389>.

Imagine a living work of art, a miniature tree that evokes a sense of tranquillity and harmony with nature. Such is the allure of the bonsai tree, an enchanting creation that captures the hearts of nature enthusiasts and artists alike. Bonsai, derived from the Japanese words *bon*, meaning tray or pot, and *sai*, meaning planting, or to plant, is a centuries-old practice of growing and nurturing trees in shallow containers, transforming them into exquisite living sculptures.

The history of bonsai can be traced back to the ancient China and other areas in East and Southeast Asia, where it was originally known as *penjing*. *Penjing* is a Chinese word for a landscape or scene (*jing*) in a pot, and is often used to denote miniature landscapes. *Penjing* incorporates natural elements like rocks, water, figurines, and occasionally other plants in a container with the tree(s) to mimic the pristine vegetation. The Japanese later adopted and improved this art, elevating it to a level known today as *bonsai*, which focuses on a single or more trees of the same species.

The ancient art of bonsai involves meticulous shaping and pruning suitable trees to achieve a desired aesthetic while maintaining their natural growth patterns. Through a careful combination of natural and controlled cultivation techniques, arborists (specialists in the care of trees) instill a sense of age, beauty and harmony in these miniature trees. This is a delicate balance that requires horticultural knowledge, artistic sensibility and patience, all of which are imbued in the ethnocultural traditions of East Asian societies and passed down from generation to generation. Despite the fact that bonsai trees are not grown for food or medicine, their care requires commitment, attention to detail and a great deal of time. This may have been one of the cultural practices intended by the Chinese and Japanese alike to teach resiliency, patience, persistence and consistency.

The bonsai process begins with selecting a suitable tree species that can thrive in a container environment. On average, bonsai trees grown from seed will take 10–15 years to mature, with most tree species requiring about 30 years to be considered a fully mature bonsai. As is the case with a variety of tree species, bonsais can outlive humans who planted them! The lifespan of a bonsai tree depends largely on what species it is and the care it receives. The oldest known bonsai is *Ficus retusa*, commonly called Indian Laurel, which was acquired from Taiwan and is currently displayed in the Crespi Bonsai Museum in Italy. It is estimated to be over 1000 years old!

In South Africa, the most popular bonsai are exotic species, as many enthusiasts want a bonsai that makes them feel connected to tropical climates, which are difficult to find in the country. Common choices include the Chinese Elm

(*Ulmus parvifolia*), Cork Oak (*Quercus suber*), Chinese Juniper (*Juniperus chinensis*) and trees of the genera *Bougainvillea* and *Ficus*. There are also several local tree species that South Africans grow as bonsai, including Acacias, Kei Apple (*Dovyalis caffra*), White Stinkwood (*Celtis africana*) and Weeping Boer-bean (*Schotia brachypetala*). The majority of South African adopted bonsai species are hardy and capable of withstanding arid conditions. However, each species has its own distinct characteristics and requirements. It is, therefore, necessary to research each species to understand its particular needs. It is important to note that a great deal of horticultural skill is needed to succeed on the journey to bonsai mastery.

Most bonsais, like other trees, grow best in semi-shade, preferably outdoors in the garden, where they receive plenty of sunlight. However, some species enjoy full sun, while others prefer full shade with natural light, and some can survive several months indoors despite being deprived of natural light and ultraviolet radiation.

Nevertheless, like most trees, bonsais enjoy seasonal weather variation. Therefore, the fundamental technique used to create bonsai is based on the prior knowledge of the tree cultivation, with perpetual pruning and shaping of branches and roots to help maintain the tree's size and shape, while wiring allows the artist to guide its growth, creating the illusion of a full-sized tree in miniature. Watering and fertilising are also important aspects of the bonsai care. They are crucial for maintaining nutrients and moisture as bonsai trees are restricted to what is available in their containers. However, overwatering can lead to root rot, while underwatering can cause dehydration and damage to the tree tissues and organs. Adding appropriate nutrients ensures that the tree receives the nourishment it needs to flourish. A carefully planned watering, fertilising and pruning schedule are vital to sustaining the tree's health.

The bonsai process begins with selecting a suitable tree species that can thrive in a container environment.

Beyond its artistic allure, bonsai holds great cultural and philosophical significance. In Japanese culture, bonsai represents the harmony among man, nature and the divine. It symbolises patience, contemplation and the appreciation of the fleeting beauty of life. Recently, bonsai trees have captured the interest of many and gained popularity worldwide, including various parts of Africa. Bonsai trees are often displayed in homes and gardens, providing a connection to nature and a source of serenity. It is also believed that its appearance can induce physiological relaxation.

New market opportunities have emerged for small-scale business owners and artisans all over the world in response to the recent increase in bonsai demand. This also calls for the need for associations to govern and regulate the market space. The African Bonsai Association (ABA), established in the 1980s, was among the 32 founding countries in

This Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) bonsai is about 50 years old and is displayed at the Bonsai Museum in Pescia, Italy. Photo by Saiko, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=72786081>.

Chinese Elm (*Ulmus parvifolia*) bonsai, about 100 years old. It is displayed at the Bonsai Museum in Pescia, Italy. Photo by Saiko, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=72786092>.

April 1989 at the inaugural meeting of the World Bonsai Friendship Federation (WBFF) in Osaka, Japan, where a drafted constitution was presented. Since then, the ABA has been representing Africa and will do so at the 10th World Bonsai Convention, which the WBFF will be hosting in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, in August 2026. The South African Bonsai

Sargent Juniper bonsai (*Juniperus chinensis*), also known as Shimpaku Juniper in Japan. Displayed since 1976 at the National Bonsai and Penjing Museum, United States National Arboretum, Washington, DC, USA. Photo: <https://www.bonsaiempire.com/blog/expensive-bonsai>.

Association and two other South African groups, the Eastern Bonsai Society and Bonsai Addicts, work together to host regional conferences. Meetings such as the Fifth African Bonsai Convention, hosted in Pretoria in October 2019, present information on our indigenous South African bonsai tree species, popularize the industry and attract both local and international tourists, thus generating revenue.

There is a high demand for bonsai worldwide, including Africa, with some trees selling for thousands of dollars. For instance, the Sargent Juniper bonsai on display at the National Bonsai and Penjing Museum in Northeast Washington, DC, United States, cost \$350 000 (equivalent to over 6.5 million Rands). The naturally serene appearance of this exemplar also inspired the Museum's logo. Bonsai trees have not just generated employment opportunities in the artisan industries but have also significantly influenced the cultural fabric of many societies in the world by infusing a divine harmony between humanity and nature.

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“Badge of servitude”:

Black People and Passbooks in Republican Bloemfontein (1854–1899)

Image 2: View of Waaihoek from Queen's Fort, 1905. (Photo: National Museum)

By Derek du Bruyn

For many black¹ people who have lived through apartheid (1948–1994), the hated passbooks they had to carry every day is emblematic of their traumatic experiences of that time. Although the passbook is synonymous with apartheid, the ideology behind it is much older. The system by which black people were compelled to carry some form of identification when they either lived in, or visited, “whites-only” South Africa, dates back to Bloemfontein’s republican period (1854–1899). Ordinance No. 5 of 1866 required that all male subjects of Moshoeshoe I (Image 1), Paramount Chief of the Basotho and first king of Lesotho, were required to carry a pass (called “pas” in Dutch) when they travelled through the Orange Free State republic or visited any town within its boundaries, including Bloemfontein. Not long after this ordinance was implemented, the pass requirement was extended to residents of Bloemfontein’s so-called “locations”.² In 1872, a municipal regulation declared that “... every colored [sic] or native servant in the town must be provided with a printed ticket, signed by his master, setting forth that he is employed as a daily, monthly, or yearly servant”. The regulation warned that all found without a ticket “... will hereafter be treated by the landdrost [magistrate] as

squatters, and be punished or removed accordingly”. After that, the practice of regulating and controlling the lives of black people by means of something tangible such as a ticket, became an effective tool in the hands of white authorities to monitor race relations in Bloemfontein.

The ticket in question was a printed card that had to be obtained at “... the Town-clerk at the Town-house”, to quote *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*. Residents of Waaihoek (Image 2), Bloemfontein’s oldest location at the time, who thought they could get away with not carrying a ticket or so-called “card”, had a rude awakening when members of the local police conducted unexpected stop-and-searches. In 1876, *The Express and Orange Free State Advertiser*, which was published in English and Dutch, reported that local constables arrested two people of colour “... omdat zij zonder passen waren” (“because they were without passes”). The guilty parties were arrested and taken to the local prison where they had to spend one night in “... de slechte atmosfeer van het donker gat” (“the bad atmosphere of the dark dungeon”). Noteworthy is the use of the Dutch word “passen” (“passes”); subsequently, the English word “pass”

1 In this article, the terms “black(s)” or “black people” refer to all people of colour who were legally and socially discriminated against on the basis of race.

2 In the historical South African context, the term “location” referred to a segregated living area for people of colour. Locations – today known as “townships” – were usually situated on the margins of “whites-only” towns and cities.

Image 1: Moshoeshe I, Paramount Chief of the Basotho, undated. (Photo: National Museum)

Image 3: Carl Borckenhagen, undated. (Photo: National Museum)

was used interchangeably with the term "ticket" to describe the identity card.

While the lives of Bloemfontein's black workforce were severely affected by the pass regime, it also inconvenienced white employers. Needless to say, Bloemfontein's white "masters" and

"mistresses", as white employees were known then, were upset when their workers did not pitch for work because they were arrested and jailed for not having a ticket. Carl Borckenhagen (**Image 3**), editor of *De Express en Oranjevrijstaatsch/e Advertentieblad* (commonly known as *De Express*), complained about the "... so one-sided and objectionable law as our 'Ticket Law'". According to Borckenhagen it took him two hours to release his worker "... from the filth of our *tronk* [prison]", only to hear that the arrest was a mistake. Borckenhagen's employee was not the last person who was arrested for not having a ticket. In fact, during the 1880s unannounced police raids became commonplace in Waaihoek and in Kaffirfontein, Bloemfontein's other old location. In 1882, *De Express* reported of a police raid in Kaffirfontein in which 500 people were found without tickets. Reportedly, the first three were fined £1 each, after which the remaining 497 applied for tickets at once. In 1884, the same newspaper reported of another raid in Kaffirfontein in which the police "... arrested a large number of boys who were without – or in possession of improper – passes". The "pass-less", as they were described, were fined "... 5s. [shillings] each or three days rice water".

During the 1880s it had become clear that the pass system was not only used to control the movement and lodgings of Bloemfontein's black people but also to ensure the availability of a permanent supply of cheap labour for whites. Article 15 of the *Regulations for the Natives within the Bloemfontein Municipality* (1882), which dealt with the pass issue, was strictly enforced. These regulations referred to the compulsory carrying of a so-called "certificate" which had to be obtained from the Town Clerk and cost the bearer six pennies. In a leading article *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* of 3 May 1883 echoed the sentiments of most white residents when it stated that those location residents who were residing in Waaihoek or Kaffirfontein "... without either ticket or master, should be unearthed and punished with a fine if they did not at once get a

baas". It boiled down to the following: without a baas [white employer] a black person had no right to reside in the locations because such living areas were exclusively for those who were in the full-time employ of whites. To deter black people from outside Bloemfontein to stay on and eventually reside in the locations, Municipal Notice No. 9 of 1884 (**Image 4**) informed "farmers and others" that no black person will be able to enter Bloemfontein "... unless provided with a Pass from his Master". Not only was such a pass valid for one visit only but a special police force was formed to enforce this new regulation.

Image 4: The Bloemfontein Municipality's Notice No. 9 of 1884. (Source: *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*)

In order to enforce the pass system effectively, Bloemfontein's Town Council increasingly resorted to police action in the form of raids and stop-and-searches. In 1883, *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* reported of a police raid in Waaihoek which saw "native servants" being marched to "... the Landdrost's [Magistrate's] office, because they had either lost their Municipal ticket, or because they had none". The newspaper wryly referred to the inferior "card-board"

ticket as a "badge of servitude". Any employee who failed to comply with the ticket regulations was liable to a fine of "... from 6d. [pennies] to £2 sterling". Because of the rapid increase of Bloemfontein's black population, especially after the opening of the Cape Town-Johannesburg railway in 1890, the carrying of passes became a challenge to police because of the sheer numbers of those who had to be policed every day. Since 1895, Bloemfontein's black population exceeded the white population. The challenges notwithstanding, the pass regime became the Town Council's most effective tool to enforce influx control. Law No. 8 of 1893 confirmed this because Article 2 required every male and female location resident above the age of 16 to carry a "*verblijf brief*" ("residential pass") at all times.

During the 1890s, police raids in Waaihoek and Kaffirfontein had become a disturbingly regular phenomenon. In 1893, members of the municipal police made an "... *inval op Waaihoek*" ("raid on Waaihoek") which saw 50 people arrested for not having an "*Inboorling Ticket*" ("Native Ticket") on them. Because these raids and the concomitant arrestation of pass-less domestic servants greatly inconvenienced their white employers, Bloemfontein's law enforcement officers were confronted with the latter's "*slechte humeuren*" ("bad tempers"). While the police raids certainly angered Bloemfontein's white employers who had to bail out their employees, the pass laws and police raids greatly disrupted the lives of location residents. In addition, they were subjected to police harassment and to the most brutal and inhumane treatment at the hands of law enforcement officers. Black people being marched off to Bloemfontein's "*Landdrost Hof*" ("Magistrate's Court") like "driven cattle" was not an uncommon sight, to quote *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*.

Needless to say, the treatment Bloemfontein's black residents received from the local police caused much indignation. Such was their outrage

and discontent that a deputation from Waaihoek visited Bloemfontein's Mayor, Mr S.P.J. Sowden³ (**Image 5**) in 1897. Members of the deputation complained, among others, about "... children being stopped by the police and asked for their tickets". The Mayor was surprised to learn that black children as young as 14 years required a ticket. Despite the deputation's plea, the Mayor dismissed their grievances as "... more of sentiment" but, nevertheless, he promised to investigate the issue. Waaihoek residents who were familiar with the white political "sentiment" of that time did not expect much to come from this deputation. Therefore, some of them voiced their outrage by writing letters to the newspapers. One Waaihoek resident, who wrote under the pseudonym "Your Eye-witness", did not mince his/her words when he/she complained about the police "... going into houses, dragging old women out", among other things. This letter, titled "Native Cry", echoed the emotions and

Image 5: Mayor S.P.J. Sowden, 1898.
(Photo: National Museum)

sentiments of most location residents: "Is it a law to go inside the houses and catch people?", they asked.

Towards the end of the 19th century it appeared as if the question posed by "Your Eye-witness" remained unanswered, at least for Bloemfontein's location residents. In fact, police raids in the locations and arrests of pass-less residents continued unabated while the authorities looked the other way. In June 1899 – mere months before the outbreak of the Anglo-Boer War (1899–1902) – *De Express* reported of yet another police raid in Waaihoek where "... forty natives, male and female" were arrested. The War brought more suffering and hardship for Bloemfontein's black people who still had to carry passes. At the same time, however, the War also brought a glimmer of hope for them when it became evident that the British, and not the Boers, would be the conquerors and rulers in the Orange Free State capital.

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The Rufous-eared Warbler

- a small prinia -
like species associated with
karroid shrub vegetation

By Dawie de Swardt

Image: The Rufous-eared Warbler (*Malcorus pectoralis* subsp. *ocularis*) from the Paul Roux area, Free State, showing a wider chest band. (Photo: Martin Potgieter)

Imagine you are busy birding and walking in a field with low shrub vegetation in the southern Free State or in the Central Karoo and your attention is drawn to a constantly high pitched *tee-tee-tee* bird sound near you. Suddenly a small prinia-like bird with a long tail flies out of a low bush or runs like a mouse in front of you.

This bird is likely to be the elusive Rufous-eared Warbler...

The Rufous-eared Warbler, or *Malcorus pectoralis*, is a small prinia-like bird of the family Cisticolidae, weighing a mere 10 grams, which occurs mainly in the Karoo, arid to semi-arid shrublands, as well as in old cultivated fields or overgrazed grassland with low shrub species. The Rufous-eared Warbler's distribution in

the field is very similar to the overlapping Karoo and Black-chested Prinias and Grey-backed Cisticolas, which can share the same habitat in some areas. The warblers are very attractive, occurring mostly singly or in small family groups, and are sometimes difficult to spot as they feed low in the bush or on the ground in the scrubby vegetation, and are only seen when flying low or even running (like mice) to the next bush clump. They also like to perch on fence lines in its preferred habitat.

This species has adapted to the semi-arid vegetation, which is unsuitable for agriculture, and is often seen in vacated cultivated fields that has been taken over by low shrub species. Therefore, the Rufous-eared Warbler can possibly be regarded as an indicator for disturbed and overgrazed veld in some areas of its distribution range. No major differences in the species distribution have been noted between the two South African Bird Atlas Projects of the late 1980s – early 1990s and the current project, which started in mid-2007, although its range seems to get expanded to Gauteng, and the birds are also becoming more common in the western Lesotho and in the Rosendal – Paul Roux – Lindley areas of the central-eastern Free State, possibly due to changes in the veld conditions making the habitats suitable for Rufous-eared Warblers. In these areas the birds mostly prefer a poorly managed grassland invaded by *Felicia filifolia* subsp. *filifolia* (Persbergdraaibos).

Rufous-eared Warbler diet, behaviour and vocalisations

This species mostly forages on the ground or in low shrubs searching for insects on the stems and leaves, but also consumes small fruits and seeds of Wild Asparagus, Honey-thorns and alien creeping salt bushes. Diet studies based on the stomach contents by the late Dr Richard Dean in the Central Karoo (Prince Albert) revealed mainly invertebrates such as weevils and other beetles, caterpillars, several ant species, spiders and even ticks, to name a few. The birds typically occur in small family groups. During the breeding season the male mostly sits on top of a bush and gives its monotonous *tee-tee* call repeated for long periods and audible from afar. Their breeding season usually lasts during the summer months between September – December, but the egg laying can commence after a good rainfall in some areas and breeding can be initiated in any month, even during the late winter. When the incubating female is disturbed from her

nest, she will flee by running from the nest rather than flying away as other birds mostly do.

The Rufous-eared Warbler builds a small, oval nest with a side-top entrance. The nest is woven with grass leaves, stems and silky bark, bound with spider web and lined with plant down, mostly fluffy seeds of Karoo Rosemary in the Central Karoo. The nests are situated less than a metre above the ground in the bush, with some being at as low as 20 cm high. When selecting nest sites, the birds prefer the Driedoring shrubs, but may also choose other shrub species such as *Pteronia* (Resin Daisies), *Rosinia* (Doringvygie) and *Galenia* (Bloubrakbossie), depending on the area. The eggs are laid in clutches of 3 or 4 and hatch after 12–13 days; the young are fledged and ready to leave the nest in 11–13 days. The nestlings are fed by both parents with mostly small grasshoppers and caterpillars. The Rufous-eared Warbler nests are also exposed to predators such as snakes, mainly Common Egg-Eaters, which prey on the eggs.

Plumages and geographical variation of the Rufous-eared Warbler

As its name suggests, the bird has a bright rufous face patch, a white throat and a black breast band, of which the face patch is brighter in males and the throat band is narrower in females. In some individuals, the breast band can also be reduced or absent during the winter months. Their long, slender and graduated tail feathers, with buff edges on the outer webs, are often held cocked and are diagnostic. Some geographical variation occurs in the plumage of this warbler, manifesting mainly in the paleness of the underparts, the width of the pectoral band, the presence or absence of streaking on its flanks, and in the intensity of its back plumage streaking. Based on these differences three subspecies, or geographical variations, are recognised, namely *M. p. pectoralis*, *M. p. ocularius* and *M. p. etoshae*:

Image: The Rufous-eared Warbler (*Malcorus pectoralis* subsp. *pectoralis*) from Witmoskloof, Cradock, Eastern Cape, showing a narrower chest band, which can vary individually. (Photo: Martin Potgieter)

- The nominate subspecies, or "*M. p. pectoralis*", occurs mostly in the Karoo areas of the Western and Northern Cape extending further eastwards to the Eastern Cape and northwards to the Free State, with its range limit along the line south of Kimberley – Bloemfontein – Wepener adjacent to the lowland areas of western Lesotho. This subspecies is the darkest Rufous-eared Warbler; its upperparts are brown-grey with a heavily streaked back. Their cheeks and ear coverts are rich chestnut and the breast is grey with streaking on its flanks. Their lower belly is pale buff grey with warm brown lower flanks. The pectoral band is wider than in the "*M. p. ocularius*" subspecies, although can vary individually.
- The "*ocularius*" subspecies ranges from areas north of the Kimberley – Bloemfontein – Wepener line and eastwards to the eastern Free State – Senekal – Paul Roux – Lindley, northwards to the southern Gauteng, and further west to the North West Province, Northern Cape, Botswana and Namibia south of Windhoek. This subspecies plumage is paler compared to the nominate subspecies, with its upper parts paler brown and ear coverts with a rustier golden-brown appearance. The birds of *M. p. ocularis* are also whiter on their lower belly with a narrower pectoral band (which also can vary individually) and unstreaked flanks.
- The *etoshae* subspecies occurs in the northern parts of Namibia, mainly north of Windhoek towards the Etosha Pan and southern Ovamboland. With their ear coverts being paler and the breast and belly feathers

more creamy white, the birds of *M. p. etoshae* are considerably paler than the other two subspecies. The black pattern of the crown feathers in *etoshae* has wider margins than the other two subspecies.

As both the "*pectoralis*" and "*ocularius*" subspecies occur in the Free State, the Ornithology Department of the National Museum launched a project to clarify their relationships. The departmental skin collection includes specimens of previously collected Rufous-eared Warblers in different areas of the Free State, which have been measured to obtain biometric data for the comparative analysis. Additional biometric data of ringed individuals of this species will be obtained during scheduled field trips to various parts of the Free State and possibly adjacent areas in Eastern and Northern Cape. Preliminary results suggest that the "*pectoralis*" subspecies probably have a longer tarsus compared to "*ocularius*", although further data are needed to be more certain. The chest band is also to be measured to determine if any differences exist between the subspecies, as well as between the sexes.

Furthermore, the project aims to compare the mitochondrial DNA of *M. p. pectoralis* and *M. p. ocularis* to establish the degree of their isolation and when they diverged. The molecular data can also be instrumental to clarify the phylogenetic relationships of *Malcorus* genus with other Cisticolidae species. Further molecular and biometric data for comparison of the two subspecies are to be obtained during field work trips to such localities around the Free State as Florisbad, Springfontein, Fauresmith, Lindley and Paul Roux.

Image: The Rufous-eared Warbler (*Malcorus pectoralis* subsp. *etoshae*) from Etosha National Park, Namibia, showing paler ear covers and paler creamy white breast and belly feathers. The breast band is sometimes absent in individuals during the winter months as in this individual photographed on 8 July 2019. (Photo: Raphael Lebrum / Macaulay Library ML176321461, with the photographer's and eBird permissions to reproduce in *Culna*)

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Image: The Rufous-eared Warbler (*Malcorus pectoralis* subsp. *etoshae*) from Etosha National Park, Namibia, which also shows paler ear covers and more creamy-white underside with a clear breast band photographed during summer. (Photo: Christien Boshoff)

THE ARTBANKSA: NEW INTEGRATIONS, NEW VISIONS OF MUTUALITY

By Ashraf Jamal

As the legend goes—*Ex Africa semper a liquid novi*—out of Africa there is always something new. In cynical times, the Latin saying can be deemed a cliché, especially when nay-sayers insist on reminding us of misfortune, corruption, barbarism, beggary, of the toxic, prejudicial, yet persistent view of Africa's failure to mirror the West. But as Steve Bantu Biko famously reminded us, in *I write what I like*, Africa's contribution to the world lies not in industrial innovation or military might—the core ingredients of every colonizing force—but in something far more precious, humanity. Africa's power lies in its spirit of Ubuntu, in relationality, in returning to the world its 'human face'.

Sentiment or Truth? Whichever way one chooses to frame the 'gap' that Africa must bridge, there is, to my mind at least, no doubt that it does reside in what Roman Krznaric calls an 'empathic revolution'. My aim is not to set Africa apart, this has all too often proven to be the reductive case, but to understand how and why Africa can connect the world. With the greatest labour reserve on earth, the most promising market for future innovation, vast still-untapped mineral resources, the indicators, reasonably, suppose Africa to be the trigger for continued global economic innovation. Why else are the world's super powers in the East and West knocking at our door? One would be foolish to ignore predation, or the extractive desires, and needs, of foreign powers. Neo-colonialism is omnipresent.

However, my focus is not on the extractive and exploitative drives that would further hobble a benighted continent, but, on the contrary, to recognise its infinitely greater strength. It is short-sighted to suppose continued subjugation as the driving logic of foreign powers.

Power-imbalances are never static, and, even when they remain unequal, inequality too must alter. The brutality of previous eras of colonisation have

inevitably shifted in their logic and practice. The emergence of 'soft power' has, increasingly, assumed an integral role in all political and economic negotiation. That culture, or cultural exchange, has assumed centrality in the mechanics of 'soft power', reaffirms the realisation, and fact that dialogue is no longer one-sided, that reciprocity, if only chimerically, remains a fundamental ingredient in every contemporary discourse.

Thus, when we speak of 'Bridging an Africa towards an Africa we want', it is this relative mutuality in political, economic and cultural exchange that is critical. Without mutual respect no inter-relational economy is possible. This mutuality supposes desire—an Africa we want—further underscores the realisation that exchange cannot be merely nominal, as a dialogue between two preconditioned and resolved entities, but can only occur when a critical degree of openness is permitted. *Mutuality is a desirous affair*. Exchange, to truly work and be profound, requires a 'human' interface – a desirous mutuality, an exchange between equals, founded on the critical notion of a shared continent, Africa, which, as stated at the outset, is the globally recognised source of great novelty. This 'newness', however, should not be understood as an add-on, in the well-known, perhaps infamous, case of a 'New South Africa', which proved as vulnerable to aspiration as it was to abuse, but, rather, better understood as an integral, residual dimension of a country, a continent, and its many cultures. To bridge the existing divides within and across Africa, to imagine the Africa we want, requires what the Cameroonian philosopher Achille Mbembe terms an 'anticipatory politics', one that supposes an integrative and inclusive vision of exchange.

That this logic necessarily also supposes a global vision is unsurprising. One cannot conceive of Africa without recognising its place in the greater world – one that is inter-regional, continental, and global. In a bid to foster 'new integrations', new interfaces in the art world, and its economic, cultural and political

underpinnings, we should not forget that continents too can prove to be provincial, in the recent case, say, of Europe, which, increasingly, has chosen to freeze the flow of goods and people, amplify a nation-based isolationism, not least because of the perceived threat posed by refugees from the Middle East and Africa. Thus, to understand the importance of a desirous mutuality—in the case of a unified Africa—we must, at the same time, recognise the equally aggravated and aggravating reality of a Europe under siege, caught between her respective national and global aspirations. And yet, despite this vexed and vexing contradiction, it remains of vital importance that we hold fast to our continental and global salvation, which, to my mind, requires stoicism, generosity and fairness – some ingenious and innovative compromise. This is vital, precisely because the world finds itself caught between irreconcilable extremes, on the Left and Right, because centrism, the pillar of democracy, is under threat. Thus, it is unsurprising, given this unstable historical moment, that ArtBankSA should aspire to bridge the African divide, and explore the Africa we want. This, in my view, is only possible through a patient compromise, a recognition of difficulty, combined with a will to pragmatically overcome it. The rest is idealism, which, while important, will not enable the changes on the ground that we require.

'The Africa we want' is not only an indigenous vision but also it requires the entire earth. Further, it requires us to stop blaming history for our continued ills, find merit in the past that can move us forward. Colonisation cannot be redacted. If, as Fredric Jameson remarked—'history hurts'—it nevertheless also possesses the power to heal and to engender alternative exchange economies. After all, Africa—in the specific case of South Africa—is, by virtue of her history, a hybrid culture. It is unsurprising that Archbishop Desmond Tutu would, as a consequence, dub ours a 'rainbow nation'. It is this variety, this geographical, historical and cultural complexity that we must place at the forefront. As the internationally celebrated artist, Ai Weiwei, cannily

reminds us, 'our future is just an integrated concept that combines today and yesterday'. It is through integration that we will override the toxicity of difference that sets us apart and divides the world. Integrated systems are hybrid, speculative, humane. They are built on experiment, and, as such, are fearless. If Africa has, supposedly, little to lose, it certainly has much to gain. While other economies are comparatively exhausted, ours remains bountiful. The fact of the matter, and the terrible irony, is that the world no longer has a choice. Ours is a metastasized anthropogenic time in which Africa has emerged comparatively unscathed, sanctified, and undestroyed. We are now not a last resource, but the first. The challenge, in the face of the global collapse, is to learn to live anew, and differently so. This, after all, was always Africa's lesson.

That Contemporary African Art has assumed centre-stage globally at this embattled historical moment is fortuitous but also unsurprising. In an 'End Time', a time morally exhausted, a time in which democracy, the foundation of Western Civilisation, is under threat, in which extremism becomes normative, and in which we find ourselves caught between two pieties—Fascism and Revisionism—it becomes all the more critical that we learn to recalibrate the world – our morality, our vision, our values. In this regard, art has a critical role to play, precisely because, at its best, it refuses to align itself to dogma. As the Irish novelist James Joyce might say, art at its best operates through 'silence, exile and cunning'. Or as the French poet Charles Baudelaire would argue, great art outwits 'the madness of the common people and the madness of the middle classes', precisely because it refuses to be co-opted. My point? That for art to be generative and healing, for it to reconcile a deranging rift, it must step outside and beyond the pale, the better, from a position of an outlier, to reflect upon the ills of history, society, nationhood, or any other essentialist category that sets people apart.

Dipesh Chakrabarty's provocative insight—the 'Provincialising of Europe'—posed in 2015, has proved, uncannily,

to be true. The threat of a return to a balkanised Europe, in which the European Union, with its democratic centrist glue unstuck, is no longer a prophecy but a clear and present danger. We in Africa, must be wary of the destruction of our potential integration as a continent. It is not a Pan-Africanism of which I speak—this is a rhetorical ideal—but a strategic, and stoical, repurposing of our co-dependent and contrary values. If an essential Africa does not exist, it does not follow that one must abandon any attempt towards what I've called a desirous mutuality. One does so, not by advocating some continental universalism, but by crosshatching differences, overriding exclusivity, effecting a hybrid mutuality. In this regard, art has a particularly profound role to play.

In South Africa's case, a country impressively hybrid—a fact impossible to ignore—art and its curation at ArtBankSA is founded on Ubuntu, the realisation that we are who we are, because of others. Consider the following acquisitions, and what they embody and represent. If Colleen Maswanganyi's wooden relief carvings (1) are immediately distinctive, it is because they are conciliatory, their gestural expression founded upon the core principle of Ubuntu. Perhaps the most iconic works, in this regard, they are, nevertheless, matched by a work, made of beads and framed with wood, which reveals a portrait of a young Nelson Mandela (2). Created by Morgan Mahape, it conveys all the hope and longing of an emerging nation, a dream, despite our putative democracy, which remains deferred. Still, however, against the odds, hope remains in the exemplary iconic and mythic figure of Mandela. What better votive or prayer can one nation gift to another?

Gilbert Maepa's oil of canvas, 'Tša bogadi' (3), fuses tradition and modernity, reminding us that all channels must be open in an ever-changing society. Wonder Buhle Mbambo's (4) vision of an unseeing youth, their eyes masked by a black floral eyepatch, supposes that connection and advance is not the province of the eye alone. Hlengiwe

Image 1: Colleen Maswanganyi, *Nkosi sikilela II & III*, 2020, Wooden board, corkwood and acrylic, 30×37×7cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 2: Morgan Mahape, *Young Mandela*, 2018, Beads and wood frame, 100×60 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Dube's witty 'Zulu Ear Plug' (5), a nod to traditional cosmetics, reveals the innovative use of alternative material, in this case, telephone wire. Africa, of course, is famed in this regard, as a continent, more than any other, for

Image 3: Gilbert Maepa, *Tša bogadi*, 2019, Oil on canvas, 86.5x86.5 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 4: Wonder Buhle Mbambo, *Abalazi*, 2019, Mixed media on canvas, 70x100 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 5: Hlengiwe Dube, *The Zulu Ear Plug*, 2022, Telephone Wire, 50x50x4 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

having understood how to transform waste—often the waste of foreign nations—into a newfound beauty. As the great saying goes, out of Africa, newness arises. This is the frisson and

thrill, which foreigners experience on arriving in Africa. But as Pfano Bebeda reminds us, our great and ancient wood carving tradition, which predates well-nigh 600 years of colonisation, also cannot be ignored. His 'Three Horns' (6), made of African mahogany, returns us to a staple wood carving, which proved enormously impactful in Europe, and, in the works of Pablo Picasso in particular, ushered forth European Modernism, the unquestionable foundation of which, despite denial, lies in Africa.

But, of course, in a culture of mutuality, Europe in turn has impacted on the work of South African artists. Taiwo Ohu's 'House of Parliament Cape Town' (7) is a meticulous architectural draft. Painted in acrylic on canvas, before the catastrophic fire, it is a vision of repose in a fundamentally incendiary society, as we would later witness in the July riots of 2021. On the other hand, Thando Mama's 'Izingqi Zesikhumbuzo' (8), an inkjet print on photographic paper made earlier, in 2016–17, seems to generate an almost prophetic unease regarding governance. Its seemingly multiplied coated figure evokes a surreal theatre of the absurd, some enigmatic and unfathomable state of play. What it makes apparent, is that art reflects the tensions in a society, but it cannot speak fluently on its behalf – to do so would be dogma. In the case of Ilene Bothma's 'Empty Threat' (9) and 'Conditional Threat' (10), it can eerily evoke unease. Or, in 'Grannies soccer match' (11) and 'Football Mateli' (12) by Kabelo Pedro Serasengwe and Mfundo Mbali, it can capture an irresistible conviviality and healthy competitiveness.

The emotional range of the presented works reveals the complexity of South African society – its grievances, unease, yet also its hopes. If Sthenjwa Luthuli's work—a superwood cut block, acrylic and gloss—is especially arresting and unnerving, this is, in part, because of its title, 'Chasing Fear' (13), as it is principally about the collision course the two highly animated figures are caught within. The heads are cut off, yet echoed in the mandala-like formation that encircles the figures. Their chests are thrust out, arms akimbo, legs and feet firmly placed.

Image 6: Pfano Bebeda, *Three Horns*, 2020, African Mahogany Wood, 72x40x12 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 7: Taiwo Ohu, *House of Parliament Cape Town*, 2018, Acrylic on canvas, 100x150 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 8: Thando Mama, *Izingqi Zesikhumbuzo*, 2016–17, Inkjet print on photographic paper, 117x78 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

A study in which wood engraving and paint are integral, the postures archetypal, the work, to my mind and eye, is not only concerned with the underworld of fear and dread, but also the overworld of a bluntly balletic encounter. If Luthuli's work is especially emblematic, it is because it reconciles the energy of conflicting fields which comprise what is none other than a deft curation of a national treasure house.

Image 9: Ilene Bothma, *Empty Threat*, 2016, Oil paint, glue and enamel on paper, 54×43.5 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 10: Ilene Bothma, *Conditional Threat*, 2016, Oil paint, glue and enamel on paper, 54×43.5 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 13: Sthenjwa Luthuli, *Chasing Fear*, 2016, Superwood cut block, acrylic, gloss, 178×130 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 11: Kabelo Pedro Serasengwe, *Grannies soccer match*, 2021, Acrylic on canvas, 90×60 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

Image 12: Mfundo Mbali, *Football Mateli*, 2020, Oil on canvas, 122×95 cm. ArtbankSA Contemporary Collection.

My wager? That ArtBankSA embodies and represents a positive spirit of cultural custodianship and exchange. If anything, the ever-growing ArtBankSA collection expresses not only our benighted history but also our inspired present and illuminated future. As an art collection, a vehicle for dialogue, it signifies an open temperament, one that is as generous as

it is cautiously introspective. Integrative, novel, it is, as such, also deft. It is a national curatorial and, by extension, a diplomatic enterprise, that stands on a firm footing, with its chest thrust bravely outward, arms and hands that are not appropriative, and therefore thrust backward. This, as a symbol of a desirous mutuality, is exemplary.

A photograph of a taxidermist, Herman H. ter Meer, in a white lab coat, working on a large orangutan skin specimen. The specimen is mounted on a wire frame and is being held up by the taxidermist. In the foreground, there is a table with various tools and a skull. The background is a dark, textured wall.

Taxidermy specimens in the NATIONAL MUSEUM'S Mammal exhibitions

By Nico Avenant

The National Museum has recently embarked on a long process of upgrading its Mammal exhibition halls. While we are excited about the prospects of the changes, this mission also presents us with an opportunity to reflect on the composition and layout of the existing mammal displays. The National Museum currently exhibits 153 life-sized taxidermy (originally cotton-wrapped wire bodies supporting sewn-on cured skins) and fibreglass mammal specimens. Taxidermy specimens have a special place in the Museum exhibitions and allow visitors to see what rare or extinct animals looked like from up close when they were more common or alive. On the National Museum's displays, these specimens are supplemented by the actual study skins, skulls, teeth and wet samples (specimens fixated in formalin), as well as by the text (including braille), sound recordings, maps, drawings, pictures and carvings.

Image: Master of Fine Arts, taxidermist Herman H. ter Meer, photographed with one of his unique dermoplastic moulds over which an orangutan skin would be mounted. (Photocopied from Becker, 2004; © Naturkundemuseum Leipzig).

Image: This Giraffe calf was mounted in the late 19th century and is our oldest mammal taxidermy specimen on display.

The term *taxidermy* is derived from the Greek words *taxis* (arrangement) and *derma* (skin) and, according to the Cambridge Dictionary (n.d.: online), can be described as “the activity of cleaning, preserving and filling the skins of dead animals with special material to make them look as if they are still alive”. As the skins are basically mounted over a framework, the end products are also referred to as “taxidermy mounts” (Wikipedia n.d.: online). Preparation of the hunting and fishing trophies is an old practice. The techniques used in taxidermy were already formalised by the mid-18th century, when the first methods for the preparation of specimens for natural history exhibitions were published (Wikipedia n.d.: online). Soon after, professional taxidermists could be found in Germany, France, England and Denmark. They even “studied” to practice their trade, and competed to do their apprenticeships with the most well-known and recognised specialists in the field. Already then the trademarks of the true professionals included not only a good knowledge of skin tanning, animal anatomy and behaviour, but also of sculpture and painting. Interestingly, while many today consider taxidermy as a form of art, and taxidermy specimens therefore worthy of extreme preservation, others may treat it merely as a skill. As Hein van Grouw, Senior Curator of Birds at the Natural History Museum (London) remarked, “nature has done the designing for you, and you cannot get any better than that. A taxidermist (therefore) isn’t coming up with anything new” (Pavid n.d.: online) and therefore should not claim his skill as art per se.

The present collection of taxidermy specimens on the exhibition at the National Museum includes a number of remarkable items, some of which were imported from Europe. Arguably the most valuable and well-known examples, for which we have reliable information, were prepared by the *Taxidermy Hall of Fame* taxidermist and Master of Fine Arts, Herman Hendrikus ter Meer, a pioneer of modern dermoplasty (“developed his own technique for making manikins”; “By using a mixture of plaster, glue, and turf, he was able to make a manikin which could be sculpted as it slowly hardened”). Ter Meer was born on 16 December 1871 in Leiden, The Netherlands, and grew up in a family and tradition of taxidermists. His grandfather, father and uncle all worked in the Taxidermy department of the former Reich Museum of Natural History in Leiden, The Netherlands. This is also where he was first appointed as a taxidermist, on 1 February 1895. In 1907, he moved to the Zoological Institute of the University of Leipzig, Germany, where he worked until his death on 9 March 1934. Ter Meer prepared two of the specimens displayed at the National Museum: a Serval and a Black Wildebeest. These taxidermy mounts were produced during his tenure at the University of Leipzig, in 1931 and 1932 respectively. The skill and craftsmanship of this master taxidermist is still evident today (Becker, 2004). Even though most of our other mounts were done more than 30 years after those of ter Meer’s, his specimens are still the best preserved. These truly remarkable mounts remain our most prized taxidermy specimens – the real works of art, indeed.

Our oldest taxidermy specimen is the Giraffe calf, which stands next to an adult female on the ground floor, opposite the Museum shop. We unfortunately have no record of who the taxidermist was, nor the exact year when the work was completed. The small giraffe was first exhibited in the late 1890s in the First Raadsaal (during the days of the Orange Free State Republic, before the Second Anglo-Boer War). What we do know is that some of the taxidermy mounts displayed in the First Raadsaal during that period were prepared in Cape Town. It is, therefore, not impossible that our little giraffe was a passenger on one of the earliest trains between Cape Town and Bloemfontein! (The railway line first reached Bloemfontein in 1890.)

Image: The Black Wildebeest bull (on the left) was reconstructed in 1932 in Leipzig, Germany, by the master taxidermist Herman H. ter Meer.

Image: Ninety-two years after this serval was recreated by Herman H. ter Meer it still looks identical to when it was photographed in 1931 in Leipzig. It remains our most lively and best preserved carnivore mount in the National Museum exhibitions.

Specimens that came to South Africa as complete taxidermy mounts included the endangered Aye-Aye, endemic to Madagascar; the near threatened Platypus, endemic to Tasmania and the eastern part of Australia; the vulnerable Giant Anteater, endemic to Panama and the northern parts of South America; and the least concern, according to the IUCN (2023), Brown bear (also called the Grizzly bear) from Eurasia and North America; amongst others.

Long-time favourites in our mammal exhibitions are the large elephants, rhinoceroses and hippopotamuses, which are for many the focus points of specific halls. These impressive, live-size beasts are some of the most photographed items in the National Museum, and time and again leave large groups of pupils that frequent us, in awe. Since these specimens are made of more durable fibreglass, they are also favourites among visually impaired visitors, who are allowed to experience their size, shape and texture through the sense of touch.

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Image: The secretive and nocturnal Aye-Aye occurs in very low densities in the remaining and fragmented forest pockets of the coastal Madagascar. The main threats for this endangered species are hunting and loss of its habitat to deforestation. Its distribution range is also expected to decrease significantly in the not too distant future, due to climate change.

Image: The impressive live-sized Elephant, Rhinoceros and Hippopotamus exhibitions are some of the most photographed in the National Museum.

Image: They are also firm favourites amongst our visually impaired guests.

The importance of Cultural Heritage

Figure 1: Kyiv St Sophia's Cathedral, Ukraine. (Photo credit: Rbrechko - Wikimedia CC BY-SA 4.0)

By Loudine Philip

In a situation of life and death during wartime, it might sound superfluous that concern for Ukraine's cultural heritage has also become newsworthy since its invasion by Russia on the 24th of February 2022. The Ukrainians themselves are risking their lives to safeguard cultural objects by transporting movable objects and artworks to safer areas and safeguarding immovable objects such as statues by covering them with sandbags. Ukraine has a long and illustrious history and as a result also a rich legacy of cultural heritage which, given the severity of the invasion, is near on impossible to safeguard.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has reported that they are monitoring the situation, but it is more than just a mere concern for the physical properties of the heritage components. Ukraine is home to seven World Heritage Sites namely St Sophia Cathedral & Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra dating to the 11th century, Lviv Historic Centre Ensemble, Struve Geodetic Arc, Virgin Beech Forests of the Carpathians, Residence of Bukovinian and Dalmatian Metropolitans, Wooden churches of the Carpathian Region, and Chersonese. To date, none of the seven has been damaged by the Russian missiles, but several museums, libraries, statues,

churches, and so forth, have been destroyed. The Ukrainians accuse the Russians of deliberately destroying their cultural heritage, while the Russians call it collateral damage.

It was only in 1907 that cultural heritage became a topic of international law, and since 1950 UNESCO and other intergovernmental organisations have developed a series of international treaties and texts to protect it. The first of these was UNESCO's 1954 Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property (referred to as the "Hague Convention"), developed in part in response to the destruction and looting of monuments and works of art during World War II. Its genesis was in the belief that preventing their destruction or deterioration was important for the future of the emerging international world order and for preventing conflicts.

But why is cultural heritage important and why in particular are the Ukrainians so passionate about preserving their own that they are willing to risk their lives to save and safeguard it? Our cultural legacy is one-of-a-kind and priceless. Cultural objects are tangible witnesses to the past, revealing our genuine history and preserving our recollections of it. Cultural legacy evokes strong feelings such as identity, consciousness, and a sense of communal belonging.

Figure 2: The monument to the Duke of Richelieu in Odessa, Ukraine being sandbagged to protect it from the Russian invasion of Ukraine (Photo credit: <https://odessa-life.od.ua/news/odessity-zashchitili-djuka-ot-bombbezhenki>)

Figure 3: The damaged menorah monument at the entrance of the Drobitsky Yar Holocaust memorial complex, Kharkiv. (Photo credit: Sergey Bobok/AFP Getty Images)

It took a long time for the world to accept that cultural property belongs to "all mankind" regardless of where it comes from. According to UNESCO, its disappearance is "a harmful impoverishment of the heritage of all the nations of the world."

Deliberate destruction of cultural heritage during warfare is a way to destroy and overtake a society by erasing its memory and this is exactly what Ukrainians are accusing Russia of doing. In an interview by NBC News, Ukraine's former vice minister of culture, Iryna Podolyak, said "*They just want to erase from the map Ukraine – our heritage, our history, our identity and Ukraine as an independent state*".

A picture that was taken on March 27, 2022, shows a view of the Menorah memorial, set on the place of a mass killing of Jewish people by Nazis during WWII, a day after it was damaged in a Russian shelling, at the entrance of the Drobitsky Yar Holocaust memorial complex on the eastern outskirts of Kharkiv.

UNESCO is keeping a close eye on the development of the war. On 21 September 2022 they verified that 192 sites have been damaged since 24 February. This includes 81 religious sites, 13 museums, 37 historic buildings dedicated to cultural activities, 17 monuments, and 10 libraries, but none of the seven World Heritage Sites have been harmed to date.

In the interim SUCHO (Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online) – a project led by more than 1,500 foreign volunteers with the goal of digitizing and preserving Ukrainian cultural treasures – is working round the clock to identify and archive material from Ukrainian cultural institutions by employing a combination of technologies to crawl and archive sites and its content to safeguard it for future generations.

According to UNESCO the deliberate destruction of Ukraine's cultural heritage during the current invasion by Russia could be considered a war crime, but what punishment would ever be just enough to compensate a country for the loss of an important part of its national identity?

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Image 1: The cover of a reference book or passbook that belonged to a Batho resident, 1958. (Source: National Museum)

“Oh, that law, it was terrible!”:

Memories of pass laws, permits and policemen in apartheid-era Batho (Mangaung)

By Derek du Bruyn

In his novel, *The Go-Between* (1953), Leslie P. Hartley wrote “the past is a foreign country; they do things differently there”. Although Hartley referred to British society at the end of the Victorian era, his famous quote is also relevant to South Africa and other countries that have experienced drastic socio-political changes. The fact that the past is described as “a foreign country” means it can never be fully understood by us who live in the present age because we do not belong there. Post-1994 democratic South Africa and pre-1994 apartheid South Africa are indeed two very different countries. For those who grew up in the former, the latter is “a foreign country”.

Today, the *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa* (1996) is the cornerstone of our democracy and the foundation on which the present dispensation rests. The *Bill of Rights* (Chapter 2) “enshrines the rights of all people in our country

and affirms the democratic values of human dignity, equality and freedom”. It is hard to believe that before 1994 black¹ people did not enjoy the basic human rights and freedoms South Africans take for granted such as the right to vote; freedom of movement; the right to have one’s dignity respected; the right to privacy; and the right to reside anywhere in the Republic, to name a few.

The National Party, which came to power in 1948, used its racist apartheid policies and practices to suppress the majority of South Africans and deny them the basic human rights that are annually celebrated on Human Rights Day. Apartheid laws and regulations were used as instruments to control and monitor black people. The *Natives (Urban Areas) Act* (1923) mandated all towns and cities in the Union of South Africa (est. 1910) to establish “native locations”² where only the employed was housed and from which the unemployed was

1 In this article, the terms “black(s)” or “black people” refer to all people of colour who were legally and socially discriminated against on the basis of race.

2 In the historical South African context, the term “location” referred to a segregated living area for people of colour. Locations – today known as “townships” – were usually situated on the fringes of “whites-only” towns and cities.

Image 2: The first page of a typical passbook contained the carrier's personal information. (Source: National Museum)

banned. Those who were not welcome in "whites-only" towns and cities had to eke out a living in the impoverished "native reserves" and later in the black "homelands".

Location residents were subjected to a host of discriminatory apartheid regulations that affected every aspect of their lives. Batho or Batho Location (est. 1918), as Mangaung's (Bloemfontein) oldest surviving township is known, was no exception. Oral historians of the National Museum's Department of History have conducted interviews with elderly Batho residents for whom apartheid was a daily lived reality. Therefore, this article endorses oral history as "lived practice", to quote oral historian Sean Field. The interviews – conducted over a period of ten years – have yielded detailed accounts of the interviewees' personal experiences. Direct quotes from interviews paint a vivid picture of what it was like to be on the receiving end of apartheid oppression and discrimination.

Although racial segregation and discrimination were enforced by Dutch and British colonial authorities long before the National Party came to power, the post-1948 apartheid regulations were vigorously implemented. These measures were enforced with an iron fist by apartheid bureaucrats, notably the police, right through the fifties, sixties, seventies, and eighties. Most interviewees have experienced oppression and discrimination during all four decades. One of them is long-time Batho resident Moitheri L. Machogo (b. 1949). She explained how apartheid laws and regulations were tightened after 1961 when South Africa became a republic: "Apartheid was there but not as 'open' as it became after the republic [came into being] because even during that time when the British was [sic] in power, it was there but 'mild'. After that; that was when the Boers told themselves that we were *kaffirs*³, you understand?"

Pass laws, passbooks and platkeps

Although Bloemfontein's black residents have been compelled by municipal regulation to carry some form of reference document as early as 1872, it was only after 1948 that the hated "passes" or "passbooks" were introduced. *The Natives (Abolition of Passes and Co-ordination of Documents) Act (1952)*, commonly known as the *Pass Laws Act*, made it compulsory for all black people between the ages of 16 and 65 to carry a "reference book" at all times when they resided in apartheid South Africa. Juliet M. Bokala (b. 1928) recalled the time when she and her family were first issued with passes: "We didn't want to take these passes but we were forced to take the passes. Everyone got a book like this, a pass".

Another Batho resident, Alinah S. Motleng (b. 1938), recalled that all black people were "expected to carry that identity document called *dompas*". The *dompas*, a colloquial term for a passbook, was a rectangular black booklet (**Image 1**) that permitted the carrier's presence in a location and specified the conditions under which the person could stay there. A passbook contained several pages with information on the carrier's "group" (ethnic group) and "tribe" to which he or she belonged (**Image 2**); marital status; name of husband, wife, parent or guardian; residential address; and name and address of employer(s). Rabokanana J. Ketela (b. 1938) recalled that in his passbook was also "written the [house] number where you stay", among others. "You see, this number, if they catch you [sleeping] at the next door, next, next house ... its trouble!". Rabokanana recalled that offenders had to pay a hefty fine: "[I]f they catch you, you are going to pay two rand, two times". He understood only later why "sleeping next door" was considered an offence!

The "they" which Rabokanana referred to are the notorious municipal policemen who were responsible for enforcing the

3 A derogatory and offensive term used by some whites to refer to people of African origin.

Image 3: An unknown couple in front of the pass office on Lovedale Road, Batho, c. 1970s. (Photo: National Museum)

pass laws. In Batho these policemen were called *platkeps* because of the shape of their caps. The Pass Laws Act gave the *platkeps* extensive power over the movement and lodgings of black people. They could demand at any time and at any place to see a person's passbook and checked if it was up to date and whether or not the person was "legal" or "illegal". Juliet Bokala described the horror of an unexpected stop-and-search: "I remember one morning, when I got to work ... there were many people standing there, policemen. They wanted our passes. When you don't have a pass you must stand there [and wait] the whole day. Someone was arrested because she didn't have a passbook. Oh, that law, it was terrible!"

All passes and permits, such as a permit to seek work, had to be obtained, renewed, and paid for at the local pass office which, in Batho's case, was located on Lovedale Road (**Image 3**). Tsoeu J. Khoarela (b. 1919), who lived in Batho "for a long time", remembered Batho's pass office well: "I also had my reference book from the same place [pass office]. Most of my documentation indicates that it was done in Batho". Tsametse Leeuw (b. 1940) recalled that Batho residents jokingly called the pass office "Ten Hall": "Yes, we called it 'Ten Hall' because its original name was 'Town Hall'".

Tsametse explained that Batho's first pass office "was situated next door to Mapikela House [Thomas M. Mapikela's double-storey house in Community Road]. Then it was transferred to Lovedale Road when they built a new building". For Tsametse and the other interviewees Batho's pass office triggered painful memories of humiliation and hardship: "When you did not pay [house rent or permit fees] then you were taken there; then you will be charged and sometimes when you had money you would be able to pay for the release of your loved one by paying that charge and rent".

Lodger's permits and house raids

Tsametse Leeuw's mention of "release" is significant in this context because people who were caught breaking apartheid laws were arrested by the *platkeps* and locked up. Most arrests related to people who were not in possession of a "lodger's permit", also known among Batho residents as *lodges* or *lojas*. For Rabokanana Ketela it was the "sleeping next door" permit!. Nomvula R. Ntuli (b. 1938) explained the purpose of the lodger's permit: "Even if you were my visitor, I was not supposed to let you stay overnight before I go to the office [pass office] to ask for 'days'. If you arrived late at night, I had to take you to the *blockman* to get a permission letter".

Permanent Batho residents had to be in possession of a "residential permit" and if they wanted to host visitors, a lodger's permit had to be obtained and paid for. This permit allowed guests to stay for seven days. During office hours such a permit could be obtained at the pass office but after hours the local ward councillor, also known as a *blockman*, had to issue the permit. Moitheri Machogo recalled that lodger's permits were meticulously checked and both the host and the visitor could be arrested for wrongdoing: "... when the *platkeps* came that they found your visitor having that letter [lodger's permit]; and if that visitor does not have the letter, the host will get arrested. The letter would become *lodges* and if your visitor does not have it, that person will get arrested".

It was not uncommon for neighbours to spy on each other and report unauthorised visitors to the local *blockman* who, in turn, alerted the *platkeps*. This could lead to the dreaded house raids that typically happened in the early hours of the morning. Nomathamsanqa S. Thebe (b. 1961) recalled such a frightening visit: "... one Saturday morning we heard a knock and they [police] just opened. I tried to hide under [the] bed but they had seen me. They dragged me out by the leg and put me in the *bakkie* [police van]". Offenders were taken to the Batho police station where they had to pay a fine of R1,00. Mateboho D. Modiroa (b. 1941) testified that one of her worst childhood memories involved seeing "municipal police drive around the location [Batho] arresting others while you [offender] are sitting at the back of the van".

Loitering and loaferskap

Another offense that could lead to arrest was the issue of loitering and idleness, commonly referred to by apartheid bureaucrats as *loaferskap*. It referred to a position of being unemployed, i.e. being an "idle native", to quote apartheid language. Long-time Batho resident Florie M. Makhabe (b.

Image 4: Batho's old pass office building repurposed as a crèche and day care centre, 2013. (Photo: National Museum)

1958) recalled that in the apartheid years "it was illegal to hang around without a job. You could hardly see individuals hanging around the location [Batho] doing nothing". People who arrived in Batho looking for employment had to obtain a special permit allowing them to be in the location for only 72 hours to actively look for a job. Hilda K. Motsamai (b. unknown) recalled that work seekers were not allowed to loiter because they "would be arrested for that". She testified that "after they [police] arrested you they will find work for you somewhere". According to Florie, whose brother was arrested a number of times for *loaferskap*, "somewhere" often meant manual labour on a "potato farm".

The evening curfew and "steam train siren"

Finally, it was deemed an offense for a black person to be in the "whites-only" town after 21h00 at night. As early as 1894 municipal regulations protected white Bloemfontein residents from location residents by enforcing an evening curfew. This curfew was kept in place until the 1980s. Tsamets Leeuw recalled the loud siren that went off to warn black people to rush back to the location: "In town there was this 'steam train whistle' [siren] that would go off at 8h45 pm and as a black

person you had to clear yourself out of town. If 9h00 pm hit while you were in town, you would get arrested". Batho residents were also not allowed out in the location's streets after 22h00 at night. Needless to say, the *platkeps* patrolled the streets and arrested those found outside.

Conclusion

While some apartheid laws, such as the Pass Laws Act, were repealed during the late 1980s, the bulk of it was only removed from the law books during the mid-1990s. Personal experiences of these laws as a lived reality are not only permanently ingrained in the Batho interviewees' memories of the apartheid past but such experiences have also left permanent emotional scars. Being degraded and dehumanised caused a sense of injustice which, some interviewees argue, has not been adequately addressed yet. The last word belongs to Moses B. Kgoroge (b. unknown) who felt that they were "arrested for nothing really, having done nothing [wrong]". For this reason he argued that "we must get compensated, the ones that were arrested for *loaferskap*".

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*The impact of climate change on soil invertebrates:
What experiments tell us?*

By Lizel Hugo-Coetzee

Figure 3. Chamber with carbon dioxide infuser to increase temperature and carbon dioxide levels. (From Spruce and Peatland Responses Under Changing Environments (SPRUCE) Oak Ridge National Laboratory)

Climate change is an undeniable reality, and while natural climate variations have occurred over millennia, the current pace of change exceeds natural expectations, primarily due to human activities. The most noticeable changes are in the levels of carbon dioxide, temperature and rainfall. These changes will not be the same everywhere. For example, some areas are predicted to have less rainfall (like southern Africa), while others will witness increased precipitation. Temperature is also expected to rise by 1.5°C (best-case scenario) to 4°C (most pessimistic scenario) by 2100, with variations across different geographical locations. These changes in our climate will have profound consequences for all life on our planet, including soil-dwelling invertebrates.

Soil invertebrates, such as mites (Fig. 1) and springtails, play essential roles in ecosystem functions such as breaking down organic matter and partaking in the intricate soil food web. They depend on the right soil temperature and moisture levels to thrive. Additionally, changes in carbon dioxide levels can indirectly impact them by altering the plant assemblages they rely on. When the temperature and moisture conditions shift, it can cause problems for the ecosystem and affect how quickly organic matter is broken down in the soil.

To understand how climate change is impacting soil invertebrates, scientists use experiments where they can manipulate the climate on a small scale to see what may

Figure 1. Soil mites under the microscope. (Photo by Louise Coetzee)

happen in the future. It's like making a mini version of the Earth's future and comparing it to how things proceed in the current natural world. One effective tool researchers use is something called an open-top chamber. These chambers can be small and cover just a few plants (Fig. 2) or be huge and enclose entire trees in a forest (Fig. 3). They are like clear plastic boxes with no roof, so the sunlight can get in and warm things up, but they also allow for natural rainfall. Some chambers even have heating coils buried under the soil to make

Figure 2. Open top chamber to increase temperature inside enclosure. (From Wikimedia Commons)

Figure 4. Experiment on Marion Island, with plastic sheets for warmer temperatures and lower rainfall. (Photo by P. Le Roux)

the environment even warmer. For studying both warming and higher carbon dioxide levels, scientists use chambers that release extra carbon dioxide. Closed-top chambers are used to test how warming and drying affect animals inside. Some modifications use clear sheets with open sides to let the wind, carbon dioxide and humidity in, but still reduce rainfall and increase temperature (Fig. 4). These experiments can last from just a few months to as long as 20 years. Researchers collect soil samples with invertebrates from inside these chambers and compare them to samples from outside, which serve as a control group.

Scientists have done a lot of these experiments around the world, and in a meta-analysis of 86 of these experiments it has been found that overall the soil invertebrate system seems quite stable; however, the results differ depending on the type of experiment, geographic location and many other variables. In general, when it gets warmer and drier, there tend to be fewer springtails. However, mites can respond in many ways in different places. Surprisingly, no studies from Africa have been identified in this analysis (Fig. 5). The closest study has been done on Marion Island, which is experiencing significant climate changes. Over the last 60 years, the annual rainfall on Marion Island has decreased by 25 mm, while annual air temperatures have increased by 1.2°C. This study focused on a cushion plant inhabited by soil invertebrates, revealing that after one year, the mite population density increased under the dry-warm treatment, while the springtail density decreased. It also showed that different species responded to the changes each in their own way, highlighting the need to study individual species.

Such experiments help us understand how climate change affects soil invertebrates. More studies, especially in Africa, will help us get a better picture of what's happening to the soil ecosystem as our climate keeps changing.

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Figure 5. Geographic locations of experimental studies used in an analysis to determine general trends in soil invertebrates. (From Goncharov et al. 2023)

GESTIG 1685 FOUNDED
GROOT CONSTANTIA
LANDGOED • ESTATE

ICONIC GROOT CONSTANTIA — SOUTH AFRICA'S OLDEST BRAND

By Sharon Snell

Groot Constantia, a vineyard which was founded in 1685, is the oldest wine brand established in South Africa. This historic enterprise has operated successfully for over three centuries in South Africa and it is well known internationally. The company has a strong identity; its logo depicts the iconic old colonial Cape Dutch gabled homestead, which is easily recognisable. Wine tourism at Groot Constantia started in the 1700s and nowadays the estate receives about 300,000 visitors per year. The history of the estate (colonialism, slavery and wine making) has been intrinsically woven into the brand narrative.

Viticulture was first introduced to South Africa soon after arrival of the Dutch. The Dutch East India Company (Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie, or VOC) established a permanent settlement and victualling post in Cape Town in 1652, with Jan van Riebeeck (1619–1677) as the first Commander. He immediately requested thousands of vine cuttings from overseas and viable stocks started to arrive by yacht in 1655 and were planted in Wynberg. Van Riebeeck made an entry in his journal on 2 February 1659, where he noted that wine was made for the first time in South Africa on this day:

"To-day, praise be to God, wine was made for the first time from Cape grapes, namely from the new must fresh from the vat. The grapes were mostly Muscadel and other white, round grapes, very fragrant and tasty. The Spanish grapes are still quite green, though they hang reasonably thickly on several vines and give promise of a first-class crop. These grapes, from the three young vines planted 2 years ago, have yielded about 12 quarts of must, and we shall soon discover how it will be affected by maturing."

Image: First Governor of the Cape Colony Simon van der Stel established the wine farm Constantia in 1685. Portrait by Pieter van Anraedt. Source: www.wikipedia.com.

Nowadays, South Africa produces 10,826 hectolitres of wine, which is over 4% of world production, so the country is currently ranked as one of the Top10 wine producers in the world according to the International Organisation of Vine and Wine. South African vineyard surface area amounts to 125,586 hectares, mostly situated in the Western Cape.

Simon van der Stel's beloved Constantia

Simon van der Stel (1679–1712) is known as the founding father of the wine industry in South Africa. In 1679, van der Stel was appointed the Commander, then later the first Governor of the Cape Colony, by the VOC. He was born in Mauritius in 1639 and his mother was of Malay descent. Prior to his appointment to the Cape, he was stationed in Amsterdam where he worked for the VOC and owned two vineyards just outside the city (in Muiderberg), which produced wine and brandy. Van der Stel's instructions were to expand agricultural production in the Cape Colony and in this regard, he explored the Stellenbosch region, which later became a renowned home of winelands. Here he gave grants of land to free burghers and immigrants, and many of these new owners established wine farms, became very wealthy and formed the rural aristocracy of the Cape. Van der Stel also provided long term loans and farming implements to those who had nothing, like the Huguenots, whose viticulture skills enhanced the wine industry in the Cape.

Having conducted extensive testing of soils, Van der Stel coveted lush land behind the Table Mountain in the District of Wynberg for himself, as he found it most suitable for a vineyard. In 1685, he was granted a plot of 891 morgen (about 763 hectares), which he named Constantia. When van der Stel died in 1712, ownership of Constantia returned to the VOC, and the company divided it into three separate properties (Bergvliet, Groot Constantia and Klein Constantia) and sold it in 1716.

Image: The Valley of Constantia by Roworth, Edward (1940–1949). Source: The artwork is in the collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein.

Image: Anna de Koningh, daughter of Angela of Bengal (a freed slave) was the first female owner of Groot Constantia. Anna also inherited the farm, Groot Phesantekraal, which produces an opulent and elegant Chenin Blanc as a tribute to Anna.

Source: www.grootphesantekraal.co.za.

Becoming Groot Constantia

In 1716, a wealthy Swede, Oloff Bergh, purchased Constantia on auction. He did not contribute significantly to the vineyard and when he passed in 1724, his wife, Anna de Koningh, inherited the farm. Anna de Koningh was the daughter of the enslaved Angela of Bengal, who, along with her children, was freed in 1666. Anna de Koningh was the first woman and the first woman of mixed descent to own a wine farm in South Africa. She, however, had no interest in viticulture and neglected the farm.

The farm changed ownership a number of times over the years. In 1798 Hendrik Cloete (senior) purchased Groot Constantia and it stayed in his family for many generations. Groot Constantia was divided again when in 1823, the widow of Hendrik Cloete (junior) divided it and sold portions to her sons. The larger portion was sold to Jacob Pieter Cloete, and this is the portion that retained the name Groot Constantia from 1824 onwards. The company thereafter suffered many setbacks that ravaged the wine industry, including the abolition of slavery in 1834, a fungal disease in the 1850s, reduction of the import duty on French wines imported to Britain in 1860, and vine disease in 1866. After a series of devastating setbacks, Groot Constantia went on auction and was purchased for a low sum of £5275 for the Cape Government in 1885.

Image: *Sense and Sensibility* by Jane Austen and illustration by Hugh Thompson. The caption of the illustration is 'How fond he was of it!' Image used under the terms of the Project Gutenberg License.

Constantia wines immortalised in popular consumer culture

During the Napoleonic wars, the British re-annexed the Cape from the Dutch in 1806 and introduced preferential conditions for the export of wine to Britain, with the result that the majority of wine produced in the early 1800s was exported to Britain. Those were the golden years for Groot Constantia and the wine industry in the Cape Colony because demand exceeded production.

Constantia wines cemented its place in consumer culture, when it was referenced in a complimentary manner in poetry and popular fiction. It was first mentioned by a German poet Friedrich Gottlieb Klopstock in 1795. In his ode *Der Kapwein und der Johannisberger*, Klopstock bemoans his unpatriotic taste for preferring "daughter Konstanzia" with her bridal blush and scent of rose oil to wine of his homeland.

In 1811, Jane Austen published her first novel, *Sense and Sensibility*. In the book, Mrs Jennings offers Elinor a glass

of Constantia wine to give to Marianne and she then refers to it as some of the finest old Constantia wines:

"My dear," said she, entering, "I have just recollected that I have some of the finest old Constantia wine in the house that ever was tasted, so I have brought a glass of it for your sister. My poor husband! how fond he was of it! Whenever he had a touch of his old colicky gout, he said it did him more good than any thing else in the world. Do take it to your sister."

Constantia wines received a favourable mention in 1870 in Charles Dickens's novel, *The Mystery of Edwin Drood*, as well as in a French novel by Joris-Karl Huysman in 1884.

Emperor Napoleon Bonaparte highly esteemed Constantia wines, and Groot Constantia used to deliver at least 30 bottles of wine to him a month when he was exiled to St Helena during 1818–1821. Linking the Constantia brand to the iconic Napoleon's personality increased the demand for the Grand Constance wine that the emperor drank.

In May 2021, an unopened bottle of Grand Constance 1821, purportedly prepared by Groot Constantia with the Napoleon's monthly order in mind, was auctioned off for R420,000. In September 2021, another remaining bottle of the same wine went on auction and was sold by Strauss & Co. for a record breaking R967,300.

The multi-award-winning Grand Constance was relaunched in 2005 and a 375 ml bottle of 2018 Grand Constance will set you back R815.00 if you buy directly from the estate. This brand is marketed as an exclusive wine using the historic narrative of it being a choice of royalty and nobility. The bottle design and symbolism maintain its status as a luxury brand in

Image: *Napoleon Crossing the Alps*, a portrait by Jacques-Louis David (1748–1825). Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons.

the mind of a connoisseur. The artwork is the same as was used on the bottle of Grand Constance produced in the 1800s. It invites modern brand-conscious consumers to reminisce about that bygone era of historic battles, grand dining affairs and leisure pursuits enjoyed by the wealthy and titled.

Cultural-historical legacy of the wine industry

Groot Constantia was declared a national monument in 1984, and it is a living museum recognised for being the origin of the wine industry in South Africa. It is managed by the non-profit Groot Constantia Trust, which acts as an ambassador for the wine industry and wine tourism in South Africa. The Groot Constantia Homestead and Wine Museum has been operating as a museum since 1969 and the exhibitions include displays about rural slavery,

which was prominent at the time.

Recently, Groot Constantia applied to interdict Boschendal's application for a trademark, which included the words "a Cape icon since 1685" and would be used on its wines. Boschendal, one of the oldest wine estates in South Africa, is an operating farm that sells wines and offers accommodation, restaurant and conference facilities, as well as other tourist activities. In 2015, the High Court dismissed the application and ruled against Groot Constantia, holding that Boschendal was entitled to use the trademark. Even though Boschendal did not produce wine in 1685, there is evidence that Simon van der Stel granted the original farm to the French Huguenot Jean le Long in that year. In addition, the court held that Boschendal had reached its iconic status, having been proclaimed a national heritage site and fitted the trademark that they had applied for.

Image: Grand Constance 1821, favourite of Emperor Napoleon Bonaparte. Source: Strauss & Co. The same artwork is used on the bottles of Grand Constance wine sold today.

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Aardvarks (*Orycteropus afer*) and their symbolism in African culture

By Loudine Philip

In many African cultures, the aardvark is viewed as a symbol of strength and resilience, and anyone fortunate enough to see one is said to be blessed. The Hausa healers in West Africa pound and grind the heart, skin, and nails with the roots of a specific tree to create a charm that supposedly makes the wearer invisible at night – no doubt a great concern for any father with beautiful daughters at home!

The aardvark is a unique and strangely beautiful animal whose origin in its current form can be traced back to at least 5 million years ago, based on fossil finds. It belongs to the superorder *Afrotheria* which means they have familial ties with elephants, hyenas, and golden moles. On account of its ancient chromosome pattern, the aardvark is genetically considered a living fossil and is the only species left of the order *Tubulidentata*. This order is named after the characteristic tubular shape of their composite teeth. The aardvark's teeth consist of clusters of hundreds of tiny straw-like tubes that are continuously replaced as they wear down.

As a nocturnal animal, it mostly hunts at night. The aardvark is a ferocious little fighter when confronted or cornered and uses its tail and powerful claws to fight off predators. They are also very good swimmers and have the ability to seal up their nostrils when digging for termites and ants which form their main diet. Their exceptional sense of smell helps them to detect the position of termites below ground level.

They also have exceptional hearing abilities and will quickly hide in a burrow or dig a hole to hide from predators. Their ears have a unique shape and can fold up to prevent soil from getting into them while burrowing. Their tongues can extend to approximately 30 cm and are coated with a sticky substance so that their prey sticks to it and can thus consume a lot of ants or termites with a single lick.

And if we are not yet sufficiently awed by this wonderful creature, it is most likely the sole reason for the survival of the aardvark cucumber (*Cucumis humifructus*). The aardvark feeds almost exclusively on termites and ants, with the exception of this specific species of cucumber. It is the only type of cucumber that bears its fruit underground. The seeds and some water are contained in the tough outer skin of the fruit. The aardvark digs it up for its water content and, in the process, also ingests the seeds. Aardvarks have the curious habit of burying their dung, thus creating a fertile bed for the seeds in the dung that are expelled from the body and then covered with soil. This is an extreme example of a symbiotic relationship between a plant and an animal, as the aardvark cucumber is solely reliant on the aardvark for its dispersal and propagation. In areas where the aardvarks have been wiped out, the aardvark cucumbers have also disappeared. Animals such as both the Spotted and Brown Hyena, wild dogs, jackals, Bat-eared foxes, porcupines, South African Shelduck, and ant-eating Chats depend on the aardvark's abandoned burrows to use as safe dens for their young.

It is quite rare to see an aardvark because they mostly hunt at night and quickly disappear into a burrow when they hear something approaching. No wonder they are associated with powers of invisibility!

Image credit: Aardvark: Heather Paul / Creative Commons ("Aardvark (Orycteropus afer)" by warriorwoman531 licensed under CC BY-ND 2.0.)

Image credit: Aardvark teeth: Mammal Division, Museum of Zoology, University of Michigan

Image credit:
Aardvark
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2023 FREE STATE

YOUNG ARTIST AWARD

Learners were requested to submit original artworks in any medium under the theme "Restoring damaged ecosystems".

The Competition had 3 age groups
Category A: ages 5 to 9 years; Category B: ages 10 to 14 years;
Category C: ages 15 to 19 years

Winners: Category A:

Deandre du Toit - 1st Prize

Suné Louw - 2nd Prize

Olivia Hasenjager - 3rd Prize

Winners: Category B:

Zoey Su - 1st Prize

Athena Su - 2nd Prize

Bachumile Sithole -
3rd Prize

Geertjie Venter
- 3rd Prize

Winners: Category C:

No 2ND & 3RD prizes awarded
due to lacklustre entries.

Suné Fourie - 1st Prize

The Awards Ceremony

CURIOUS TIGER FLIES OF SOUTHERN AFRICA

Figure 1. *Coenosia attenuata* resting on a leaf, searching for its prey. Photo 1524389, (c) Katja Schulz, some rights reserved (CC BY) - <https://www.inaturalist.org/photos/1524389>

Tiger Flies (Fig. 1), scientifically called *Coenosia*, are small inconspicuous grey flies. They belong to a family of flies called the Muscidae, generally referred to as “Houseflies.” However, they are not your stereotypical pesky housefly (Fig. 2) and are unlikely to come into your house to irritate you like their cousins. You see, these little flies are actually fierce predators and typically hunt all kinds of insects.

One such species *Coenosia attenuata*, the “killer” or “hunter fly” is an important biological control agent in greenhouses and can be used to control plant pests such as fruit flies. They can also be quite entertaining and can behave like tiny falconer’s birds (Suvák 2008) perching on your finger, flying away, and coming back with a tasty insect snack.

My interest in *Coenosia* started with the discovery of a very weird new species of *Coenosia* from a farm near Oudtshoorn in the Western Cape. Trying to identify it yielded no known results, and it was described as *C. macrotrisetia* (Muller & Miller 2013). It is only known from the male and had the strangest triple pair of head bristles (Fig. 3) I had ever seen, with enlarged swollen ends (Fig. 4). While comparing it to other museum specimens we found a similar existing species called *C. globulisetia* (Pont 1980) (from the Drakensberg) but this species, also only known from the male, had one pair of bristles (Fig. 5).

In 2017, we went on a general collecting trip to Mariepskop Mountain, Mpumalanga, a site for which the fly diversity is very poorly understood. We always try and put up Malaise traps (massive 6m flight interception traps) in areas that are potential flightpaths with the intention of optimizing our insect catches. I essentially rock-climbed through a deep ravine, risking life and limb to install the trap in what we thought, was “the most amazing position” (Fig. 6). The results were probably the worst collecting we had done for the entire two weeks on the mountain. The trap did at least make for a very nice photo (Fig. 6).

However, in the trap were three specimens. I knew immediately that what we had caught was another new species of curious tiger fly, *Coenosia flagellisetia* (Muller 2019). The fly presented with strange swollen-end head bristles, however this time, the fly was even stranger in that it had whip-like hairs all over its body (tiger flies typically have straight bristles) (Fig. 7a). Even better, we also collected a female, the first for this strange group of flies. The female had a typical *Coenosia* appearance (Fig. 7b), and without any strange bristles. Interestingly upon dissection of the flies it was found that they had nectar in their gut, meaning the flies are also nectar feeding and potentially high-altitude pollinators in addition to their predatory behaviour.

Figure 2. *Musca domestica*, the common housefly. USDAgov, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons <https://www.flickr.com/photos/usdagov/8674435033/sizes/o/in/photostream/>

In 2021, during a survey of the flies of Lesotho, high up in the alpine zone (at 3032 meters above sea level!) of the Maloti Mountains, we managed to put up a Malaise trap and do some sweeping in-between the downpour (Fig. 8). The rainfall experienced during that week of collecting can only be described as “bucketing.” This time we collected multiple males and females, another new species, with a mix of characters between the species occurring at Mariepskop and Oudtshoorn. We named it *C. curiosa* (Muller & Midgley 2022), after the curiosity this group of tiger flies has evoked in us (Fig. 9). This new species

Figure 4. Low vacuum scanning electron microscope photo. Based on Muller & Miller (2013) fig. 4a.

Figure 3. Illustrated head of *Coenosia macrotrisetata*. Based on Muller (2019) fig. 9.

Figure 5. Illustrated head of *Coenosia globulisetata*. Based on Muller (2019) fig. 10.

Figure 6. Malaise trap in ravine on top of Mariepskop. Based on Muller (2019), fig. 2.

Figure 7. a: Male of *Coenosia flagelliseta* showing the whip-like hairs (arrowed); b: female, with normal bristles.

Figure 8. Habitat where *Coenosia curiosa* was collected at Afriski Mountain Resort, Lesotho.

is also the first record for the genus in Lesotho, highlighting just how much work is left to do in our region.

As we continue to study these curious little creatures, it offers us a fascinating window into the complexity and diversity of insects, and especially flies in Africa. We deepen our understanding of the living systems around us, and how various interactions, from pollination to predation, contributes to the continued existence of our natural world.

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Figure 9. General appearance of *Coenosia curiosa* male, with the strange head bristles clearly visible.

16 December 1982: The day Vic Carrasco and a band called *Image* rocked Bloemfontein

By Derek du Bruyn

Image 1: Vic Carrasco holding a photo album with newspaper clippings and photos of the day he and the other members of *Image* made music history. (Photo: Derek du Bruyn)

Before 1994, white South Africans – Afrikaners in particular – commemorated the Battle of Blood River on 16 December, also known then as the Day of the Vow or *Gelofedag* in Afrikaans. For conservative whites that day was equal to the Sabbath, a holy day to be respected and not disgraced by worldly activities. In 1982, P.W. Botha was Prime Minister and apartheid still intact; yet, the status quo was challenged not only by black activists but also by white dissidents. Even in conservative Bloemfontein the waters were tested by a small group of progressive whites, who saw the need for social change. On the local pop music scene a few bands and musicians grasped that pop music transcended racial and class divisions. One such band was *Image*.

Formed in 1981, the band (**Image 2**) consisted of Hein du Plessis (electric lead guitar), Tertius du Plessis (drums), André (Diaz) Janse van Rensburg (rhythm guitar), David Mokhutle (keyboard), and bass guitarist and lead vocalist, Vic Carrasco. Born in Bloemfontein to Portuguese and

Image 2: Members of *Image* shortly after the band was formed. From left to right are Tertius du Plessis, Hein du Plessis, Vic Carrasco, André (Diaz) Janse van Rensburg, and David Mokhutle. Hein, André, and David have passed away. (Photo: Vic Carrasco Private Photo Collection)

Mchunu of *Juluka*, as well as PJ Powers of *Hotline* were also established musicians. In fact, during the early 1980s they were the Who's Who of the South African music scene. Needless to say, it was a great compliment for *Image* to be invited to perform at such a star-studded event. It was no surprise though; with their blend of pop, rock, reggae and jazz music styles *Image* was a firm favourite among local pop music fans.

While the superstar pedigree of the event was one thing, the fact that it was called "multiracial" was even more significant. In Bloemfontein, where black and white were still strictly separated by apartheid regulations, multiracial bands were unheard of. Vic explained that *Image* made history when it became the city's and, in fact, the Free State's first multiracial band. During that time this 'achievement' was certainly newsworthy: *The Friend* reported that *Image* "call themselves a multiracial band because they have a Black keyboard player". Vic recalled that *The Friend*, which had a substantial black middle-class readership, was very interested in the band and made effort to promote them.

According to Vic, the band did not become multiracial to make a political statement but for a practical reason. For him and the other band members it was not about race but musical talent. Originally known as *Satin Sounds*, the band's musical ability was hampered by the lack of a keyboard player. Vic had heard of David Mokhutle (**Image 4**), a gifted black keyboard player from Rocklands, who was a member of *The Hectors* during the late 1970s. Vic approached David, who agreed to join them, and a new band named *Image* was born. Vic said that David's musical talent and strong jazz and reggae background became a major boon to *Image*; in fact, it improved the band's musical capacity and expanded its repertoire. In addition, David was well received by the band's predominantly white audiences.

Thursday 16 December 1982 was a sweltering high-summer day in Bloemfontein, but the heat did not deter the crowds. The concert was proudly advertised as "open to all

Image 3: One of the advertisements for the concert that appeared in *The Friend*. (Source: *The Friend*)

Spanish immigrant parents, Vic (**Image 1**) – short for Vitoriano – has been a valued member of Bloemfontein's Portuguese community ever since. Today, he is a well-known Bloemfontein businessman. Paging through a photo album with newspaper clippings of that memorable day, Vic reminisced about the excitement that preceded it. "It was big – we made history!" Vic said. The event was dubbed the "Multiracial Superstar Music Celebration '82" and promoted in the local English media, notably *The Friend*. The local Afrikaans newspaper *Die Volksblad* ignored the event. In the days leading up to the concert, *The Friend* provided media coverage in the form of advertisements and reports about the bands and artists who agreed to perform (**Image 3**). The venue for the open-air concert was the South African Railways sports ground in the Hamilton industrial area near Rocklands (Mangaung).

Naming the event a "superstar music celebration" was no exaggeration: imagine the likes of *The Rockets*, *Hotline*, Margaret Singana and *Juluka* all performing on the same occasion in conservative Bloemfontein. In addition to Margaret, who was an international superstar known for hit songs such as *Good feelings* and *Mama Tembu's wedding*, Johnny Clegg and Siph

Image 4: Keyboard player David Mokhutle, undated. (Photo: Vic Carrasco Private Photo Collection)

“races”, a phrase not often heard or seen in Bloemfontein then. While most of the city’s whites were spending the day in quiet solitude, local pop music lovers flocked to the railways sports ground in their thousands to rock and roll. An entrance fee of R5,00 – a small fortune at the time – was charged. According to newspaper reports more than 3,000 people, most of them black, attended the concert. Some even came from Lesotho to enjoy pop, soul, jazz, Afro-rock and disco music.

Despite being a relatively new band, *Image* (**Image 5**) was a crowd pleaser. *The Friend* reported that *Image* “thumped out some pretty solid reggae numbers and soon had people weaving and twisting to the beat”. Their rendition of Bob Marley classics such as *Is this love* and *Jamming* were well received. *Image* was followed by PJ Powers (**Image 6**) and *Hotline*, Margaret Singana (alias ‘Lady Africa’, **Image 7**), and then “the crescendo came with *Juluka*”, to quote *The Friend*. The crowd went wild when Johnny Clegg (**Image 8**) performed numbers from *Juluka*’s latest album, including *Scatterlings* and *December African rain*. The mood was exhilarating and otherworldly. It was as if the racial

Image 5: *Image* on stage in Bloemfontein on 16 December 1982. (Photo: Vic Carrasco Private Photo Collection)

Image 6: PJ Powers of *Hotline* performing in Bloemfontein on 16 December 1982. (Photo: *The Friend*)

Image 8: Johnny Clegg, alias the ‘White Zulu’, in action in Bloemfontein on 16 December 1982. (Photo: *The Friend*)

Image 7: Margaret Singana performed in a wheelchair because of a stroke she had suffered. (Photo: *The Friend*)

divisions of that time were temporarily transcended by the music because of its universal appeal.

The cherry on the cake for Vic and the other *Image* members was the picture of the band that appeared on the front page of *The Friend* the following day. Not Margaret Singana or *Juluka* or *Hotline*, but them! Taken on stage from behind the band with a view towards the crowd, the picture emanated a message of hope (**Image 9**). Below the photo the newspaper declared in bold black letters that the concert was a “big hit”. To crown it all, *Image* was also shown on national television during primetime news that

Image 9: This photo of *Image* appeared on the front page of *The Friend* on 17 December 1982. David Mokhutle is visible behind the keyboards. (Photo: *The Friend*)

Image 10: Vic Carrasco took this snapshot when *Image* was broadcasted on national television. (Photo: Vic Carrasco Private Photo Collection)

evening. Armed with his camera, Vic took a picture of his television screen the moment the band was shown (**Image 10**). After 41 years he still cherishes the

small snapshot because it froze a moment in time when music created common ground through which people could connect, if only for an afternoon.

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Vic Carrasco Private Photo Collection.

A globally invasive plant species: - *Rumex crispus* L.

By Oladayo A. Idris

R*umex crispus* is an invasive plant species found worldwide. In English, it is known as curley or curly dock, yellow dock, narrow-leaf dock, and sour dock. It is known as ubuhlunga in Xhosa and idolo lenkonyana in Zulu. In Afrikaans, it is known as krultongblaar and occasionally weebblaar. The plant originated in Europe and Western Asia but spread to all continents (except Antarctica) and can now be found in almost all parts of the world. It is said to be among the top five most widely distributed plants in the world. We may have seen it in quite a number of places, primarily in wetlands and on dry land, particularly in agricultural areas, grasslands, and waste lands (see pictures).

Fruits of *Rumex crispus*
(Source: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Rumexcrispus.jpg>)

The genus name "Rumex" is thought to be derived from "rumo", the Latin word for "docks", which describes the ancient Roman practice of sucking the leaves for moisture. Rumex is also believed to have originated from the Latin rumex ("sorrel"), which describes the brown colouration and red tint of the leaves. Another account has it that the word "rumex" probably comes from the Greek word "spear" or "dart", with reference to the spear-shaped leaves. The species name "crispus", on the other hand, means "curled", which alludes to the wavy and curly leaves of the plant. *Rumex crispus* belongs to the family Polygonaceae and is a perennial plant that can survive for several years by means of a fleshy taproot.

Rumex crispus is a herb that grows upright or semi-upright, 40–150 cm tall, with an extended flower stalk or inflorescence. The leaves are smooth with distinctively curled edges and grow up to 24 cm in length. The greenish or reddish-tinged flowers are produced in clusters on the stalk, which produces 2–3 mm long, angular, glossy, dark brown seeds. The root is large and carrot-shaped (it can grow up to 20–30 cm), with a dark brown exterior and a yellow-to-orange interior. As a result of the plant's roots, it can withstand harsh conditions and regenerate when conditions are favorable, giving it considerable longevity.

Submitted by: Dr Oladayo A. Idris, Department of Animal and Plant Systematics

Rumex crispus plant

(Source: <https://plants.ces.ncsu.edu/plants/rumex-crispus/>)

Rumex crispus plant with flower stalk or inflorescence
(Source: <https://ngpherbaria.org/portal/taxa/index.php?taxon=2781&clid=4026#>)

This also makes it difficult to control as a weed. It is tolerant or resistant to a number of herbicides. However, *R. crispus* can be controlled by either a single or combined herbicide. According to studies, sulphonylurea herbicides, such as thifensulfuron, and synthetic auxin herbicides, such as MCPA and Dichlorprop-P, in combination or independently, have been used successfully to control the plant.

This invasive plant does have benefits. The leaves are eaten as a wild vegetable in some parts of the world, including the Eastern Cape Province. It is an excellent source of both vitamin A and C, as well as a source of iron and potassium. Nevertheless, it should be consumed with extreme caution as it has a high antinutrient (oxalic acid and tannin) content, which is linked to irritation of the urinary track and can cause kidney stones. Prior to the development of modern medicine, it was commonly used in traditional medicine for the treatment of wounds, blood and skin diseases, jaundice, sore throats and coughs, for de-worming, as a laxative, astringent, liver stimulant, and in the treatment of cancer.

Seeds of *Rumex crispus*

(Source: <https://plants.ces.ncsu.edu/plants/rumex-crispus/>)

Rumex crispus root

(Source: <https://www.friendsofthewildflowergarden.org/pages/plants/curleddock.html>)

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HOME IS ... WHERE THE CLAW FITS

Pfingstl et al. 2020

By Lizel Hugo-Coetzee

Photo 1: An intertidal mite, *Fortuynia atlantica*, clearly showing claws of all legs. (Photo by Tobias Pfingstl, from Pfingstl et al. 2020)

Almost all terrestrial animals have some type of claw. Vertebrates like mammals, reptiles and birds have their claws made of a protein called keratin, while invertebrates, for example insects, spiders and mites, have claw-like structures made from a combination of chitin, calcium carbonate and sclerotin. A typical claw is a curved, strong and often hard appendage at the end of a limb. Nails in humans are also made of keratin, but don't end in a sharp or curved point. Claws assist with various functions such as walking, climbing, digging, catching and self-defense. Any cat owner can assert that the feline claws are very efficient for defense!

Claws can be very specific to the habitat an animal lives in. As the claw is the primary contact the animal has with the substrate it walks on or through, one would assume that claws have evolved as the animal's best adaptation to the environment. Different claw shapes and sizes may allow animals to occupy a broad range of niches and habitats, and therefore reduce competition for resources with other similar animals. Also, animals move easier on a rough surface where their grip is better. There are a few studies on the correlation of the claw size, surface roughness and ecology of dinosaurs, birds, lizards, insects and oribatid mites.

Oribatids, or beetle mites, are small eight-legged organisms, with one, two or three claws on each leg, acting as decomposers in a variety of habitats like forests, grasslands, freshwater and the marine intertidal zones. The claw-related studies on oribatid mites was done in the marine intertidal zone and mangrove forests. The intertidal zone is the area of the shore that is flooded at high tide and exposed at low tide and is often hit by strong waves. Intertidal oribatids live on rocks, in barnacles or algae mats, and may move up

the rocks or hide in air pockets in rock crevices during the high tide to avoid drowning. Mangroves are trees or shrubs growing in salt water of estuaries and coastal lagoons in the tropics and subtropics. These plants, and the associated animals, are also affected by the tides, but not so much by strong waves. Very few mangrove forests exist in South Africa and they can only be found in certain coastal lagoons and estuaries on the east coast.

In a study done on Japanese Islands, the claws of oribatid mites from various habitats—canopy of mangrove forests (leaves and branches), bark of flooded trunks, intertidal algae and forest floor of an adjacent forest—were compared. Interestingly, the body size of mites did not differ significantly between species from the different habitats, but the claw length and the number of claws did. Mites in the intertidal environment, as well as from the flooded trunks of mangroves mostly had one long, sharp claw, while species from the canopy mostly had three short claws. The single claw of intertidal mites was also nearly twice as long compared to species with a single claw from the forest. Mites with three short claws can move faster on a tree, but cannot grip as tight as the mites in the intertidal zone with one claw. These adaptations probably appeared as a response to the need for speed in unpredictable weather like wind and rain in the canopy, and for a tighter grip against the strong waves in the intertidal zone.

In a further study of only the single claws of intertidal oribatids, species were compared from algae on the rocky shores and algae on the mangrove roots on various tropical and subtropical islands. The shape of the claws differed between the rocky shores and mangrove roots, with higher and more curved claws in species living on the former

Photo 2: Claws of mites from different habitats: A: one claw from an intertidal mite, B: one claw from a terrestrial mite, C: three claws from a canopy mite.

substrate and more slender and less curved claws in the mangrove mites. Higher claws are supposedly more resistant to breakage and also assist with vertical climbing, and a more curved claw enhances clinging ability, all helping to withstand strong waves and to escape the high tide. The surface of the mangrove roots, on the other hand, offers a better grip since the mangrove stems may be hairy or covered by wax or other secretions, thus being more suitable for less curved claws. Also, mangroves do not face the strong waves of the rocky shores.

These studies show that the claw shape and size correlate well with the habitat where oribatid mites live in the intertidal environment. The same may be true for mites living in other habitats. In short, home is where the claw fits.

Photo 4: Mangrove forest. (Photo by Tobias Pflingstl)

Photo 3: Intertidal zone with a strong wave.

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Snakes in the Suburbs of Bloemfontein

By Cora S. Stobie and Michael F. Bates

Have you seen a snake in your garden recently? We are fortunate to have about 120 species of snakes in South Africa. As part of its citizen science initiative, the Herpetology Division of the National Museum's Animal and Plant Systematics Department is managing a Facebook group called *Free State Reptiles and Amphibians (including adjacent areas and Lesotho)*, which seeks to gather photographic and videographic records of all reptiles and amphibians found in this region. These data have resulted in re-assessment of the distribution of the Rinkhals *Hemachatus haemachatus* (Bates & Stobie 2022), Puff Adder and Cape Cobra (Bates et al.

2023), amongst others. We have been particularly interested in our Bloemfontein records as a way to investigate finer-scale distribution patterns, and we are now gaining a better understanding about which species occur in the city suburbs and small holdings.

We currently have photographic records of 19 species of snakes that occur naturally in Bloemfontein, although a few other species are also expected in this area but are rare or live underground. Records of four exotic snake species have also been obtained, together with another two South

A typically marked Puff Adder (*Bitis arietans*) from Bloemfontein. (Photo: Jade Hastings)

African species that normally occur in other provinces but have apparently been translocated to Bloemfontein. Across the wider Free State region, we have amassed accounts for 36 of the 42 snake species expected to be found naturally in this area.

There is a common misconception that most, if not all, snakes are deadly. In reality, very few snakes are actually dangerous, although all should be treated with respect, especially if you are unsure about their identity. Even venomous species are not necessarily 'dangerous' as they usually avoid humans rather than actively pursue and bite them. Of the 19 species we have recorded thus far in Bloemfontein, only three are classified as highly venomous, two as venomous, six as venomous but not dangerous, and eight as non-venomous. The five medically-significant species that we have recorded in and around the city are the Puff Adder (*Bitis arietans*), Cape Cobra (*Naja nivea*), Rinkhals (*Hemachatus haemachatus*), Bibron's Stiletto Snake (*Atractaspis bibronii*) and Highveld Garter Snake (*Elapsoidea sundevallii media*).

An exciting reason for using Bloemfontein as a setting to examine fine-scale records is that the distribution ranges of two medically significant species, the Cape Cobra and the Rinkhals, appear to be located mostly on either side of the city. In general, Cape Cobras are much more likely to occur on the western side of Bloemfontein, while Rinkhals seem to occur almost exclusively in the east. We will be investigating the reasons for this apparent biogeographical structuring.

The three species that are most commonly reported in Bloemfontein—the Puff Adder, Cape Cobra and Brown House Snake—may not actually be the most abundant species in the city. This is perhaps because people tend to post photographs of unusual or venomous species, rather than common ones. However, due to the large numbers of records received for these three species, it does seem that they are relatively abundant in the city, and we will now expand on them.

Distribution of the Puff Adder (*Bitis arietans*) in the suburbs and small holdings of Bloemfontein. Recorded areas are shown in yellow and orange (recent records). This species is frequently reported from the area, but mostly in small holdings and suburbs adjacent to natural grassland/hillocks in the northern and western parts of the city.

The Puff Adder (*Bitis arietans*) is the most commonly reported species on our Facebook group. These snakes are relatively large and stout, usually growing to about one metre in length. They typically have pale, dark-edged, backwards-pointing chevrons on the back, although we recently described a specimen from Bloemfontein that lacks these markings (Bates et al. 2023). This species is involved in the largest number of serious snake bites in the country (Alexander & Marais 2007) due to a combination of its abundance, cryptic colouration, tendency to not move away when approached, and its habit of ambushing prey on or near paths. It expels air with a loud, intimidating sound if threatened, which is probably how it got its common name. The Puff Adder has a cytotoxic venom that destroys cells and soft tissues in the body of its victim. As a result, these snakes are widely persecuted, even though they play a very important role by curbing rodent populations.

The second most commonly reported species is the Cape Cobra (*Naja nivea*). Despite the name, this species is found quite widely across western South Africa, Namibia and Botswana. In the Free State, it is often referred to as *geelslang*. These are quite large snakes, attaining a length of about two metres. They occur in a range of colours, though yellow is the commonest. Their tail tip is usually black or dark brown, and juveniles typically have a dark band across the front of the neck. This species is responsible for the majority of snake bite deaths in South Africa, although, as with most snakes, the Cape Cobra will rather flee than fight. It has a strong neurotoxic venom that acts on the nervous system (including the brain) and inhibits the victim's respiratory system.

Adult Cape Cobra (*Naja nivea*) from Bloemfontein. Note the black-tipped tail typical of this species. (Photo: Jade Hastings)

Juvenile Cape Cobra (*Naja nivea*) from Bloemfontein. Note the black band on the throat, typical of juveniles of this species. (Photo: Jade Hastings)

The third most commonly reported species in Bloemfontein is the Brown House Snake (*Boaedon capensis*). These are non-venomous constrictors with several sharp teeth but no venom fangs. They can bite and draw blood, but should not be regarded as dangerous. Brown House Snakes in the Free State rarely reach one metre in length, although in KwaZulu-Natal they can grow up to 1.4 metres (Alexander & Marais 2007). This snake is generally reddish brown, although it may be darker brown. The head bears

a pair of cream stripes on either side, running from the nostril to above the eye and continuing to the back of the head. When the head is viewed from above, the pale stripes form a 'V' pattern. In some specimens from KwaZulu-Natal, these stripes extend all the way down the body. This is probably the most common snake in Bloemfontein and is easily recognised by its distinctive colour pattern. It may be under-represented on the Facebook group, because it is common and not as 'exciting' as the venomous species, and therefore not photographed. Brown House snakes are often found in urban areas and around houses, where they search for rodents and lizards, and occasionally even birds and bats.

The Herpetology Division is privileged to work with a number of talented and dedicated local snake relocators. These are experts who are trained to remove snakes from homes or businesses in a responsible manner and release them back into the wild. If you come across a snake indoors, calling a snake relocator to remove it would be your best port of call. Trying to remove it yourself can be dangerous! Snakes are an important part of the ecosystem and some species, such as the Brown House Snake and Mole Snake, play an important role in controlling local rodent populations. A small callout fee for the snake relocator's service is generally considered appropriate, especially as fuel is not cheap these days! To get ready for such an emergency, download the African Snakebite Institute app and reach out to someone in your area.

If you have photos of snakes or other reptiles or amphibians that you have encountered in the Free State or Lesotho, please consider posting them to our citizen science Facebook group *Free State Reptiles and Amphibians (including adjacent areas and Lesotho)*. These records allow us to accurately map the current distributions of our species and investigate trends in their distribution over time.

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Distribution of the Cape Cobra (*Naja nivea*) in the suburbs and small holdings of Bloemfontein. Recorded areas are shown in yellow and orange (recent records). This species is frequently reported from the area, but mostly in the west.

Brown House Snake (*Boaedon capensis*) from Bloemfontein. Note the pale stripe on the side of the head, typical of this species. (Photo: Jade Hastings)

Image: Distribution of the Brown House Snake (*Boaedon capensis*) in the suburbs and small holdings of Bloemfontein. Recorded areas are shown in yellow and orange (recent records). This is one of the most common and widespread snakes in Bloemfontein.

Theme: Accelerating youth economic emancipation for a sustainable future.

This year marked the 47th anniversary of the June 16 Soweto and other related uprisings. The Soweto uprising ended tragically with hundreds of young people brutally killed. Following the advent of democracy in 1994, the new democratic government declared 16 June as National Youth Day and June as Youth Month. National Youth Day and Youth Month was celebrated under the Theme: Accelerating youth economic emancipation for a sustainable future.

Exhibition: In Solidarity with the Class of '76: The Mangaung School Boycotts of the Late 1970s and Early 1980s

The National Museum held a temporary exhibition to commemorate the day and to provide background information for visitors about the Mangaung school boycotts of 1976, 1977 and 1980. The exhibition provided a brief overview of some of the boycott actions that were staged by students from black schools in Mangaung during this period. Profiles of six struggle activists who played either a direct or an indirect role in the Mangaung school boycotts were compiled. With the exception of Winnie Mandela, all individuals were interviewed for the National Museum's research projects on **Mangaung's liberation heritage**. The profiled activists speak for themselves through direct quotes from oral history interviews. The exhibition was concluded with a discussion of the aftermath of the Soweto uprisings and how the Soweto students have inspired other students to resist an inferior education system. During the late 1970s and early 1980s school boycotts were powerful tools for the youth to demonstrate and voice their discontent. The exhibition was prepared by the History Department.

Youth Career Expo in the Creative Industries at PACOFS

The National Museum participated in the Youth Career Expo in Creative Industries which was held at PACOFS on 15 June 2023. Learners from schools in Mangaung and out of school youth participated in the career day. They had the opportunity to learn about different career opportunities within creative industries.

The career day was hosted by the Department of Sports, Arts and Culture. Deputy Minister Nocawu Mafu opened the exhibition. She conducted a walkabout of the exhibition and spoke with the exhibitors.

In her keynote address, she said that it was important for young people to remember where they are coming from

they lost their lives for us so that today we can talk about freedom.

The Museum was well represented at the exhibition by the various human and natural science departments. They spoke to the learners and gave them information on museum careers. Both Oliewenhuis Art Museum and ArtBankSA were on hand to represent visual arts and to give learners more information about the visual arts careers.

The Museum's in house Design Department, led by Christo Venter, was responsible for the creative displays at the exhibition. The Karoo Palaeontology Department demonstrated how fossils are prepared and gave information on our fossil heritage in South Africa.

and where they are going. On the morning of 16 June 1976, between ten and twenty thousand black students walked from their schools to Orlando Stadium in Soweto for a rally to protest about being forced to learn in Afrikaans in their township schools. Many young, fearless leaders were shot & killed by the apartheid police. 1976 lost their youth and

Exhibition: Young resistance artist celebrated at Oliewenhuis Art Museum

Dumile Feni, *Untitled*, Undated. Blue ball point pen on back of Gallery 101 visiting card. Drawing: 7 x 3.8 cm, Board: 8.2 x 5.1 cm

Dumile Feni, *Mother and child*, 1965. Pencil sketch. Drawing: 20 x 13 cm, Paper: 29.8 x 20.2 cm

Dumile Feni, *Itchy*, Bronze, 1966, 26 x 16 x 15 cm

Oliewenhuis Art Museum hosted temporary exhibitions to celebrate Youth Month. They also profiled the work of young resistance artists. Resistance artists, **Dumile Feni**, **Julian Motau** and **Ezrom Legae** were the leading resistance artists from as early as the 1960s. The work of these artists reflects their daily struggles of poverty, malnutrition, displacement, and ultimately, the brutal, dangerous, and inhumane circumstances they lived in.

Even though they were young, these artists fearlessly voiced their frustration within their artworks showing their fury at their inescapable plight.

Julian Motau, 1967, *Agony and Sorrow*. Conté on paper, 151 x 93.3 cm

Julian Motau, 1965, *Untitled*, Ink on paper, 60.3 x 39 cm

Ezrom Legae, *Head of a Wise man*. Bronze 3/5, 34 (h) x 12 (d) x 17 (d)

Ezrom Legae, 1980, *Blowing sails*. Pencil drawing, 240 x 170 mm

In his address the Deputy President reminded everybody that the youth of 1976 laid their lives for a purpose. He said that they were driven by a resolve to bring down apartheid in favour of a non-racial, non-sexist, democratic, united, and prosperous South Africa. Their undying spirit and commitment to ending apartheid helped pave the way for a more equitable education system in South Africa. Because of them, the youth in schools are not compelled to acquire an inferior education in the language that has been imposed upon them. Moreover, the youth of 1976 fought for their political freedom; now, we must fight for economic freedom; thus, the theme for this year is "Accelerating Youth Economic Emancipation for a sustainable future."

Official Youth Day Commemoration at Dr Petrus Molemela Stadium in Mangaung

National government commemorated Youth Day on 16 June 2023 at the Dr Petrus Molemela Stadium in Mangaung. Museum CEO, Sharon Snell was in attendance and the keynote address was given by Deputy President Paul Mashatile.

The 2023 Youth Month focused on a spectrum of opportunities for young people in the private sector, public sector, and civil society across the spectrum. This included employment, entrepreneurship, skills development and youth service opportunities and a range of support to assist young people to find traction in the labour market.

Prehistoric Leopard tortoise body mass/size change: climate change or human predation?

By Daryl Codron, Sharon Holt, Beryl Wilson & Liora Kolska Horwitz

Introduction

Animal body size, and in particular body mass (live weight), determines many biological and ecological traits including food intake, metabolism, thermoregulation, generation time, longevity, growth rate, home range size, reproductive strategy, extent of sexual dimorphism and even extinction risk (e.g. Peters 1983; Damuth & MacFadden 1990). Being large comes with certain competitive advantages. First, it is associated with reduced metabolic rates and energy demands per unit mass (an elephant uses much less energy relative to its mass than a mouse does) and, second it is associated with a reduced risk of predation. Consequently, natural selection generally favours evolution towards larger mass, a phenomenon known as Cope's Rule (Damuth & MacFadden 1990).

Climate is another factor influencing body size. In cold environments, animals tend to be larger than in warm ones. This, because their larger volume (mass) to surface area ratios mean that rates of heat production relative to heat loss are also higher, such that larger size keeps them warm. This effect, arguably the first ever macroecological pattern described by natural science, is called Bergmann's Rule (Damuth & MacFadden 1990).

Another explanation for variation in body size is the temperature-size rule; this model predicts that in warmer temperatures an animal's development rate is accelerated (progression through the life cycle towards reproductive maturity) and faster than that of growth rates (increases in mass). In warm climates, this leads to small adult body size in mature animals. While a (negative) latitude-body size relationship has been found both within and across many species, there are known exceptions to this temperature-size rule, such as a species of grasshopper, *Chorthippus brunneus*, that in high temperatures attains a larger body size at maturity than in cool climates (Walters & Hassall 2006).

An additional factor that can influence body size, is human predation – one of the many areas in which humans directly impact the functioning of the natural world (Darimont *et al.* 2009). When hunting or gathering prey, humans tend to target the large, reproductive-aged adult animals since these provide the greatest quantities of meat and other products. Consequently, animals populations exposed to continuous and intensive harvesting by people show rapid changes in body size as the large, mature animals are removed from the population.

Tortoises and body size/mass change

Tortoise remains are commonly found in archaeological assemblages across the globe, indicative of their important role in past human diet. Although tortoises grow throughout their life, researchers examining animal bone assemblages from South African archaeological sites, have reported a reduction in average tortoise size/mass, with larger tortoises in assemblages dated to the Late Pleistocene (Middle Stone Age; ~130,000–40,000 years ago), and smaller ones in the Holocene (Later Stone Age; ~40,000 to 2000 years ago). The researchers attributed the observed size reduction to either: (1) **climate change**, with drier and warmer conditions, coupled with impoverished nutrition, resulting in smaller tortoises being available in the landscape and so available as prey (e.g. Henshilwood *et al.* 2001); or (2) **overkill**, namely that the protein demands of a rapidly-growing human population placed excess predation pressure on large, reproductively mature tortoises, resulting in a reduction in their average body size (e.g. Klein & Cruz-Uribe 1983; Steele & Klein 2005/6, 2013). Both hypotheses are plausible, so the cause of this diminution in tortoise size continues to be debated.

The Later Stone Age (LSA) levels of Wonderwerk Cave in the Northern Cape Province preserve evidence of an association of humans and the Leopard tortoise (*Stigmochelys pardalis*), extending back over the last ~12,000 years, a period that straddles the end of the Late Pleistocene through Holocene epochs (Holt *et al.* 2018, 2019). Notably, the LSA in the cave is marked by extensive climatic fluctuations – a shift from extremely moist to extremely arid conditions (Ecker *et al.* 2018). It is also characterized by a change in the intensity of occupation from ephemeral to intense, as well as by changes in human culture (from the Oakhurst/Kuruman lithic techno-complex to the more recent Wilton and finally the most recent period, the Ceramic LSA (Humphreys & Thackeray 1983). The Wonderwerk Cave tortoises serve as an excellent example with which to examine the relative impact of climatic versus human factors on tortoise size.

To help resolve this debate, we examined tortoise body size/mass throughout the LSA sequence of Wonderwerk Cave (Codron *et al.* 2022). We asked whether: (1) tortoises experienced a net change in their body size/mass over this period, (2) did this lead to a smaller (as expected) average adult size, and (3) can the timing and direction of these changes be explained by climate change or by excessive human predation?

How to estimate body mass/size of fossil animals?

Faced with remains of only bones and teeth, palaeontologists have to use indirect approaches to estimate live weights (body mass) of ancient animals. The most common method of “putting the meat back on the bones” makes use of the fact that the size dimensions of various animal body parts are closely related not only to each other, but to the organisms’ body mass. The precise nature of these size-mass relationships varies depending on the animal group and the studied body part, but in general they follow a pattern of *allometric scaling*, which is explained in Figures 1a and 1b. Provided we can characterize this allometric relationship mathematically – which requires analysis of size data from living animals of known body mass – we can estimate the live weight of fossil animals based on measurements of their remains (Figs. 1c & 1d). Fortunately for us, several previous studies of tortoises have reported a clear correlation between long bone measurements and body mass (e.g. Miller & Richard 2005; Llorente *et al.* 2007; Esker *et al.* 2019).

What to do with fossil tortoise remains

The difficulty working with fossils is that, unlike in Hollywood movies like *Jurassic Park*, complete skeletons are very rarely found. Instead, palaeontologists and archaeologists must work with many isolated bones, or often just bone fragments, to piece together the puzzle of the past. Another hurdle, specific to the tortoise remains recovered from the Wonderwerk Cave sequence, is that many are limb bones or other parts of the post-cranial skeleton, which cannot be measured in living tortoises without killing and dissecting them.

Figure 1. A short introduction to allometric scaling. The body size of an animal is positively related to its body mass (live weight), i.e. as the mass increases, so too does the animals’ size. However, the increase in size is less-than-proportional to the increase in mass, because mass reflects a 3D volume whereas size parameters like length and width, are measured on a ‘flat’ (2-D) surface (the blue curve in (a)); in rare cases, both measures increase at the same rate, i.e. one to one, forming an ‘isometric’ relationship (the straight red line in (a)). In (b), the relationship is reversed and reflects an increase in body mass thus offering a mathematical method that allows calculation of the animal body mass from a measurement of its size (e.g. length). The accuracy of the body mass estimate depends on how strong the relationship is: in (c) individual animals (blue circles) lie close to the allometric curve (black line), and so the estimate is accurate, but in (d) other factors (differences between the sexes, ages, habitats, or many other variables) influence the body mass and so the prediction accuracy is poorer.

To overcome the problem, we used a four-step approach (Fig. 2) in our allometric reconstructions of body mass based on the fossil remains:

- i) We constructed size allometries based on measurements of the shell relative to 11 limb bone measurements, taken on **modern skeletons** of 152 Leopard tortoises collected from farms in the Northern Cape and Free State (Holt *et al.* 2021). These animals had been killed after coming into contact with electrified farm fences, an animal conservation and welfare concern we have discussed elsewhere (Holt *et al.* 2021).
- ii) Next, we took the same five shell measurements (as previously measured on the modern skeletal sample – Fig. 3) on 192 **live** Leopard tortoises released into Grant’s Hill, Bloemfontein, between 2016–2018. We also weighed these animals before release, thereby obtaining data on their body mass to establish their body mass-size allometric equations.

Figure 2. The four-step approach to the allometric reconstruction of the body mass.

Figure 3. Measurements taken on shells of live and skeletonized Leopard tortoises to establish their body mass-size allometric equations.

- iii) We then used these data to construct the allometry of shell length to body mass of these live animals, to measurements of shell and limb bones of the modern skeletal data set. In this manner, we were able to estimate body mass of the dead tortoises based on their limb bone size.
- iv) Lastly, we measured over 350 fossil Leopard tortoise limb bones recovered from the Wonderwerk Cave sequence. Using the data already collected from the live tortoises and modern skeletal sample, we were able to do a back-calculation and estimate the shell dimensions, and so body mass, of each individual found in Wonderwerk Cave.

Figure 4. Location of the farms where the tortoises killed by electric fences were collected, Grant's Hill where the live tortoises were released, and Wonderwerk Cave where the Later Stone Age tortoises were excavated.

Insights from tortoise allometry

Our four-step allometric approach was a success! Results from the analysis of the modern skeletal sample of Leopard tortoises, showed that the 11 post-cranial skeletal elements we had measured, reliably predicted tortoise body mass (>90% of the variation; Fig. 5). Shell size was an even better predictor of body mass, with all five shell dimensions explaining around 99% of the variance in mass! Moreover, the allometric relationships between the different bones and the shell were not influenced by size and shape differences between male and female tortoises, nor did they vary depending on whether the bone was from the left or right side of the skeleton. This is important, because it means the same equations could be applied to the entire Wonderwerk Cave fossil assemblage, for which the identification of the animal's sex from individual bones, is impossible.

Figure 5. An example of how we reconstructed fossil tortoise body mass, using shaft width of the humerus (upper forelimb) as an example. We start by establishing the allometric relationship between the shaft width of the humerus and shell length, based on data from tortoise skeletons {a}. Next, we identified the allometric relationship between the shell length and the body mass, based on measurements of live animals {b}. We then measured the widths of fossil humeri and used the equation from {a} to estimate the shell length of the fossil animal (red segment in {c}). Finally, we took the estimated shell length and, based on the equation derived from {b}, we back-calculated to estimate the live body mass of the fossil animal (red segment in {d}). Note that all fossil animals recovered from Wonderwerk Cave lie in the smaller size range of the species.

In total, our study provided 999 allometric equations that future researchers can use to study the size and mass relationships in Leopard tortoises, and at the same time creating opportunities to ask new questions about their evolution. For example, the ulna (elbow bone) was a notable under-achiever: its dimensions account for less than 50% of the variation in body mass. Such weak allometric relationships imply that the ulna, perhaps, plays less of a role in weight-bearing than some of the others, and so is adapted to perform some other yet-to-be-discovered function.

Evolution of tortoise body mass at Wonderwerk Cave

Armed with this set of reliable allometric equations, we were able to make confident estimates of the live body masses of the fossil tortoises from Wonderwerk Cave. Interestingly, we found that their average body mass was quite low, ranging between 280 and 550 g (Fig. 5d), though this varied a bit between the different skeletal element used for estimation. By contrast, the average body mass of modern live Leopard tortoises in South Africa is between 10 and 20 kg (Boycott & Bourquin 2000). The Later Stone Age people that occupied Wonderwerk Cave clearly did not have a preference for, or access to, very large individuals!

Taking our analysis a step further, we subdivided the fossil sample into seven units based on their age within the cave sequence, with Layer 4d the oldest (dated to ~11,800–10,400

years before present) and Layers 3a/2b the most recent (dated to ~500–2,300 years before present; Table 1). These units are correlated with known changes in past climate, as well as shifts in human cave occupation intensity and the type of stone tool industries found in the cave i.e. tools that share characteristics (Ecker *et al.* 2018; House *et al.* 2022; Fig. 5).

Table 1. Wonderwerk Cave Later Stone Age archaeological levels, dates and past climate reconstructions (based on Ecker *et al.* 2018; Table1; House *et al.* 2022).

Later Stone Age levels	Dates years before present	Past Climate	Stone Tool Industries
1	Historic	fluctuating moist & cool to dry & warm	Disturbed levels
2a			
2b			500
3a	2w300		
3b	4500–2800	dry to warm moist	Wilton
4a/4aLH	6200–4600	wetter	
4b	6900–5900	wetter	
4c	9400–6900	semi-arid	
4d	11800–10400	semi-arid	Kuruman/Oakhurst

Note that the dates for each layer do not overlap indicating breaks in human cave occupation. An exception is Layer 4a/4LH that partly overlaps with Layer 4b. This, as layer 4LH is found only in a specific part of the cave.

Later Stone Age levels are coloured to show tortoise size/mass trends—smaller in 4c & 4d and larger from 4b upwards.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, the average body mass of tortoises was smallest in the oldest parts of the sequence pre-dating 6900 years ago (Layers 4d–c), and thereafter increased, remaining almost constant from ~6900 years ago (Layers 4b) through to the uppermost layers (Layer 2b) some 500 years ago. Thus, the average body mass of tortoises did not change at the transition from the Kuruman/Oakhurst to Wilton stone tool industry or again between the Wilton and Ceramic LSA. Additionally, body mass did not follow the expected trend of cave occupation intensity, which increased from layer 4a/4aLH onwards. The latter serves as a proxy for population size or frequency of cave occupation. If human predation was the key factor influencing body size/mass, then we would expect to find the smallest tortoises in levels experiencing the most intense cave occupation. However, at Wonderwerk Cave the opposite trend is found. The lowest average tortoise body mass occurs in levels 4d and 4c when cave occupation was sparse, while the largest average body mass occurs in Layer 4b onwards, periods that experienced more intense cave occupation (Rhodes *et al.* 2022). Thus, we have no clear evidence that human activity had any adverse impact on the evolution of tortoise size over the occupation time of Wonderwerk Cave layers.

Climate change, on the other hand, probably played a critical role. The earliest part of the Wonderwerk Cave sequence is characterized by warm, semi-arid to

Figure 6. Evolution of the Wonderwerk Cave tortoise body mass through time. Our results indicate a clear increase in average size from the oldest parts of the sequence (Layers 4c and 4d; purple), but no further change through the rest of Holocene (green). The black horizontal bars are medians, and each circle in the graph depicts an individual fossil.

arid conditions with a mixed vegetation of woody C3 plants and C4 grasses. Thus, the low average body mass of tortoises recovered from this period is consistent with the predictions of the temperature-size rule (see Introduction). The average body mass increased in the middle parts of the sequence ~6000 before present (layers 4b and 4a/4aLH), characterized by warm, but moist and humid conditions, perhaps reflecting the greater nutritional value of the food that was available to the tortoises. This we interpret as, ultimately, the outcome of global temperature increases from the Pleistocene to Holocene.

By contrast from level 3b upwards climatic conditions appear to have changed and become warmer and drier than in

4b and 4a/4LH, and an open C4 grass environment, yet the average tortoise body mass did not change over this period. It might be that the change in climate at this point in time was too small, or of too short duration, to have had a significant impact on tortoise body size/mass.

Conclusion

The Later Stone Age Leopard tortoise assemblages of the Wonderwerk Cave sequence documents an approximately 12,000-year-long association with humans. Using information derived from hundreds of measurements of modern Leopard tortoises in the region, we were able to reconstruct changes in the tortoise body mass pattern over this period. Our study revealed an evolutionary shift to increased body size/mass as recently as the Middle Holocene, ~6900 before present.

The influence of climate on the body size/mass of many vertebrate species is not limited to the past. With global warming we are witnessing size change in numerous species, from small rodents to large sized mammals (e.g. Yom-Tov & Geffen 2011; Nengovhela *et al.* 2020). Notably, global warming may adversely affect reptiles (including tortoises) specifically their incubation temperature (Booth 2006), and so impact hatchlings in terms of their size as well as growth rate, sex, shape, colour, behaviour etc. It may also affect the distribution range of reptile species. Consequently, trends observed in the fossil record, such as at Wonderwerk Cave, may improve our understanding of the outcome of climate change on present-day biodiversity.

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A PEAK IN CABINET'S OF

BY Sudré Havenga

1. A PIECE OF GERMAN INGENUITY

Factory-produced clocks were first credited to the Lenzkirch Uhrenfabrik, located in the small town of Lenzkirch in the German Black Forest region. Lenzkirch is one of the finest German clockmakers and was founded in 1849 in Lenzkirch, Germany by Eduard Hauser (1825-1900). In 1851, Eduard Hauser and Ignaz Schoepperle joined forces with 5 other men, Franz Josef Faller, Paul Tritscheller, Johann Nikolaus Tritscheller, Joseph Wiest and Nickolas Rogy to form the Aktien-gesellschaft fur Uhrenfabrikation, Lenzkirch (Stock Holder Corporation for Clock Manufacturing, Lenzkirch). The Lenzkirch factory came into full production in 1860 and continued until 1932. Hauser studied clock making while travelling in France, Switzerland, and England. Under his leadership the factory was modernised with steam engines powering all of the machines. The factory also owned a sawmill and foundry while tool and die makers were employed and gold and silver plating was done in house.

A 19th Century Lenzkirch enamel and bronze mantel clock is preserved in the National Museum, Bloemfontein's history collection. The bronze work includes garlands, flowers, bows framed by two Bacchus faces. Bacchus is a Roman god primarily associated with wine, agriculture, and fertility. He was also the patron of the arts and the protector of the theatre. This piece features a cobalt blue enamel body, porcelain face with Roman numerals and finely crafted filigree gilt hands. The eight-day twin train movement carries the Lenzkirch hallmark: Lenzkirch, the pine cone and A G U (Aktien Gesellschaft fuer Uhrenfabrikation).

Lenzkirch clocks are highly collectable because their quality and beauty set them apart from all other clocks made in the Black Forest region.

2. KING CHARLES II AND THE INVENTION OF THE POCKET WATCH

Did you know that it was the English king, Charles II (1630 – 1685) who started a new style of 'pocket watch'?

The idea of a timepiece that could easily be carried around dates back to the early 1500s when German inventor and master locksmith Peter Henlein invented the first ever 'pocket watch' in Nuremberg, Germany. However, these early watches were very heavy and somewhat awkward. Hulking in shape, there were pins and wedges

TO OUR CURIOSITIES

& Elmar du Plessis

holding them together, and they were rather worn around the neck as a pendant because they could not fit inside a pocket.

In the years that followed many new designs and improvements followed: a minute-hand was introduced; the number of wheels within the watch mechanism was increased thus decreasing the number of times the watch had to be wound up each day, all allowing for a more accurate timepiece. But it was not until the Restoration of the British monarchy and the return of King Charles II in 1660 that watches became small enough to fit inside a pocket.

Soon after his return to England, King Charles II introduced a new male fashion indicative of England's independence from any foreign influences, especially that of France. Noblemen had long worn variations of trousers and jackets, mostly influenced by the French doublet, until the king declared the vest part of the new fashion of clothes that should be worn at court. The vest was, unlike the French doublet, a tight-fit, knee-length garment that followed the line of the coat it was worn underneath. It was made from plain wool, devoid of any ribbon, lace or gold thread. For King Charles II this attire presented the ideals of self-reliance and independence; simultaneously giving the English wool trade a boost.

Shortly afterwards King Charles II started placing his watch inside the vest pocket, and so introduced us to the "pocket watch" that, soon enough was considered a status piece all over the world. Because of this, the shape of the pocket watch transitioned from being drum-shaped cylinders to a flat design, so it easily fitted into the vest pocket. Glass was also used for the first time to cover the face of the watch, offering the time dials reliable protection.

By 1700, the silhouette of the vest was much simplified and shortened, giving it the name waistcoat as it only reached to the waist and no further. However, by the late 20th century the significance of the waistcoat as a status symbol began to fade. It was no longer needed as a place to store a pocket watch because wristwatches became more popular by the day.

A variety of pocket watches dating from the early 20th century is housed in the History Collection.

photo 5 (a – c): Pocket watches, circa 1900s in the History Collection.
(photo: Marelle van Rensburg)

3. AN ANIMAL DRAWN VEHICLE NAMED FOR A PIECE OF CLOTHING

The cape cart was one of the most popular vehicles in South Africa from the late 1850s to the 1930s, and many examples of it can still be found to this day.

The name refers to the tent-like hood of this two-wheeled vehicle. In Afrikaans the cape cart is commonly known as a 'kapkar', referring to the *kappie* (bonnet) worn by many Afrikaner women at the time. The English 'cape cart', accordingly, refers to a type of loose coat, most often without sleeves, that is fastened at the neck and hangs from the shoulders.

The cape cart was drawn by two or more horses and could take at least two passengers, or up to four if necessary. Baggage was carried on a rack at the back, and in a pinch, passengers too. In the days before railways, the cape cart was often used to carry post. It could cover the distance at an average speed of 8 miles per hour, making it one of the fastest means of transport available at the time.

On display in the Wagon Museum, situated at 95 St George Street in Bloemfontein, is one such cape cart.

4. BLOODLETTING A CURE FOR EVER ILLNESS

Bloodletting (Phlebotomy) is one of the oldest medical treatments known to man. It is the practice of taking or removing blood from a person with the intention to treat, manage or cure an illness. This ancient treatment was based on the Humoral theory developed by the medical theorist Alcmaeon of Croton (c. 540–500 BCE). Hippocrates (considered the father of modern medicine) is credited for applying this theory to medicine in the fourth century BCE. In short humoral medicine was based on the principle that an imbalance in the blood fluids of a person namely blood; phlegm; yellow bile and black bile caused physical and mental sickness. This perceived imbalance was treated by bloodletting, purging or induced vomiting.

Bleeding a person was thought to rid the body of impurities and for this reason was used to treat a number of ailments - fever, madness, anaemia, smallpox, epilepsy, gout etc. Since treatment options were limited and antibiotics were unheard of, bloodletting was the go-to treatment for most physicians often with catastrophic results. It is believed that the following famous people were bled to death or at least died prematurely due to vigorous bloodletting: George Washington (1732-1799); King Charles of England (1630-1685); Queen Anne (1665-1714) and Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart (1756-1791).

The first bloodletting tools were made of sharp pieces of wood and stone. By the 15th century the most popular instrument was the thumb lancet and by the 18th century spring lancets and scarificators (could make multiple cuts in one motion on the release of a trigger) were used. The

bloodletting tool still readily found in antique collections today is the fleam (fleame, flem, flue or flew). A fleam consist of two- or three-blades that fold into a brass or horn case. The tips of the blades are triangular in shape and the blades are arranged from large too small. Fleam's were intended for animal bloodletting, but the smaller blades were used on humans as well. The size of the animal determined the size of the blade a person would use. The blade was placed over the jugular vein and driven in with a wooden club known as a fleam- or blood stick.

Image: Two veterinary fleams housed in the object collection of the National Museum.

G 2033 carries the makers mark James Rodgers & Co / Cutlers Sheffield which dates to c. 1842

G 1731 carries the makers mark Encore / [Thomas] Turner & C / Sheffield

photo 6: Cape cart on display at the Wagon Museum

photo 7: Voortrekker bonnet (Afr. *kappie*) in the History Collection.

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Image: Dr Munyaradzi Mushonga receiving an introduction through traditional praise singing before delivering the keynote address at the Exhibition opening at Oliewenhuis Art Museum.

Decolonial Aesthetics/Aesthesis in Pitika Ntuli's *Azibuyele Emasisweni* (Return to the Source) Art Exhibition

By M Mushonga

The Man/Woman in the Mirror

I am going to talk about what I think are some of the key lessons we learn from Pitika Ntuli's *Azibuyele Emasisweni* (Return to the Source) art which scored a first at the Global Fine Arts Awards. Yet in order to speak to the art, it is important to know the person behind the art. Yet, what do I know about he who has been described by many as an exceptional artist. From where I stand, Pitika is not an exceptional artist because exceptional artists do not exist. There has never been an exceptional artist anywhere, anytime. What has always existed are good thinking-doers and doing-thinkers who die for art to live. Then, what do I know about he who is

a sculptor; a cultural ambassador, a historian, and according to Ngugi Wa Thiongo, a poet of resurrection; he who loves to die a little many times in order to give birth to another piece of art; a predatory poet who violates linguistic principles, strangles morphology, and murders syntax before locking them up in muted cages of sounds; a spiritual healer yet also the spirit himself. What do I know about an activist writer and decolonial scholar who spent 32 years of his life in political exile? What do I know about he who refused to succumb to the defonation of a cultural bomb at the centre of his universe? What do I know about he who resisted to get the software of European knowledge and memory downloaded into his hard disk of African Spiritualism, gnoseology, and memory?

Image: Pitika Ntuli's Azibuyele Emasisweni (Return to the Source) Exhibition at Oliewenhuis Art Museum

Africa-Centred and Planet-Centred Azibuyele Emasisweni

I have titled my talk *Decolonial Aesthetics/Aesthesis in Pitika Ntuli's Azibuyele Emasisweni (Return to the Source) Art (Exhibition)* to speak to Pitika's life story and intellectual interventions that challenge orthodox epistemology and philosophy. Decolonial aesthetics/aesthesis therefore refers to

ongoing artistic projects responding to imperial globalization and global coloniality. It is the terrain where Pitika Ntuli and artists around the world are contesting the legacies of modernity by being involved in projects of re-existence in artistic practices all over the world. Decolonial aesthetics is about the liberation of sensing, sensibilities, tastes, emotions, beauty, et cetera, that remained/remain trapped by modernity and its darker side: coloniality.

Pitika's Azibuyele Emasisweni and all his artist works challenge the [Hegelian, Roperian and Hobbesian] idea of a pre-European Africa as a land of childhood, an Africa without history, an Africa that existed outside the geographical reach of reason, a place where there was no account of Time, NO Arts, No Letters, No Society except WARS & DEATH. To weave his art around themes such as Earth; Water; Air; Fire; African Spirituality; Indigenous Knowledge Systems; and Healing, Azibuyele Emasisweni calls upon us to be African again, and to refuse to be photocopies of the West. Pitika, like Ngugi wa Thiongo and many like-minded thinkers, is making a passionate call to 'return to the base'. What is the base? The base is the people and their languages, cultures, spiritualities, cosmologies, belief systems, sensibilities, and their gnoseologies (knowledges).

Pitika's art simply demonstrates the indisputable fact that all human beings are not only born into valid knowledge systems but are also legitimate knowers and producers of legitimate knowledge. It tells us that all organisms need to know in order to live and have to live in order to know. For without living there is no knowing and without knowing there is no living. Without various concoctions of roots, leaves of trees, herbs, steaming, belief systems, spiritual interventions and various ways of thinking and doing, Africa could not have fared better than other continents in the brutal fight against COVID-19. Pitika summoned bones to heal many bodies and souls during the moment of COVID-19. Yet, the healing touch of Pitika's bones predates and postdates the pandemic in its obvious attempts to not only heal the deep colonial wounds of slavery, enslavement, genocides, colonialism, apartheid, imperialism, land theft and appropriations, linguicides, culturecides, epistemicides, and the endless structural adjustments of African lives and economies by the West, aided by autocratic, incompetent, greedy and corrupt African leaders, but also to unsettle and disrupt orthodox forms of cure, treating and healing. Azibuyele Emasisweni art is a measure of resilience in both dark and happy moments.

The Humans and 'Mother' Earth/Nature

Angry and abused earth is the reason of our suffering in the 21st century. 'Mother' earth is angry because the Imperial Man decided to raise himself above nature, and to remove himself from nature and as part of nature, to colonise nature, and turn nature into a natural resource to be exploited, changing its functions dramatically.

To return to the source is therefore a clarion call for all of us to recognise the mutuality between **humans** and **earth**. Civilisations like those in Africa respected mountains, trees, pools of water, springs, valleys, rivers, forests as other beings and as the abode of goddesses and gods. The forces of creation and those created were part of the same reality. But the arrival of the Imperial Being changed all this. He began to see Africans as barbarians who were failing to rise above the state of nature. There was now confrontation between nature and the West, and victory was not always on nature's side. The natural world was now a servant of man rather than a partner. The current climate crisis and

enduring pandemics are a sign that our planet earth is in dire need of repair. It is calling our attention to the process of re-membering, reconstitution, and putting it together as Pitika does with metal, wood, stones and bones. That is why Pitika tells us that he does not copy nor work like nature, but 'works with nature'. This is a call to planet-centred and African-centred thinking, doing, sensing, and living. It is a reminder that we need to rethink alternative relationships with each other and with non-humans, rooted in reciprocity and responsibility. Achille Mbembe is convinced that it is the fear of our planet earth turning into a hothouse where we could be cooked to death (and become the tools for Pitika's art) that is propelling the desire to colonise other planets like Mars, Jupiter, etc. Yet, for now, the Earth is our only shared roof and shelter, and for that reason, we must work hard to preserve it. As Pitika posits, by killing and destroying the environment in the chase for individual riches and wealth, we are actually killing ourselves because we are the environment as the environment is us. Blowing up mountains just to obtain one gram of gold?

Being (Human) and the Bones

Besides elevating himself above nature, the Western Man also elevated himself above all other 'Beings' and relegated others to the domain of perpetual 'Becoming'. Western philosophy got preoccupied with the idea of 'Being' vs the 'Rest'. On the contrary, African philosophy is preoccupied with issues of compositionality or ethics of care (ubuntu) and relationality. By bringing together 33 local and international talent to breathe life into Azibuyele Emasisweni Art, Pitika demonstrates the importance of incompleteness in our lives. Anyone interested in understanding the illusion of autonomy and the importance of incompleteness and interdependency must read Amos Tutuola's bewitching novel, *The Palm-Wine Drinkard*. Drawing on West African Yoruba oral folktale tradition, Amos Tutuola chronicles the incredible adventures of an alcoholic man and his search for his dead palm-wine tapster. As he ventures through the land of the dead, he encounters a host of supernatural and often terrifying beings – among them the complete gentleman who was returning hired body parts to their owners. This gentleman had hired the best body parts to win the heart of the most beautiful lady in the land. When he reached where he hired the left foot, he pulled it out, and gave it to the owner and paid him; and when he reached the place where he hired the right foot, he pulled it out and gave it to the owner and paid for the rentage, until he was a complete skeleton. In the *Palm-Wine Drinkard*, Tutuola shows that the supernatural is quite simply natural. Gods, death, spirits and the curious and terrible creatures of the bushes and forests take on human nature, just as humans develop the supernatural attributes of these ordinarily invisible forces in their lives. The boundaries between nature and culture, village and town, home and bushes, human and supernatural, rational and superstitious, primitive and civilised, tradition and modernity, Africa and the West, are collapsed. The idea of mobile Africa which pays more attention to the business of repair, to curating life – to matters of breathing and respiration as opposed to the

hierarchisation and controlling of populations comes alive. Items that would rather be considered as rubbish such as bones are resurrected. That is why Homi Bhabha described Pitika as a curator of life for his ability to release "the spirit and the story that has rested deep in the bones" and "make the silence of bones... speak and sing." Pitika is the only person I know who can make bones live. Deep in the Valley of Dry Bones, the Almighty God asked the prophet Ezekiel, 'Son of man, will these bones live?'. Ezekiel replied, 'O Sovereign Lord, you alone know'. 'Prophecy over these bones, that they may live', God commanded Ezekiel. Ezekiel did as commanded, and the bones came to life – the frontal and nasal bones; the parietal and preseptal bones; the maxilla and scival bones; the palatine and lacrimal bones, and the rest of the bones joined together in the split of a second and Ezekiel stood there, perplexed, and frightened. Yet, in this 21st century, we have someone who works with elephant, rhino, giraffe and horses' bones to challenge death through their artistic resurrection. His name is Pitika aka Spirit Ntuli. He says that he works with bones because they 'are more durable and the evidence that we were alive 3.5 million years ago'.

To deploy bones to 'divine the state of the nation in a season of anomie' is to be truly innovative and to demonstrate the importance of repair. Matter such as bones, metal, wood, etc, is folded, remixed, welded, blended in new combinations according to a logic of composition. Putting together and repairing what has been broken up as opposed to tearing apart is Pitika's 'daily bread' that turns him into a thinking-doer and doing-thinker.

Conclusion

Pitika's Azibuyele Emasisweni art is gesturing us towards decolonial aesthetics/aesthesis of re-humanizing, remembering, re-constituting, repairing, re-existence and re-worlding. How do we do this? I want to offer three concluding points on how to do this. First, in the US, a movement called *Decolonize This Place* is demanding the decolonization of the Brooklyn Museum in New York City. It accuses the museum of putting art first before people. Their slogan reads: **They Want the Art, Not the People.**

Decolonize This Place demands that institutions to go beyond diversity, equity and inclusion. It poses the following tormenting and unsettling questions: *Why does an institution need professional curators? An Executive Director? A Board of Trustees? Decolonize This Place* sees these professionalized roles as elite concentrations of power. It wants to see museums and similar institutions as places of collective care and not places of curation. In light of this, I challenge the Bloemfontein National Museum and all museums on the continent and around the world to rethink their approaches to art. Museums are gently cautioned against the default response of institutions to a crisis of governance by containing and assimilating the crisis through internal processes that allow for stalling, evasion, and damage control while leaving the system that perpetuates injustice intact.

Second, for universities, *Azibuyele Emasisweni art is the best example of how to decolonise knowledge. Pitika decolonises knowledge by recentering Africa and its rich Indigenous Knowledge Systems. Quantum physics and mechanics, history, astronomy, mathematics, geometry and all the disciplines and interdisciplines in the sciences and humanities come to life in Azibuyele Emasisweni.* To return to the source/base speaks to the need to see Africa as the centre from which we think and look at the world instead of the converse. In all his artwork, Pitika recognises the importance of where he begins to tell his story, conscious of the fact that a story that starts in the wrong place cannot arrive at the right conclusion. In his book, *The Haitians: A Decolonial History*, Jean Casimir declares:

My position of strength comes from observing the outside world through Haitian eyes. When I do the opposite I place myself in a position of inferiority by accepting the definition put in place by the gaze of another.

Pitika's decolonial *Azibuyele Emasisweni art* demonstrates unlimited possibilities of healing; healing the bones of those who perished during colonial and postcolonial genocides and aggrandizement; and unlimited possibilities of engendering decolonised and re-humanized pedagogies. Pitika tells us that 'our common survival depends on us working collectively to both heal ourselves and the earth'.

Finally, to heal ourselves and the earth, to avoid a repeat of the ugly past, and to engender pluriversal pedagogies, we need to find common ground and to start building one thing that is key to every individual, relationship, institution, government, nation, and planet earth. If that one thing is removed, it will destroy the most successful individual, nation, economy, civilisation, and 'mother' earth. Yet, if that one thing is leveraged, it has the potential to create unparallel success and happiness. That one thing is **LOVE**. President Nelson Mandela once remarked, 'If people can learn to hate, they can learn and be taught how to love.'

We must begin to learn to love and to teach others love. To love thy neighbour and nature, thy neighbour loving thy neighbour and nature, and thy neighbour loving thy neighbour and nature, until love becomes **pandemic**. We must have the wisdom, knowledge and courage to love; and be ready to re-create the world by creating a peaceful society under social, economic and political conditions that may not permit love and peace.

Figure 3. Pigments used during the contact period.

PUBLIC ROCK ART SITES OF SOUTH AFRICA: KRAMBERG PRIVATE GAME RESERVE

By Shiona Moodley & Jens Kriek

Travellers along the scenic R58 between Aliwal North and Burgersdorp in the Eastern Cape Province will notice the massive, flat-topped Kramberg Mountain to the south. It is an outlier of the magnificent Stormberg Mountain Range further south, itself part of the Drakensberg, South Africa's longest and highest mountain range.

Kramberg is a sandstone colossus rising over six hundred metres above the surrounding Highveld plains and is currently part of a privately owned game reserve. Along its flanks and foothills are numerous rock shelters, some with magnificent pre-colonial rock art. Imagery varies from the San fine-line paintings characteristic of this region to later depictions of pastoralists with cattle and sheep. Perhaps the most interesting rock art site in the reserve is a deep overhang with an inner cave, situated high up the side valley of the Langkloofspruit. The overhang is roughly 25-m wide and the associated archaeology include pieces of pottery. The talus slope is covered in crypto-crystalline silicate and hornfels lithics. The painted panels are continuous along the length of the shelter and represent both hunter-gatherer (San) and herder (Khoekhoen) imagery. The shelter shows signs of continuous use over hundreds of years. The older classical phase of the San paintings, dated to possibly a thousand years ago, are below the more recent contact phase San paintings that date to roughly 200 years ago.

Contact Imagery

The San were the first people to inhabit southern Africa and for thousands of years they lived unperturbed by other cultural groups. Roughly 2000 years ago other cultures began the gradual move south, displacing and/or merging with the San. These cultures include the Khoekhoen herders, agropastoralists who are the ancestors of Black South Africans, and within the last few hundred years, European settlers. Contact imagery refers to the San rock art that was made during contact with other cultures. As the San encountered herders and farmers, we see the presence of domesticated animals in their rock art.

Fat-tailed sheep

Fat-tailed sheep (Figure 2) had been acquired by hunter-herders before they entered southern Africa. The earliest dated sheep bones in southern Africa are from an approximately 2270-year-old site in the Erongo Mountains of Namibia (Pleurdeau et al. 2012).

Some San eventually acquired sheep from the herders, as a source of wealth and food. There is also evidence to suggest that they incorporated fat-tailed sheep into their

Figure 1. Kramberg Rock Art Site.

Figure 2. Farmer herding fat-tailed sheep.

spiritual life (Huffman 1983). The large amount of fat in the tails meant that this animal, like the eland, had supernatural potency. The San associated animal fat with power that can be harnessed by the spiritual healers to enter trance and perform duties to maintain the wellbeing of the community.

The agropastoralists moved from East Africa into southern Africa. They were mixed farmers, meaning that they had herds of domestic animals, and cultivated crops. The farmer in Figure 2 is holding a knobkerrie (short wooden club with a large knob at one end) and a hat that looks similar to European-style hats, suggesting contact with European settlers.

Changes in trade networks

The oldest San paintings are considered the Classic Phase and may, in some places, date to as far back as 25,000 years (Ouzman & Loubser 2000). These paintings are generally the most numerous and show exquisite fine-lined detail, with careful shading causing gradual shifts in colour. The contact period rock art in Kramberg is far more recent, and this is evident in the pigments used. Mixed farmers came to this area perhaps 600 years ago, while the white settlers arrived around 200 years ago.

These settlers disrupted the usual trade networks that existed among San groups for thousands of years. As a result, access to pigments became scarce and the San had to use what was available (Ouzman & Loubser 2000; Lewis-Williams & Pearce 2004). The paints became powdery, with the increased use of grey, black, bright orange and yellow (Figure 3). The San also started to use inferior bonding agents causing much of the paintings to appear smeared. The animal and human figures became blocked in appearance, and there is a sharp distinction between the colours.

RESPONSIBLE VISITOR BEHAVIOUR AT ROCK ART SITES

According to the National Heritage Resources Act no. 25 of 1999 it is illegal to damage or alter a rock art site in any way without the necessary permit from the South African Heritage Resources Agency (SAHRA).

Always ask permission before visiting rock art sites.

Never touch the rock art.

Never pour liquid on rock art.

Move carefully at rock art sites so as not to kick up dust.

Never make any markings on any surface of the rock art site.

Never remove any archaeological artefact from the rock art site.

Visit rock art sites with an informed person or tour guide – it adds greatly to the experience.

Excursions to the rock art sites in Kramberg Private Game Reserve are strictly by appointment only and accompanied by a guide.

Shields, Therianthropes and Potency

The white hourglass shaped motifs in Figure 4 are Sotho-Tswana shields used during the nineteenth century (Tylden 1946). This painting is extremely interesting because it shows two San men carrying shields and knobkerries, with arbitrary placements of spears and knobkerries. Both men have antelope heads, and the panel is covered in white dots. This panel is concerned with issues of supernatural potency and altered states of consciousness (trance). The white dots are *n/om* that is activated during a trance dance. The antelope-headed men are therianthropes—shamans who are partially transformed into animals. The San believed that the shaman harnessed the *n/om* of certain animals to enter trance (Lewis-Williams & Dowson 1989). These therianthrope shamans are using Sotho-Tswana weapons to fight evil. This tells us that there was a prolonged contact between these two groups, and certain aspects of the Sotho-Tswana culture and symbolism was incorporated into the San cosmology (Loubser & Laurens 1994).

The rock art in Karmberg Private Game Reserve holds great social and spiritual significance because it tells us about the interaction between different groups of people over many years. It reminds us that cultures are not confined to strict boundaries but are fluid and are in constant flux.

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Figure 4. Shamans fighting evil spirits using shields, knobkerries and spears.

A LIFE CUT

SHORT BY

A PARCEL

BOMB

THE REMARKABLE LIFE OF ANTI-APARTHEID ACTIVIST ONKGOPOTSE ABRAM TIRO

“It is better to die for an idea
than to live for an idea that
will die.”

By Khotso Pudumo

Onkgopotse Abram Ramothibi Tiro, photo credit Mayibuye Archives University of Western Cape (UWC).

A reflection on the legacy of Onkgopotse Abram 'Ramothibi' Tiro in the context of the history of liberation education.

Every age has its own sages and visionaries, men and women who face the demands of their time with courage and determination while leaving their footprints in history. Onkgopotse was an outstanding man who challenged the apartheid regime and was seen as a formidable enemy by the state. Considering his humble beginnings and rise to become a student activist, and the many hats he wore in the various organizations he served, his ultimate goal was the liberation of all South Africans.

Abram Onkgopotse 'Ramothibi' Tiro was born on 9 November 1945 in a small town of Dinokana near Zeerust in Ngaka Modiri Molema District, North West Province. Onkgopotse was raised by a single mother, Moleseng Anna 'MmaAbram' Tiro. He was his mother's firstborn followed by his two sisters (Tsholofelo and Mmatiro) and two brothers (Mogomotsi and Mookami). MmaAbram was a domestic worker in Emmerentia, a suburb of Johannesburg in Gauteng Province. Onkgopotse's childhood was difficult, his mother and his extended family who brought him up were people of limited means. They struggled to put him and his siblings through school.

Onkgopotse's uncle Ned Onkgopotse Tiro, after whom Abram was named, and his aunt, Bafedile Masoba, had a profound influence on his upbringing and honed his leadership skills. Abram Onkgopotse spent some time with his uncle and helped him run a bakery.

Abram began his schooling at Ikalafeng Junior Primary School and later went to Keobusitse Senior Primary School, Motswedi Secondary School, and Barolong High School in Mafikeng. He matriculated in 1968 and passed with first-class marks. From 1957 to 1960, for three full years in Dinokana there was no schooling due to riots. During that period, Onkgopotse worked full-time at a manganese mine, where he earned 75c a week and later R3 when he was promoted.

After completing his schooling, Onkgopotse enrolled for a degree in Humanities at the University of the North (Turffloep), currently the University of Limpopo. In his final year, he was elected as the president of the Student Representative Council (SRC). During the graduation ceremony in 1972, Onkgopotse harshly criticised the Bantu Education Act of 1953. That speech became known as the "Turffloep Testimony". He was expelled from the university because of his controversial speech that angered the authorities at the university.

Despite demonstrations by students under the SRC, Tiro was not readmitted. One of his earlier encounters with the administration as SRC President was when they wanted to delete two of his articles, which they considered "objectionable", from the student diary: the South African Student Organisation (SASO) Policy Manifesto and the Declaration of Students' Rights. The university administration seized the diaries and detached the articles. After the diaries were returned to the student body, the students burned them.

Onkgopotse's expulsion from Turffloep had consequences that the university's administration could not have foreseen. In May 1972, a series of strikes started at black campuses across the country in support of him, all major black campuses joining a solidarity strike in less than one month, and on 2 June 1972, students at the University of Cape Town demonstrated in support of Onkgopotse.

In 1973, Onkgopotse became involved in the activities of the Black Consciousness Movement (BCM). He not only participated in the first major protest in 1972 at Turffloep but was also at the center of the action. When the SASO/Black People's Convention (BPC) leaders were banned in 1973, he took over as SASO's permanent organizer. He was elected as the president of the Southern African Students' Movement (SASM), an affiliate of the All-African Students' Union.

After his expulsion from Turffloep, Onkgopotse was offered a post to teach history at Morris Isaacson High School in Central Western Jabavu, Soweto. It was during this brief period there that he established his place in the history of the freedom struggle.

Onkgopotse introduced his pupils to the philosophy of the BCM and launched a campaign to encourage students to question the validity and content of the history textbooks approved by the Department of Bantu Education. When his presence at Morris Isaacson High School became known, the authorities were alarmed.

Morris Isaacson High School became known as the "cradle of resistance" and produced student leaders like Teboho 'Tsietsi' Mashinini, Murphy Morobe, and Khotso Seatlholo, to name a few who headed the Soweto riots in 1976. Onkgopotse was actively involved in the formation of the SASM, which

Onkgopotse Tiro delivering the Turffloep Testimony. (Photo from book Parcel of Death, the Biography of Onkgopotse Abram Tiro)

along with the SASO were affiliates of the BCM and aimed to influence the student politics in southern Africa. In 1972, he was elected Honorary President of the movement at a congress in Lesotho. However, it did not take long for the apartheid government to force school headmasters to fire students who were employed after their expulsion from universities. After six months at Morris Isaacson, the principal was coerced into dismissing Onkgopotse.

Onkgopotse travelled all over southern Africa, including Lesotho, Swaziland and Botswana, and won great support for the Black Consciousness philosophy. However, when he learned in late 1973 that the police were planning to arrest him, he fled to Botswana, where he played a leading role in the activities of the SASM, SASO and BPC. He led a simple life at the Roman Catholic Mission in Kgale, a village about 20 km from Gaborone (the capital city of Botswana) but was influential in establishing contacts with militant revolutionary groups such as the Palestine Liberation Organisation in 1973.

On 1 February 1974, while still in Botswana, Onkgopotse was filling out an application form to continue his studies at UNISA when a student handed him a package purportedly sent by the International University Exchange Fund. When Onkgopotse opened it, a parcel bomb exploded, killing him instantly.

Onkgopotse was the first South African freedom fighter who was hunted by the apartheid government beyond South African borders to have him assassinated with a parcel bomb.

Lawrence Mphafe was the student who was asked to deliver a parcel to Onkgopotse. Along the way, the parcel emitted a "weird rattling sound" that caused Lawrence to inspect it. The parcel was from the International University Exchange Fund (IUF) in Geneva, Switzerland, and was addressed to Mr Abraham O Tiro, St Joseph's College, Private Bag 13, Kgale, Gaborone, Botswana.

Lawrence delivered the parcel as instructed and was thanked by Onkgopotse, who suggested that he could have offered him a cold drink, but he had just finished it during lunch earlier. As Lawrence left, about 30 meters away he bumped into the principal of St Joseph's College, Father John Corrigan, exchanging greetings as they passed each other. After a few steps there was a loud blast. They both turned back and their eyes locked.

The room in which Onkgopotse attempted to open the parcel bomb looked unbelievable. There were holes in the wall and the floor, and the furniture was wrecked. The explosion was so fierce that it shattered windows, partially destroyed the ceiling, dented aluminum pots, and blew an iron stove with so much force that it cracked and flew to the other end of the room. Onkgopotse was disemboweled and his face disfigured. It seemed that Onkgopotse attempted to shield his face with his hands; however, the bomb severed and crushed his hands so finely that they were never found.

Onkgopotse was buried in Botswana because the South African apartheid regime would not allow his body to be brought to

his home in Dinokana village. With the support of the Azanian People's Organisation (AZAPO), Onkgopotse's family requested assistance from the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) in bringing his remains back to South Africa for reburial. On 20 March 1998, AZAPO president, Mosibudi Mangena, Onkgopotse's mother Mrs Moleseng 'MmaAbram' Tiro, and family members received Onkgopotse's remains at the border post between South Africa and Botswana. He was finally laid to rest at Dinokana village on 22 March 1998.

Gordon Winter, a journalist working for the South African intelligence forces during the apartheid years, revealed in his book '*Inside BOSS: South Africa's secret police*' that Onkgopotse was killed by the Z-Squad, a covert unit of the Bureau of State Security (BOSS). The TRC failed to investigate his death.

Mr Moeketsi Israel Lesia stated: "So, I had to go around and look for information in terms of affiliation. So, initially, one was reserved around Black Conscious Movement (BCM) because in 1973 when I was at Petersburg one became aware of BCM and SASO (South African Student Organisation) through the influence of the University that was called Turfloop. So, one used to get material from SASO and BCM and one studied this material but also issues that affected one. The one that was a bit sensitive was the death of Tiro who was the BCM leader at Turfloop, Onkgopotse Tiro. Who was assassinated in Botswana, he left the country and was then assassinated through a letter bomb. So, one became sensitive around the issues but also the reactions that was prevailing in the country".

A remarkable man, Onkgopotse Abram Ramothibi Tiro, who fought for the liberation of South Africans, sacrificed his life in the course of conscientising students about freedom. Heroes like him will never be forgotten. You are honored Mr Onkgopotse Abram Tiro for your contribution to the freedom struggle of South Africa.

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EDUCATION NEWS

Exciting Museum lessons

School learners thoroughly enjoy our **temporary classroom exhibitions** with “**real**” **objects** that they can see and touch and with **hands-on activities** which they can take part in during our curriculum-based lessons at the Museum

International Museum Day 2023

The Education Department celebrated International Museum Day with an **exciting outdoor exhibition** in front of the Museum. Through these interesting items on display we gave the public a glimpse of what to expect inside the Museum.

We handed out Museum stickers to passing pedestrians, visiting school groups and all interested parties.

Mobile Museum visits

Museum on the move!

The Education Department's Mobile Museum brings part of the Museum to your area, be it a school or various organizations such as Old Age Homes and libraries, on request. It is a customized vehicle loaded with stuffed animals and real objects from the various Museum departments and exhibitions.

EDUCATION NEWS

Participation in Career Expo

The Education Department took part in the **2023 Provincial Tourism Career Expo at CUT**. School learners from around the Free State were invited and we had the opportunity to introduce them to the different departments of the National Museum and tell them about the different career opportunities at the Museum. They had the chance to see and touched some interesting objects and received some informative pamphlets on Museum careers.

Participation in Special events in 2023

Celebrated Africa month 2023

School learners could participate in some interactive activities, such as to greet in our 12 official languages, traditional dances, drum playing, etc. We reached a total number of **2707 learners and educators**.

Home School Expo 2023

The Education Department took part in the **Annual Home School Expo at the Free State Residential Care Centre**. Home-schooling communities from across the Free State attended and we were able to introduce them to the great variety of educational activities we have available at the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

National Museum presented National Science Week 2023

The Education Department hosted NSW from 31 July to 4 August 2023. The theme for the week was **“Our polluted Earth”**. We presented a well-informed PowerPoint presentation which highlight what we do wrong to harm our Earth and emphasised what all of us can contribute by making small changes every day to help to save our planet.

A total number of **6 362** learners and educators participated in our National Science Week.

Teacher Training Workshops

These workshops are aimed to give teachers the **knowledge and skills** to make affordable visual aids for their classrooms and to create activities that can be save, educational and affordable.

HISTORY NEWS

A New Publication on Bloemfontein's Black History

Dr Derek du Bruyn is a museum historian with a passion for oral history. He has studied the gardening history and culture of the residents of Bloemfontein's Batho township for his PhD. He launched the Museum's first oral history research project which focussed on the cultural, social and political history of Batho as well as an oral history research project on the military and stalwart veterans of the liberation struggle.

Image: Book cover of *Mangaung's Batho Township: A treasure trove of black history* – a book authored by Dr Derek du Bruyn. The layout and design of this publication was done by Carien van Eck. Copies are for sale in the National Museum shop at R25,00 each.

Derek du Bruyn published a book on the history of Mangaung's historical Batho township. Based on more than a decade's historical research, this glossy publication aims to introduce the public to the rich and fascinating history of Bloemfontein's oldest existing township (est. 1918). The book explores various aspects of Batho's multi-layered social and cultural history, including the reasons for Batho's founding as a so-called "model location"; the story behind the township's name; some of Batho's influential personalities such as Thomas Mapikela; the history of Batho's English-style architecture; and the residents' fascinating gardening culture, to name but a few topics.

Celebrating Youth Month 2023: Learning about family and family trees!

On June 16, South Africans celebrate Youth Day in remembrance of the Soweto Uprisings of 1976 and in appreciation of the sacrifices that were made by Soweto's learners for our freedom. To celebrate Youth Month 2023 the History Department organised an event at the First Raadsaal Museum for Grade Six learners and teachers from Lesedi

Primary School in Bochabela. The theme of the event was "Me and my family tree". The learners were shown what fun it is to compile a basic family tree. Each learner had to complete and decorate his or her own family tree template. First, second, and third prizes were awarded to the best family trees.

Image: Elmar du Plessis (Collections Management) showed the learners how to handle, care for, and store old family photos and documents.

Image: Khotso Pudumo (History) explained how learners can use oral history to obtain information about their families, especially the names of great-grandparents and other members of the extended family. The learners were encouraged to value their families and to learn more about the lives of their parents, grandparents, and great-grandparents.

Image: Pulane Mashiyi, curator of First Raadsaal Museum and Wagon Museum, took the learners on a tour of both museums. She told them about the early history of Bloemfontein and the Free State.

Image: The event was concluded by lively song and dance items performed by the learners of Lesedi primary school.

HISTORY NEWS

Oral History Association of South Africa (OHASA) Conference

Khotso Pudumo presented a research paper at OHASA's 20th Annual National Oral History Conference that was held at the conference facilities of the Maropeng Cradle of Humankind Visitor Centre in Mogale City, Gauteng Province, from 9–13 October 2023. The paper was titled: "The Impact of Controlled and Uncontrolled Trauma upon Mangaung Political Activists by State Agents: An Oral History Review" under the conference theme of "Liberation, Transformation, Commissions and Community Narrative". Using oral history interviews that were conducted with political activists from Mangaung, Khotso's paper explored the impact of trauma inflicted on them by state agents.

Image: Khotso Pudumo at the OHASA Conference.

Celebrating Heritage Day: Basotho Litema Heritage Celebrated

The History Department co-hosted a special event at Oliewenhuis Art Museum on 15 September 2023. More than 100 learners from Martie du Plessis Special School and Olympia Primary School in Bloemfontein attended the event. This year's event focused on the colourful *litema* wall decoration of the Basotho of the eastern Free State and Lesotho. According to the artist and expert on Basotho culture, Lenosa Mahapang, *litema* is a centuries old style of wall decoration that is still practiced by some Basotho women. *Litema* is the adorning of the plastered walls of traditional dwellings with organic and curvilinear patterns using paint. *Litema* celebrates special

events such as the birth of a child but more typically it marks Christian holy days such as Christmas and Good Friday. Lenosa explained that Basotho women also consider *litema* as a means of "nurturing" their homes.

Inspired by *litema*, the learners worked in groups to turn sections of the art museum's exterior walls into their own versions of the art form. By using oversized stencils of *litema* designs and chalk crayons, the learners transformed white walls into colourful friezes of wall paintings. They were assisted by students of the Department of Architecture at the University of the Free State (UFS) and staff of the National Museum and Oliewenhuis Art Museum. Prizes were awarded to the groups who made the best *litema*. The judges were Lenosa, Mary Mofama, a natural builder and Dr Anita Venter, a lecturer at the UFS and an expert in natural building techniques. Group 14's rendition of *litema* was named the overall winner. In addition to creating *litema*, some of the learners performed song and dance items, much to the enjoyment of the other learners and guests.

Image: The winning team with the judges and an assistant. Mary Mofama stands in the back row between two learners. In front are Dr Anita Venter and Lenosa Mahapang.

Image: The Heritage Day event was concluded with a performance of the traditional song *Seanamarena* by members of the National Museum's choir. From left to right are Tsholo Dintlhwane, Joyce Malaku, Sekhomatso Gubuza, Simon Zenani, Sebongile Mabasao, Nthaopa Ntheri and Dieketseng Meko.

TERRESTRIAL INVERTEBRATES NEWS

Discovery of a flightless fly from Lesotho

Burgert Muller and Dr John Midgley on fieldwork in Lesotho.
Insert: female specimen of the Snipe fly, *Atherimorpha latipennis*

Burgert Muller and Dr John Midgley (from KwaZulu-Natal Museum) described the first occurrence of reduced wings (brachyptery) in the Snipe flies (Rhagionidae). The unique tiny-winged female specimens of *Atherimorpha latipennis* were collected during a collaborative fieldtrip to Lesotho, as part of the DIPoDIP project, which aims to study the diversity of South African pollinating flies. The research paper was published in the international journal, *Zookeys*, and was also covered in international and local newspapers.

Dr Daniel delivered a keynote address at the 40th conference of the Zoological Society of Southern Africa.

The 40th conference of the Zoological Society of Southern Africa was held at Champagne Sports Resort, Central Drakensberg, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, from 25 – 29 September 2023.

The theme of this conference was "Extreme Zoology", including topics that reflect the unusual times that we are in, such as global change, a zoonotic pandemic, the biodiversity crash, and the extraordinary technologies that are becoming accessible to scientists. Dr Gimo Daniel, Principal Museum Scientist and Y1-NRF-rated scientist, was invited to deliver a keynote presentation. Dr Daniel's talk was entitled "Systematics of dung beetles: Why it matters in the era of biodiversity extinction?"

What does it mean to be a keynote speaker? Being selected to deliver a keynote presentation at a conference is indeed an honour. Keynote speakers are typically recognized experts or influential figures in their respective fields, and they are invited to share their insights, knowledge, and perspectives with the conference audience. "Accepting an invitation to give a keynote presentation is not just an

Dr Gimo Daniel at the 40th conference of the Zoological Society of Southern Africa.

acknowledgement of your expertise but also a recognition of your contributions to the field. It's an opportunity to showcase your work, share valuable insights, contribute to the overall success of the conference, and most importantly, be a great role model for fellow young African zoologists," says Dr Daniel.

TERRESTRIAL INVERTEBRATES NEWS

2023 Field Museum Visiting Scholars Award

Dr Gimo Daniel hard at work at the Field Museum, Chicago, USA

Dr Gimo Daniel was awarded 2023 Field Museum Visiting Scholars Award to conduct research at the Field Museum, Chicago, USA under collaboration of Dr Bruno de Medeiros. His main project is aimed to understand the effects of climate and topography on spatial patterns of genetic structure in southern African dung beetles. He is also conducting collection based research, studying dung beetle species housed at the Field Museum.

Scholarship to attend training in Tanzania.

Jarmaine Magoai obtained a scholarship to attend training on the taxonomy of Afrotropical pollinating Diptera at the Sokoine Pest Management Center of the Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania from 16 – 27 October 2023. The course included 12 participants from Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe. The schedule included lectures, trapping methodologies, fieldwork, pinning, labelling and identification using the family key.

Jarmaine Magoai attending training in Tanzania (fourth from the left)

Fieldwork at Meiringskloof

Dr Lizel Hugo-Coetzee, Jan Andries Neethling and Burgert Muller visited the Meiringskloof Nature Park in the Free State for specimen collecting. Dr Lizel's focus was on soil mites occurring close to water, Jan Andries focused on pseudoscorpions and Burgert on fly larvae in the streams. Many specimens were collected making it a very successful fieldtrip.

Dr Lizel Hugo-Coetzee, Jan Andries Neethling and Burgert Muller sampling in Meiringskloof Nature Park

ANIMAL AND PLANT SYSTEMATICS NEWS

Staff member celebrates 40 years at the Museum

Dr Michael Bates started working at the National Museum, as a research assistant in the Department of Herpetology, at the beginning of January 1983. He recently completed 40 years of service to the institution, having served under four different directors. In 1993, while at the Museum, he completed a master's degree in Environmental Biology through University of Natal (Durban), and in 1998 was promoted to the position of Senior Museum Scientist. In 2007 he completed a doctoral degree in Zoology through Stellenbosch University, and was appointed head of department in 2013. In 2015 he was promoted to Specialist Scientist, and in 2021 became the first head of the newly-created Department of Animal and Plant Systematics, which comprises herpetology and botany divisions.

Michael has authored over 350 herpetological publications, including full length research papers, research notes, popular articles, obituaries, tributes, bibliographies, editorials and book reviews. He has attended 35 national and international conferences where he has had the opportunity to present the results of his research. Over the years he has conducted several field excursions in search of reptiles and amphibians, including extensive searches for flat geckos, crag lizards and girdled lizards throughout South Africa. His research focuses on the taxonomy of various African lizards and snakes, including descriptions of new species. He has thus far named two new genera and six new species of reptiles. One of his major achievements thus far is the role he played as senior editor of, and a major contributor to, the book *Atlas and Red List of the Reptiles of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland*, published in 2014.

Regarding his involvement in the herpetological community, Michael served on the committee of the Herpetological Association of Africa for an uninterrupted period of over 27 years (1990–2017), including terms as Chairman and Newsletter Editor. He has also refereed numerous manuscripts for about 20 different scientific journals and other publications. Michael was editor-in-chief of the Museum's scientific research journal (called *Indago* since 2016) for 10 years; and also served for several years on the editorial committee of the Museum's popular magazine, *Culna*.

In 2012 he was awarded an African Biodiversity Information Centre – Study Visit Scholarship to the Royal Museum of Central Africa in Tervuren, Belgium, where he spent three weeks examining their large collection of egg-eating snakes. He has also spent time examining collections of various reptiles at museums in San Francisco, New York, Villanova, London, Paris, Berlin, Vienna, Lisbon, Porto, Nairobi, Bulawayo, Pretoria, Cape Town, Port Elizabeth, Durban, Pietermaritzburg and Kimberley.

In 2019 he was appointed as a Research Fellow in the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences at the University of the Free State. To date he has co-supervised three honours students at the university. He has also examined two masters and two doctoral dissertations for four different universities. He currently serves as a member of the International Scientific Committee for the 10th World Congress of Herpetology in Kuching, Malaysia (2024), and is also a member of the Skink Specialist Group of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature's (IUCN) Species Survival Commission.

Dr Michael Bates holding a common girdled lizard collected on a recent field trip in KwaZulu-Natal. (Photo: Cora Stobie)

Frog experts visit the Herpetology Division

Prof. Les Minter, Extra-ordinary Professor at North West University (Potchefstroom), and Dr Ed Netherlands of University of the Free State (Bloemfontein) visited the Department to examine and photograph the holotype of a rain frog, *Breviceps striatus*, from near Greytown in KwaZulu-Natal, collected and described in 1940 by Dr A.C. Hoffman, a former zoologist and director of the National Museum. This holotype, the specimen on which the description of *Breviceps striatus* was based, is still in good condition after over 80 years in ethanol (preservative). Prof. Minter and Dr Netherlands also examined and photographed another rain frog collected at the same locality. The two researchers are studying the taxonomic status of rain frogs in KwaZulu-Natal and other parts of South Africa.

Prof. Les Minter (left) and Dr Ed Netherlands (seated) examining and photographing museum specimens of rain frogs in the Department of Animal and Plant Systematics. Head of the department, Dr Michael Bates, is in the middle. (Photo: Marelie van Rensburg)

ANIMAL AND PLANT SYSTEMATICS NEWS

Exploring plant biodiversity: An expedition to Witsieshoek Mountain Valley

In November 2023, Dr Oladayo Idris (Botany) together with Dr Solomon Owolabi, a geologist from the Department of Disaster Management Training and GIS Centre (University of the Free State, Bloemfontein), and Mr Zingisile Mbo (intern at Ornithology and Botany), conducted the first of three plant surveys in the Witsieshoek Mountain Valley of the Batlokoa Community in Qwaqwa, eastern Free State. The primary focus of the project is to investigate the biogeographical boundaries of the vegetation within its unique ecosystem based on species turnover patterns, distribution, and richness indices. Concurrently, the expedition sought to enrich the Museum's herbarium by expanding its collection of specimens. Hundreds of plant samples were collected. During the expedition, a range of elevations (1905–2225 m a.s.l.) along the mountain valley was investigated via 14 pre-identified sampling points.

Dr Oladayo Idris (right) and Dr Solomon Owolabi (left), collecting field data in Witsieshoek Mountain Valley. (Photo: Zingisile Mbo)

Milestone achieved: 1000 herbarium specimens digitised

The Botany Division has achieved a major milestone by successfully digitising (photographically recording) 1 000 herbarium specimens, marking major progress in a transformative journey to make the Museum's botanical collection accessible to all. The achievement is a testament to our commitment to advancing research, botanical exploration, and education in the field of botany through a digital window.

New species of green-eyed girdled lizard from Angola

Dr Michael Bates, together with a team of collaborators, recently published, in the journal *Vertebrate Zoology*, the description of a new species of lizard, the green-eyed Mombolo Girdled Lizard (*Cordylus momboloensis*), from the west-central highlands of Angola. Specimens of a similar lizard, the Angolan Girdled Lizard (*Cordylus angolensis*), were also described in detail. The latter species was known from only a single specimen collected in Caconda, Angola about 130 years ago. This study included genetic analyses, examination of external morphology (scale counts, size, colour pattern) and CT-scanning of the skeleton.

Holotype of the Mombolo Girdled Lizard (*Cordylus momboloensis*) from Sandula (Mombolo), Angola. (Photo: William Branch)

South African Association of Botany conference

Dr Oladayo Idris, collection manager of the herbarium in the Botany Division, attended the 49th scientific meeting of the South African Association of Botany held at the University of Zululand in Richards Bay, KwaZulu-Natal, in January 2024. Dr Idris presented a paper titled "Effect of plant biopesticide-polluted soils on soil organisms (*Eisenia andrei*) and soil enzymatic activity, with biochar as an ameliorant", co-authored by Mr H.H. Smith (North-West University), Dr O.H.J. Rhode (Agriculture Research Council – Grain Crops), and Prof. M.S. Maboeta (North-West University).

Delegates at the 49th SAAB conference at Richards Bay. From left: Ms Anneri du Toit, Dr Ademola Adetunji, Ms Bianca Boshoff, Prof. Stefan Sierbiert, Mr Charl Clarke, Mr Tean Joubert, and Dr Oladayo Idris. Back: Prof. Jacques Berner. (Photo: courtesy of Jacques Berner)

ANIMAL AND PLANT SYSTEMATICS NEWS

Enigmatic Namibian egg-eating snake found to be a valid species

Dr Michael Bates recently published an article in *Bonn Zoological Bulletin* showing that two species of egg-eating snakes occur in Namibia. Most researchers had, since 1983, considered the subspecies *Dasypeltis scabra loveridgei* nothing more than a possible colour variant of the well-known Common Egg-eater (*Dasypeltis scabra*). A detailed morphological analysis of 153 preserved museum specimens from Namibia indicated that two distinct morphotypes, 'scabra' and 'loveridgei', occurred in the country. The Namibian Egg-eater (*D. loveridgei*) has hourglass-shaped markings along its back, together with other features such as only six (not 7) upper labial scales, the 2nd and 3rd (not 3rd and 4th) in contact with the orbital, and longer internasal scales. The Common Egg-eater occurs mainly in central and north-eastern Namibia, while the Namibian Egg-eater is widespread in the country, except for the north-east. The two species are even found together in a few areas.

The Namibian Egg-eater (*Dasypeltis loveridgei*), now shown to be a different species from the similar-looking Common Egg-eater (*D. scabra*). (Photo: Wulf Haacke)

Article about the toxicity of Black Jacks

Dr Oladayo Idris and coauthors recently published a paper in the journal *Chemistry Africa* in which 137 compounds were identified in the plant *Bidens pilosa* L., commonly known as Black Jack. Four of these compounds had not previously been reported in this species. This study involved the use of precision analytical equipment. *Bidens pilosa* is an annual weed which, because of its resilience to unfavourable environmental conditions, spreads extensively in tropical and subtropical areas, including South Africa. It is used in a range of applications, including food and traditional medicine, plant biopesticide, weed control, and the removal of heavy metal contaminants from soils. Because of the plant's extensive range of traditional uses, isolated compounds were utilised in the study to analyse its health risks (toxicity) and health benefits. The study concluded that Black Jack

extracts may be toxic at high concentrations at the cellular level, but no potentially poisonous compound was identified.

The Black Jack plant (*Bidens pilosa*). (with permission of Kuo et al., 2021, *Food Frontiers* 2[1]: 32–45)

Herpetologist visits University of Pretoria for genetics research

In August 2023, Dr Cora Stobie travelled to the University of Pretoria's laboratory of the Molecular Ecology and Evolution Programme (MEEP), Department of Biochemistry, Genetics and Microbiology, for two weeks. The purpose of this trip was to sequence the genes of two lineages of the Common Girdled Lizard (*Cordylus vittifer*) using new primers that were designed to overcome a mutation. This research is part of an ongoing project by Dr Stobie and collaborators Dr Bates and Prof. Paulette Bloomer (University of Pretoria) investigating speciation in populations of this species. Sequences were produced for 23 lizards of the two lineages. This was critical for assessing whether the various genetic lineages are different species or merely different populations of the same species.

Dr Cora Stobie at the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, University of Pretoria. (Photo: Arrie Klopper)

ANIMAL AND PLANT SYSTEMATICS NEWS

Herpetologists report on unusual puff adder

Dr Michael Bates and Dr Cora Stobie, together with Mr Jade Hastings of the University of the Free State, recently published a research note documenting an unusual colour variant of the well-known and highly venomous puff adder (*Bitis arietans*). A young female of this species was found on a property in Langenhoven Park, Bloemfontein, near the edge of an expanse of natural grassland. It was captured by Mr Hastings, a snake rescuer. The snake's colour pattern was so unusual that it was decided to document it and submit a research note to *African Journal of Ecology* for publication. Although a few unusual colour patterns have on occasion been reported in puff adders, e.g. plain brown with a dark stripe down the middle of the back, the speckled pattern of the Bloemfontein snake was unique.

The unusually marked Puff Adder (*Bitis arietans*) from Bloemfontein.
(Photo: Johan Marais)

Unveiling the chemical compounds in Khaki Weed

Dr Oladayo Idris and collaborators recently published an article titled "Comparative phytochemistry using UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS phenolic compounds profile of the water and aqueous ethanol extracts of *Tagetes minuta* and their cytotoxicity", which investigated the chemical composition, or secondary metabolites, of *Tagetes minuta*, also known as Khaki Bush or African Marigold. A number of novel compounds were identified in the plant. African Marigold has been a subject of interest for researchers and herbal enthusiasts for its multi-faceted uses as a pest control agent, cosmetic, medicinal herb, natural herbicide, and ingredient in cosmaceutical products.

Khaki Weed or African Marigold (*Tagetes minuta*).
(Photo: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=71907005>)

Venomous snake handling bootcamp

The *African Snakebite Institute* recently hosted a few venomous snake handling workshops, presented by Mr Johan Marais and facilitators, at the Hellenic Community Centre in Bloemfontein. Dr Cora Stobie attended the Venomous Snake Handling Bootcamp for a Level 2 accreditation. Participants practiced how to safely handle puff adders, snouted cobras, Cape cobras and rinkhals, and received personalised critique from the trainers to improve their skills.

On the left is Mr Johan Marais, presenter of the Venomous Snake Handling Bootcamp, and on the extreme right is Dr Cora Stobie.

Herpetologist attends conference in England

Dr Michael Bates attended the 22nd European Congress of Herpetology held at the University of Wolverhampton in England in September 2023, where he presented a paper titled "Three new species of flat geckos (*Afroedura*) from the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa" (coauthors: Nicolau, Conradie, Edwards, Makhubo & Branch).

Selected delegates to the 22nd European Congress of Herpetology at the University of Wolverhampton in England in September. Dr Michael Bates is in the center. (Photo: courtesy of Arthur Tiutenko)

15th Herpetological Association of Africa conference

In January 2023, Dr Bates and Dr Stobie attended the 15th Herpetological Association of Africa conference held in Hoedspruit. Dr Bates delivered an oral presentation titled "A new species of *Cordylus* from the Angolan highlands, and

ANIMAL AND PLANT SYSTEMATICS NEWS

the rediscovery of *Cordylus angolensis* (co-authored by: Mr Javier Lobón-Rovira, Dr Edward Stanley, the late Prof. William Branch & Mr Pedro Vaz Pinto). Dr Stobie's presentation was titled "A molecular analysis of the Common Girdled Lizard (*Cordylus vittifer*)" (co-authored by: Prof. Paulette Bloomer and Dr Bates).

From left: Prof. Aaron Bauer (Villanova University, USA), Dr Michael Bates, Dr Cora Stobie and Mr Marius Burger (Cape Town) at Hoedspruit Reptile Centre after the 15th Herpetological Association of Africa conference.

Facebook group: "Free State Reptiles and Amphibians"

Dr Cora Stobie and Dr Michael Bates continue to manage a Facebook group called Free State Reptiles and Amphibians (including adjacent areas and Lesotho) which collects photographic and videographic records posted on various media platforms. Over 2 896 records have been acquired and catalogued so far, with 512 being added in 2023. Over the last year 179 people have posted or commented in the group, and 31 666 people have viewed it. A total of 684 posts, 342 comments and 3 054 reactions were made in this period. Fifty-eight species were reported in 2023, with five being new to the group. This brings the group's total to 101 species, including six exotic (pet) species and five species translocated from elsewhere in South Africa. We have now reached approximately 73% of all expected reptile and amphibian species in the Free State, with 90% of expected snakes represented. The main aim of this outreach project is to gather new records for the various species found in the region and then update distribution maps. In addition, members of the public can post images to the group for identification, and aspects of the conservation of reptiles and amphibians are also discussed. A webinar was presented by Dr Stobie and Dr Bates in August to update the public on progress with the group.

A harmless Common Egg-eater (in threat display) found at Oliewenhuis Art Museum, Bloemfontein. (Photo: Michael Bates)

Educational outreach program

As part of the Museum's educational outreach program, Ms Agnes Phindane visited a few Free State schools to present lessons on herpetology to Grade 10 science learners. The presentations also focused on career opportunities in the natural sciences, especially at the National Museum. On some of these trips she was accompanied by Dr Oladayo Idris who presented information about plants, and Mr Zingisile Mbo who spoke about birds.

Ms Agnes Phindane at Grassland Secondary School, Bloemfontein, presenting a lesson "Careers in the Natural Sciences" for Gr. 10 learners. (Photo: Zingisile Mbo)

Other news

Dr Michael Bates continues to serve as a member of the Skink Specialist Group (SSG), part of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature's (IUCN) Species Survival Commission. He was also appointed as a member of the International Scientific Committee for the 10th World Congress of Herpetology. Dr Cora Stobie was elected to the committee of the Herpetological Association of Africa, as Business Administrator. Both Dr Bates and Dr Stobie presented lectures about reptile taxonomy to honours students at the University of the Free State in Bloemfontein during 2023.

ORNITHOLOGY NEWS

New sound recording equipment for the Ornithology Department

The Ornithology Department recently purchased new sound equipment to obtain bird vocalizations in the field for their avian digitized collection. Currently, there are approximately 1400 plus avian vocalization records of which African Rock Pipit, Rufous-naped, and Melodious Lark represent the majority of digital sound files on the avian database.

Image: Dawie de Swardt (HOD: Ornithology Department) is showing the Zoom H4n Pro recorder with the Sennheiser MKE 600 shotgun microphone.

Unusual sighting of Swee Waxbills at Oliewenhuis Art Museum

Image: Swee Waxbill male foraging for grass seeds at the grass clump (Photo – Fanie Riekert)

During the annual **Birdlife South Africa “Bird Week” bird ringing demonstration** at Oliewenhuis Art Museum, the team heard a "swie swie" sound of birds and to their surprise they found at least six Swee Waxbills foraging for grass seeds in the grass clumps, which should not occur in the central parts of the Free State! BirdLife Free State member, Fanie Riekert, managed to obtain a few pictures of the birds as proof of their occurrence in this area. Both male and female individuals were observed. The sighting was reported on the Birdlife Free State birding group and later several observers managed to visit Oliewenhuis to “tick” them off on their bird life lists.

New intern Museum Scientist, Zingisile Mbo, joined the ornithology department recently. Both Dawie and Lots Morapedi trained Zingisile. Lots recently celebrated his 40th year as a preparator in the Ornithology Department. During his time at the National Museum, he prepared more than 4000 skin and 2000 skeletal specimens in our collections.

Image: Lots Morapedi, Ornithology preparator with Zingisile Mbo, Intern Museum Scientist.

Image: Ornithology Intern, Zingisile Mbo, participated in a bird collecting and bird ringing field work trip at Engedi retreat, Ladybrand from 14 – 18 August 2023.

ORNITHOLOGY NEWS

6th Biennial Learn About Birds (LAB) Conference

Dawie attended the 6th Biennial Learn About Birds (LAB) Conference hosted by Birdlife South Africa in the Western Cape from 25 – 26 May 2023. He attended virtually and presented a pre-recorded “5-minute speed talk” on his new research project about Rufous-eared Warblers. The aim of new project is to collect biometric data from ringed birds and to obtain blood and DNA for genetic analysis by his research collaborator.

Image: The study species (Rufous-eared Warbler) in the hand during the field trip conducted at Florisbad Quarternary Research station, Soutpan during September 2023.

Image: Rufous-eared Warbler habitat at Holhoek farm, Paul Roux in the eastern Free State where the sub-species “ocularis” occur. These birds mainly occurs on overgrazed agriculture fields and karroid veld.

Image: Dawie de Swardt was recognised for 3000 Full Protocol submissions to the Southern African Bird Atlas Project on 10 December 2023.

Image: Dawie de Swardt (HOD Ornithology Department) busy photographing a bird at the Paul Roux study site (photo – Martin Potgieter)

Image: Rufous-eared Warbler in the hand at the Paul Roux study site during November 2023.

MAMMALOLOGY NEWS

Book launch – *Simbamangu, through the eyes of the caracal*

Image: Author, Dr Nico Avenant, was introduced by Sharon Snell (National Museum CEO) at the launch of the book *Simbamangu, through the eyes of caracal*.

On 16 November 2023, Oliewenhuis Art Museum hosted the book launch of Dr Nico Avenant's new photo story book. Nico is Head of the Mammalogy Department in the National Museum. He teamed up with Homo ambiens Wildlife Conservation Photography (www.homoambiens.com) to publish this book on one of Southern Africa's most striking and secretive cat species, the caracal. The work informs on the intricate interlinkages and complexities in nature, and the multifaceted and controversial ways in which caracal are managed in Southern Africa. It also indicates the important role that wildlife photography can play in dealing with very sensitive conservation issues. Apart from very special photos of this predator, and the habitat in which it lives, the text reflects more than 20 years of Nico's research in diverse habitats and geographic areas. The photos were taken by Roberto Isotti and Alberto Cambone and the text written by Nico Avenant and Micòl Ricci.

Image: At the launch of the book *Simbamangu, through the eyes of caracal*. Dr. Nico Avenant and three of his PhD students that worked on the caracal and black-backed jackal depredation issue.

Mammalogy exhibits at Amanzi Game Festival and Bainsvlei library.

Images: Myra Gohodzi and Dr Will Archer from the Archaeology Department interact with visitors at the Amanzi Game Festival

More than 1,600 people recently had the opportunity to experience two aspects of the Free State's rich natural and cultural heritage: small carnivores and Stone Age archaeological material. Museum departments of **Mammalogy**, **Archaeology** and **Anthropology** exhibited beautiful sight and touch displays at the most recent **Amanzi Game Festival** in the central Free State. Dr. Will Archer's demonstration of stone-knapping (stone artefact making) also grabbed attention and was a welcome bonus for visitors.

MAMMALOLOGY NEWS

Image: A temporary display and interactive touch experience, *Small carnivores of the Free State*, during the Amanzi Game Festival weekend.

Image: The Mammalogy and Design Departments exhibited a collection of 28 taxidermy specimens and interesting facts at the Bainsvlei Library during 2023.

Mammalogists on the Move

Images: Mammalogist Dr. Nico Avenant recently contributed at the 13th International Mammalogical Congress in Anchorage, Alaska. The conference ran from 14 to 20 July 2023 and was attended by over 700 delegates, from more than 53 countries. The title of Nico's presentation was *Small mammals as an indicator of habitat change in the Kalahari, South Africa*, one of the longer-term collaboration projects that the Mammalogy Department is currently involved with.

Dr. Aluwani Nengovhela recently attended the Volkswagen Foundation Summer School III (Ecological Governance in Socio-ecological Systems of Sub-Saharan Africa) at the Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda.

Image: After attending the International Mammalogical Congress in Anchorage, Dr Avenant joined collaborators at the US National Wildlife Research Centre (NWRC) in Fort Collins, Colorado, for trials on the effectiveness of a local (produced in the Karoo) deterrent collar on damage-causing coyotes. He is pictured with personnel from the National Black-footed Ferret Conservation Centre. The Black-footed ferret is one of the most threatened mammals in America.

MAMMALOLOGY NEWS

Images: Drs. Aluwani Nengovhela and Nico Avenant recently contributed at the 14th African Small Mammal Symposium in Swakopmund, Namibia. The research in central and northern Namibia was linked to the Symposium, where they contributed to four presentations.

Image: A general Collection trip to the western Free State (Philippolis area) was undertaken to search for species that have never been found in the Free State Province before. Photo is of Dr. Aluwani Nengovhela.

Images: During the recent small mammal sampling trip to Namibia the team from the National Museum and the universities of Namibia and Montpellier worked in a large variety of habitats, including at the edge of the Namib Desert, on the Skeleton coast, in Kaoko- and Owamboland, along the Kunene and in north and central Namibia. This was done through a collaboration between Dr. Nico Avenant, Dr. Seth Eiseb of the University of Namibia, and Dr. Guila Ganem of the University of Montpellier, France.

Nico currently supervises a MSc student from the University of the Free State and a PhD student from UNISA, while Aluwani co-supervises a PhD student from the University of the Free State. Nico has also recently acted as an examiner for a MSc and a PhD thesis, and Aluwani for an Honours mini dissertation. The Mammalogy Department has been involved with a field school for University of Pretoria honours students during the year. Public lectures completed by the team included presentations on damage-causing carnivores (for NSPCA officials), the value of monitoring small mammal communities for conservation management (for guides at the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve), the role and status of black-backed jackal and caracal in agro-ecosystems (at the University of the Third Age), and on caracal, the intricate interlinkages and complexities in nature, and the controversial ways in which they are managed in Southern Africa (during the launch of the book *Simbamangu, through the eyes of caracal*).

ARCHAEOLOGY / ANTHROPOLOGY NEWS

The Archaeology and Anthropology Department at the National Museum spearheaded an array of initiatives geared toward advancing the department's research, outreach, and knowledge dissemination goals throughout the year.

Image: National Museum archaeologists collaborating with the Departments of Mammology and Paleontology, in presenting materials on the special day for the society for the blind.

NRF awards National Museum archaeologist a prestigious B3 NRF rating

Image: Dr Will Archer is Head of the Department of Anthropology and Archaeology at the National Museum.

The CEO of the National Museum, Sharon Snell has congratulated Dr Will Archer for achieving a B3 NRF rating.

This prestigious accolade was awarded to him by the National Research Foundation (NRF).

The NRF conducted a rigorous evaluation by peers in order to assess and rate the research capacity of Dr Will Archer. Based on the quality and the impact of his research outputs and the comments of the reviewers he was placed in the B category at level B3. The B category researchers are those who enjoy considerable international recognition by their peers for the high quality and impact of their recent research outputs. Placement on the B 3 subcategory means that most of the reviewers were convinced that Dr Archer enjoys considerable international recognition for the high quality and impact of his/her recent research outputs.

Dr Archer has published relatively widely in some of the leading journals in the fields of archaeology and human evolution. He obtained Bachelors and Honours Degrees from the University of Cape Town, in addition to Masters degrees in both Environmental Law and Archaeology from the same institution. He pursued a PhD in archaeological science, awarded by Leiden University (Holland) in 2016, and then undertook post-doctoral research at the Max Planck Institute in Leipzig, Germany. In 2020, he was appointed as Head of the Department of Anthropology and Archaeology at the National Museum. His interests are in quantitative approaches to generating high-quality datasets through the study of stone artefacts, and through excavations of new promising archaeological sites with the best recovery methods.

Dr Archer has conducted fieldwork in six sub-Saharan African countries, working in archaeological contexts ranging in age from the Plio-Pleistocene through to the Holocene. He directs two projects in South Africa, and has held leadership roles in projects in Mozambique, Lesotho, Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania. Some highlights of this field work include (1) the earliest evidence for Homo sapiens occupation of a tropical rainforest at Panga ya Saidi, Kenya, (2) the earliest hominin flaked stone industry at Bakal-Dura 1, Ethiopia and (3) the earliest evidence for hominin aquatic resource use in East Turkana, Kenya. His current research focuses on early human cultural evolution and social networking on the southern African west coast.

Research and Fieldwork

Dr Archer presented new research at the 12th Annual European Society of Human Evolution Meetings in Tübingen, Germany, known as the 'ESHE meetings,' held in September 2022. Will also presented to the South African Archaeological Society (ArchSoc) with a public lecture in June 2022. His talk, "Exploring pattern and pace in southern African human behavioral evolution – a view from the south Western Cape," can be viewed first-hand on YouTube.

ARCHAEOLOGY / ANTHROPOLOGY NEWS

Image: A fieldtrip to several west coast archaeological sites. Top row: discussions of the stratigraphy at Diepkloof Rockshelter, Bottom left: assessing the backfill and rock art at Elands Bay Cave, Bottom right: viewing archaeological exhibits at the new heritage centre in Elands Bay.

The department's published a Quaternary Geochronology paper delving into new excavations at Simons Cave on the Western Cape coast, directed by Will and a paper on a BMC Ecology study centering on the Paleo-Primate project in Gorongosa, Mozambique, wherein Dr. Archer plays a role.

Image: National Museum staff members participating in the Rose Cottage Cave fieldwork and site documentation.

Image: Top row and bottom left: Using a drone to create landscape 3D models of the archaeological site of Pancho's Kitchen, on the Western Cape coast. Bottom right: Experimenting with different methods of processing marine limpets, which are abundant food remnants in west coast archaeological sites, but occasionally can be toxic.

Image: National Museum Archaeology Department staff scanning various items in the Department of Archaeology collections.

FLORISBAD QUATERNARY RESEARCH DEPARTMENT NEWS

Research and Field Work

Dr Lloyd Rossouw (HOD: Florisbad) joined visiting researchers surveying for new archaeological and palaeontological sites, as part of a new five-year collaborative project that will focus on the palaeoecology and open-landscape adaptations of humans in interior of South Africa throughout the Middle and Late Pleistocene. The fieldwork was directed from the Florisbad research station and lasted from June to August 2023.

Image: Project members from left to right: Drs. Michael Toffolo (CENIEH), Mailys Richard (U. Bordeaux-Montaigne), Lloyd Rossouw (Florisbad Quaternary Research Department), Felipe Cuartero (CENIEH) and Prof. Britt Bousman (Texas State University).

Image: The collaborative project involved multiple fieldwork activities including, systematic surveying of selected areas followed by and archaeological excavations.

Dr Sharon Holt visited Necsa (South African Nuclear Energy Corporation) at Hartebeespoort twice during the year to have thirty tortoise specimens CT-scanned for her tortoise atlas project. This project aims to provide a skeletal guide to the identification of SA tortoises from archaeological sites.

Image: The scanning facility at NECSA (left). The images on the right serve as a basis for presenting the morphological features that can be used to identify species, e.g. the concavity in the male plastron is clearly visible, and can be used to sex the tortoises (in addition to other features).

Outreach and Education

The Florisbad Quaternary Research Department, in collaboration with the Mammalogy Department and lecturers from the universities of Pretoria (UP) and the Free State (UFS), hosted an eventful education and training event, when fifteen Honours-students from the Department of Geography, Geoinformatics and Meteorology from the UP, attended a two-day practical and theoretical experience at the Florisbad Research Station. Dr Lloyd Rossouw also gave his annual educational tour of the archaeological excavations at Florisbad to 3rd-year students from the UFS Department of Geography, joined as co-lecturer in the UFS Department of Plant Sciences Honours module, Methods in Palaeoecology and hosted a Shadow Day at Florisbad for learners wanting to learn more about archaeology and palaeontology. Dr Sharon Holt gave a presentation on her tortoise atlas project at the Royal Port Alfred Golf Club attended by 50 members of the public.

Image: Third-year students from the UFS Department of Geography attending an on-site lecture on Pleistocene mammal fossils (left) and Grade 11 learners taking part in activities at the Florisbad Research Station (right).

Visitors and Collections

Several national and international visitors made use of the research station's collections and facilities, including Drs. Arrie Klopper and Anri van Wyk from the UP Department of Biochemistry, Genetics & Microbiology, Michelle Schroeder from the Black-footed Cat Working Group, Dr Viola Schmid from the Austrian Archaeological Institute in Vienna, Austria, and Alex Gregory from the Department of Anthropology at New York University. The department focused on digitization of previously accessioned items in its collection. Around 2000 items were meticulously recorded via flatbed scanner and digital camera.

Image: PhD Student Alex Gregory from the Department of Anthropology at New York University visited the Florisbad Research station for two weeks in June.

Image: Digitization also include using a UV scanner to bring out faded accession numbers on fossil specimens.

DESIGN & WORKSHOP NEWS

The Beeshop Shop donates live beehive for Museum display

On 18 December 2023 the National Museum welcomed a healthy active beehive back in its displays. It is an observation hive that can be viewed from both sides with explanatory information panels surrounding the hive. An observation hive offers many things to look for: to find the queen; see how the cells are being built; find a bee 'dancing' to tell the rest in the hive where to find food and much more. The Bee Shop in Bloemfontein kindly donated the hive to the Museum. You can find them here www.thebeeshopbfn.co.za

Temporary Exhibition: Birds' Nests and Eggs

A new temporary exhibition about bird nests and eggs was installed at the National Museum by the Design and Workshop Department. Ornithology (the study of birds) has a sub-discipline called Oology which is the study or collecting of bird's nests and eggs. This discipline began during the mid-1900s and lasted until approximately the 1960s. During its inception, it was considered more as a hobby rather than a scientific discipline. Today most countries have strict collecting laws for conservation purposes.

Permanent Exhibition: Hidden creatures in the soil exhibition

'Hidden creatures in the soil' is a new permanent exhibition installed on the first floor at the National Museum. Visitors can delve deep into the intricate world of soil and all the fascinating creatures that call it home – from predators to decomposers to soil engineers. The exhibition shows how soil health affects our ecosystem and how we can boost soil diversity for a healthier planet.

DESIGN & WORKSHOP NEWS

Bloem Show Exhibition

To celebrate 140 years of the Bloem Show, the Design Department put up an exhibition which was on display at the National Museum Bloemfontein until April 2023

Image: Presidential Employment Stimulus Programme Interns, Fana Nyembe and Neo Nakedi are seen here hard at work cleaning the bones that were installed in the 'excavation of the ancient hyena lair' showcase for the Dreyer Hall Exhibition.

University of the Free State: General Career Fair

On 8 August 2023 the Museum attended the General Career fair of the University of the Free State. The engagement was beneficial as a networking opportunity with the students. The Museum team was led by the Christo Venter, HOD of Design. Oliewenhuis Art Museum and the Natural and Human Science departments were present to provide information about opportunities to the students.

Image: Monde Sithole (Designer) was invited by the Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology for a sponsored trip to the Russian Federation. He attend a linguistic, cultural and education programme as part of a Russia - South African collaboration which ran during October and November of 2023.

ARTBANK NEWS

G20 Art Project – Together We Art, The Bihar Museum (Patna) and The National Museum (New Delhi), India

Artist Thalente Khomo travelled with her work “Untitled” (2017), which is a part of the ArtbankSA Contemporary Visual Art Collection, for the G20 Initiative for the Ministry of Culture, Government of India. Khomo’s work was selected to be part of the contemporary art exhibition which took place between 7 August and 7 October 2023

Images: Thalente Khomo, Untitled, 2017, Photograph, 118.9 x 84.1 cm and the artist at the opening of the G20 Art Project – Together We Art Exhibition, India

Presidential Employment Stimulus Programme (PESP3)

The Department of Sport, Arts and Culture made PESP3 funding available to the ArtBankSA to implement the Art Creating – Public Art Programme. Under this programme, visual artists create public art.

Build the Future - Ndwedwe, KwaZulu Natal

Image: Julian Mentz. Artwork Title: Build the Future. Year created: 2023 Mural located: Ndwedwe, KwaZulu Natal.

Julian Mentz was approached by an NGO “Build the Future” that build schools in the rural villages throughout KZN to paint the latest built school located in Ndwedwe, KZN which hosts 40 Grade R students. This painting represents an important step in his development as an artist. The project was conceived as individual elements executed as single pieces of a larger composition.

Kgoro ya Tokoloho ~ Freedom’s Gate - Johannesburg, Gauteng

Image: Mpho Mosia. Artwork Title: Kgoro ya Tokoloho ~ Freedom’s Gate. Year created: 2023 Mural located: Johannesburg, Gauteng.

Mpho Zetina Mosia, an artist based in Johannesburg, South Africa, is a unique blend of South African and Ghanaian heritage. She gracefully infuses her Ghanaian roots with her South African upbringing, and her artistic talents span multiple mediums. Notably this mural is thoughtfully tailored for a pre-school setting in Bramley, Johannesburg.

Soulful Blues - MusiconSA, Bloemfontein, Free State

Image: Ditshwanelo Mosia. Artwork Title: Soulful Blues. Year created: 2023 Mural located: MusiconSA, Bloemfontein, Free State.

Ditshwanelo Mosia is a self-taught artist born and raised in Mount Fletcher a small town on the edges of the Eastern Cape province.

She completed architectural draughting studies at Qualitas Career Academy in the Free State and is currently working as a professional draughtsman at Roodt Architects.

ARTBANK NEWS

Our Story - Cradock Taxi Rank, Eastern Cape

Luthando Ndabeni is a South African self-taught visual artist who specialises in a variety of mediums such as acrylic, pastel, charcoal, and graphite. Born in Gqeberha and raised in Burgersdorp and Cradock where he is currently based, his work reflects his everyday life experiences as a young black South African. His approach varies from hyper realistic to abstract. As a scholar of theology his works comprise of african identity crisis and cultural experiences, and praxis of an ordinary human being in South Africa.

Image: Luthando Ndabeni. Artwork
Title: Our Story. Year created: 2023.
Mural located: Cradock Taxi Rank, Eastern Cape.

Over the edge - Botlokwa Village, Malapani, Limpopo

Jonas Mailula is a South African fine artist. He studied as a visual Artist at Capricorn FET College and obtain a diploma in Art and Design. As a student Jonas won the first price in the art and craft stall in entrepreneur competitions at the College. He is a recipient of first price award in 2006 for Mapungubwe Art competition for Department of Arts and Culture in Limpopo. In 2008/9 he was a finalist for Absa L'atelier competition. In 2021 he was a finalist for Sasol New signature art competition.

Image: Jonas Mailula. Artwork
Title: Over the edge. Year created: 2023 Mural located: Botlokwa Village, Malapani, Limpopo.

Exhibition News

Exhibition: transition • liminality • adaptation

Dates: 16 March 2023 – 1 May 2023

Venue: Oliewenhuis Art Museum (**Annex Gallery**)

This exhibition was curated by the Art Museum Guides of Oliewenhuis. Artworks on exhibition were selected from Oliewenhuis permanent collection and ArtBankSA collection.

Exhibition: *Between Meaning and Reality: The Art Bank of South Africa 2022 New Acquisitions Exhibition*

Dates: 30 March – 4 June 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (**Main Building**)

“Living is keeping the absurd alive. Keeping it alive is above all contemplating it” – Albert Camus. The annual Free State exhibition of the ArtBankSA showcased the best of South African contemporary art by emerging artists. Exploring the meaning of life and the things we value, the exhibition featured artworks selected and purchased from the 2022 submission window by the ArtbankSA.

Exhibition: *The Power of Representation*

Venue: Oliewenhuis Art Museum

In aligning with the International Museum Day theme, “The power of Museums”, Oliewenhuis Art Museum curated this exhibition in the permanent exhibition space. It was a visual fest, and the entire Permanent Collection was re-curated. This exhibition explored the power of art, how it communicates and the *power of representation* through (among other ways) juxtaposing older artworks in the collection with newer contemporary artworks.

Exhibition: *This is us: Celebrating 29 Years of Freedom*

Dates: 26 April – 30 July 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (**Reservoir**)

The exhibition was dedicated to the working class, to those who have fought for democracy and restoration of human dignity and for those who faced imprisonment by poverty. Featuring artworks from the ArtbankSA collection, the exhibition spotlighted the mundane lives of South Africans, mothers, fathers, children, and workers. Victims of a capitalist world bent on keeping the poor, poor; families and individuals who struggle to meet their basic needs trapped in debt bondage and forced labour.

Exhibition: *Breath.Body.Art: Museums, Sustainability and Well-Being*

Dates: 12 May - 25 June 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (**Annex Gallery**)

This special exhibition was curated in celebration of International Museum Day 2023, titled *Breath. Body. Art: Museums, Sustainability and Well-Being*. Artworks in this exhibition were selected from Oliewenhuis Art Museum’s permanent collection and the ArtBankSA collection.

Exhibition: *Learning through Art: The museum as classroom* Curated by the Education Officer at Oliewenhuis Art Museum, **Yolanda de Kock.**

Dates: 22 June – 20 August 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum
This exhibition was a visual celebration of South African artists and artworks for everyone to enjoy, with a special focus on the Grade 10 – 12 Visual Art curriculum. Artworks were handpicked to optimise the learning experience for the learners so they can have the luxury to view works that are discussed in the classroom. The exhibition was curated from the Oliewenhuis Museum permanent collection, complimented by artwork loans courtesy of Sanlam Art Collection.

OLIEWENHUIS NEWS

Exhibition: *Let there be light: In plain sight*
 Curated by the Collections Manager at Oliewenhuis Art Museum, Sepadi Moruthane.

Dates: 29 June – 30 July 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (Annex Gallery)

In a world full of adversity and uncertainty, everything is in plain sight for everyone to see.

Let there be light: In plain sight, employed the analogy of sight and light by drawing inspiration from colorful composite abstract artworks from Oliewenhuis permanent collection and ArtBankSA collection, to engage visitors, patrons, educators, and students alike to see art for what it is. As we occasionally wonder, are amazed, laugh, and even cry about what life presents us, *Let there be light: In plain sight* finds expression in the open interpretation of the good, the bad, and the ugly that life presents to us.

Exhibition: 34th Annual Sophia Gray Memorial Exhibition

Dates: 31 August – 01 October 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (Main Building)

The 34th Laureate, Nadia Tromp is the founder of Ntsika Architects. The Department of Architecture, University of the Free State has hosted the annual Sophia Gray Memorial Lecture and Exhibition at Oliewenhuis Art Museum since 1989.

Exhibition: *Threads of Visual Narratives: Traditional Artistry, Contemporary Art and National Heritage*

Dates: 25 May 2023 – 3 December 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (1st floor of Main Building)

An inter-disciplinary display of collected heritage items of the National Museum.

Exhibition: *New Breed Art Competition Exhibition 2023*

Dates: 12 October - 19 November 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (Main Building)

PH Attorneys, in partnership with the National Museum, annually invites emerging Free State artists to enter the New Breed Art Competition with the aim of encouraging these artists to take a step towards being discovered as a 'new breed' of artist. The exhibition of selected artworks was on show from 12 October until 19 November 2023.

Exhibition: *The Umabatha series by Lucky Madlo Sibiyi and The White Monday Disaster series by Cecil Skotnes*

Dates: 26 October – 26 November 2023 **Venue:** Oliewenhuis Art Museum (Annex Gallery)

The Umabatha series by Lucky Madlo Sibiyi and *The White Monday Disaster series* by Cecil Skotnes, both from Oliewenhuis Museum permanent collection, was exhibited in the Annex Gallery on the first floor of Oliewenhuis. These exquisite woodcuts print series were exhibited together as Lucky Madlo Sibiyi was not only influenced, but also taught by Cecil Skotnes, one of the main pioneers of modern art in South Africa.

COLLECTIONS & LIBRARY NEWS

Images: A variety of colourful beadwork from different southern African cultures such as the Khoisan, Xhosa, Zulu, and Sotho were showcased at Langenhovenpark Public Library as part of the display, *Beadwork of SA*.

Images: Two tractors from the History Collection, the Rumely Oil Pull and Case, formed part of the *Sentraal Vrystaat Veterane Trekker- en Enjin Klub* outside exhibition showcasing a variety of vintage tractors and engines at this year's Bloem Show – the exhibition ended up winning the trophy for best outside exhibitor.

Images: A selection of clocks and watches from the History Collection were on display as part of the exhibition: *A Moment in Time: instruments that measure and show time*

COLLECTIONS & LIBRARY NEWS

Heritage Month: The sacred art and heritage of Basotho *litema* and *morella* wall decoration

The Sacred art and heritage of Basotho *litema* and *morella* wall decoration, an exhibition at the First Raadsaal and Wagon Museum in collaboration with the **Department of Architecture at the University of the Free State** featured various panels showcasing different designs and colour schemes. *Litema* (pronounced di-te-ma) is a form of mural art Basotho women use to decorate their homes with, predominantly the exterior walls.

Traditionally, the wall is hand plastered with *dagha*, a mixture of clay soil, water and cow-dung, after which the *litema* designs are engraved onto the still-wet top layer of plaster. Once the *dagha* has dried, the designs are painted in bright colours, called *morella*, that add a colourful finish to the *litema*. The tradition of *litema* mural art originated long ago, with archaeological excavations at Sotho-Tswana sites revealing evidence that *litema* and *morella* have been practised for centuries, long predating the tradition of Ndebele mural painting that has been globally popularised.

Image: As part of the National Museum's Youth Day Event, *My Family Tree*, hosted at the First Raadsaal and Wagon Museum, Elmar du Plessis (Collections Manager) encouraged Grade 6 learners from Lesedi Primary School to value their family photos and demonstrated to them the correct way to handle, care for, and store old family photos; the idea of starting their own "memory box" with photos, family documents and other keepsakes were also highlighted.

MUSEUM NEWS

Long Service Awards

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Ornitologie
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Palaeontology
Paleontologie
Lefapha la Bophelo ba kgale

Human sciences Geesteswetenskappe Mahlale a Botho

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Tsamaiso ya Dipokello le Laeborari

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Lefapha la Bonono

History
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Lefapha la Histori

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Museum Satellites & Programmes · Museumsatelliete & Programme · Makala a Musiamo le Mananeo

ArtBank of South Africa / ArtBank van Suid-Afrika / Banka ya Bonono ya Afrika Borwa · First Raadsaal Museum / Eerste Raadsaalmuseum / Musiamo wa First Raadsaal · Florisbad Quaternary Research Station / Florisbad Kwaternêre Navorsingstasie / Seteishene sa Diphuputso Florisbad · Freshford House Museum / Freshford-huismuseum / Musiamo wa Freshford · Oliewenhuis Art Museum / Oliewenhuis-kunsmuseum / Musiamo wa Bonono wa Oliewenhuis · Wagon Museum / Waenhuismuseum / Musiamo wa Dipalangwang

Die Nasionale Museum - 'n natuurhistoriese, kultuurhistoriese en kunsmuseum - is in 1878 gestig en is 'n Verklaarde Kulturele instelling wat onder die Departement Kuns & Kultuur ressorteer en deur 'n raad beheer word. Die missie van die Nasionale Museum is om deur uitnemende navorsing, bewaring, opvoeding en uitstallings ons natuur- en kultuurerfenis en 'n aangename ervaring aan alle mense te bied.

The National Museum - a natural history, cultural history and art museum - was established in 1878 and is a Declared Cultural Institution which resorts under the Department of Arts and Culture and is governed by a council. The mission of the National Museum is to provide heritage resources and an enjoyable experience to all people through quality research, conservation, education and exhibitions.

Musiamo wa Setjhaba - histori ya tlhaho, histori ya setso le musiamo wa bonono - o ile wa hlongwa ka 1878 mme o Totobatswa e le Setsi sa Setso se welang le ho tlaleha tlasa Lefapha la Bonono le setso mme se buswa ke lekgotla. Mmeshene wa Musiamo wa Setjhaba ke ho nehelana ka mehlodi ya bojalefa le letlotlo hape le boiphihlelo ba natefelo ho batho bohle ka tsela ya diphuputso tsa boleng, paballo le tshireletso, thuto le dipontsho.